

D5.3 - REPORT ON PRIORITISED POLICY ACTIONS FOR THE CASE STUDY SECTORS

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Abstract

The transition from linear fossil-based systems to circular and bio-based systems represents an opportunity and a suitable pathway for achieving several SDGs. Indeed, circular bio-based systems depict a great opportunity to reconcile sustainable long-term growth with environmental protection through the prudent use of renewable resources for industrial purposes. This needed transition is a complex process, which does not simply require innovative technologies from the supply-side, but also societal transformations based on a multi-actor process. The circular bioeconomy meta-sector may be a good candidate to put forward a new economic model, which requires transformative policies, purposeful innovation, access to finance, risk-taking capacity as well as new and sustainable business models and markets. However, a critical assessment of the environmental, social and economic impacts of the current linear fossil-based economy, as well as of the improvement potential associated with circular bio-based systems, is needed to underpin the identification of policy priorities. Bearing this in mind, SUSTRACK is a three-year project aimed at supporting policymakers in their efforts to develop sustainable pathways to replace fossil and carbon-intensive systems with sustainable circular and biobased systems (at the EU and regional scale), contributing to achieving the European Green Deal's objectives. This will be done by: identifying environmental, economic and social limits of a linear carbon-intensive and fossil-based economy; improving existing assessment methodologies; assessing the environmental, social and economic impacts of the EU's current linear fossil-based economy; comparing multiple transition scenarios focusing on the most carbon intensive sectors; identifying priorities according to scenarios analysed in the project and develop guidelines and policy recommendations.

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This public report provides an overview of the work conducted within tasks 5.1. and 5.2. Specifically, it presents results of two literature reviews and the conceptual approach to design policies for a transition towards a circular and bio-based economy (CBBE). Furthermore, the report documents policy co-creation workshops, that took place in several stakeholder events conducted in SUSTRACK: the INSPIRE, DESIGN, and IMPLEMENT. These events involved stakeholders from the four sectors considered in SUSTRACK (construction, textiles, plastics, and chemicals) and selected case studies. Finally, the report documents the results of a survey conducted to prioritise policy approaches for the CBBE transition.

Regarding the project's stakeholder engagement activities, three major conferences were organised to support the co-creation and validation of strategies for transitioning to a Circular Bio-Based Economy (CBBE).

The INSPIRE Conference, held on 16 November 2023, brought together 87 participants for a full-day event. This initial conference served as a platform to introduce the project's objectives and engage stakeholders in early discussions around bioeconomy transition pathways.

The DESIGN Conference followed with a series of sectoral workshops conducted between 4 and 12 July 2024, culminating in a closing event on 25 September 2024. The workshops attracted a total of 179 participants, while 123 attended the final event. During this phase, the project explored three key dimensions of the transition—policy, sustainability, and market—across four sectors. Stakeholders contributed to identifying challenges, sharing good practices, and formulating recommendations for each dimension, sector, and case study.

The IMPLEMENT Conference took place from 27 February to 6 March 2025 with sectoral workshops and concluded with a closing event on 21 March 2025. A total of 158 participants joined the workshops, and 43 attended the closing session. This phase focused on presenting two policy sets for each sector. Participants assessed the strengths and weaknesses of each policy set, providing valuable feedback that will inform the final policy recommendations.

To validate the proposed policy options, a survey was conducted to identify, assess and improve policy instruments to boost the transition in these sectors. The proposed policy instruments fulfilled different functions, one promoting the transition and the other one limiting the resource use.

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1. INTRODUCTION

The EU intends to transition toward a circular and bio-based economy (CBBE). This transition seeks to replace fossil resources and make-use-dispose type of economy with the help of strategies such as reduce, reuse, and recycle ("R-strategies") and with an efficient and sustainable use of renewable resources such as biomass. These measures shall contribute to climate protection, competitiveness, supply security, sustainable resource management and food security. To support policymakers in this transition, the EU Horizon research project SUSTRACK works on identifying related policy priorities. SUSTRACK focuses on the sectors construction, plastics, chemicals, and textiles.

To outline policy priorities and to support the transition, SUSTRACK undertakes several steps including case study analyses (WP3), economic modelling (WP4) and a policy analysis (WP5). This report documents intermediate results of activities in WP4 and WP5. These activities include a literature analysis, stakeholder discussions and a survey.

To ensure that policy recommendations are both relevant and actionable, the project adopted a case study-based approach (for a detailed description, see D3.1). Case studies were selected across four key sectors (construction, plastics, chemicals, and textiles) providing a diverse and representative view of the bioeconomy landscape. Hence, the policy analysis focuses on and is structured along these four sectors. Accordingly, engaging stakeholders focused on experts that are directly involved in or affected by these sectors. This way, the project seeks to examine the applicability of the policy options for the specific case studies and possibly customise them.

The objective of the stakeholder engagement process (stakeholder discussions and survey) was to co-create, validate, and adjust proposed policy actions to the different sectors.

The process of designing, validating, and adjusting policy actions covered three major conferences dedicated to the following objectives:

- During the INSPIRE Conference (November 2023), stakeholders were introduced to the project's vision and objectives. This initial engagement laid the groundwork for collaborative exploration and helped identify key themes and expectations.
- The DESIGN Conference (July-September 2024) deepened the analysis through sectoral workshops and a closing event. Here, stakeholders examined the transition to a CBBE through three dimensions—policy, sustainability, and market. For each sector and case study, participants identified challenges, shared good practices, and formulated preliminary recommendations.
- In the IMPLEMENT Conference (February-March 2025), the focus shifted to action. Two policy sets per sector were presented, reflecting the insights gathered in earlier phases. Stakeholders assessed the strengths and weaknesses of each policy option, providing critical feedback that informed the final prioritisation of policy actions.

This iterative and participatory process ensured that the resulting policy recommendations are not only evidence-based but also aligned with stakeholder needs and sectoral realities. The outcomes of these activities contribute directly to shaping a more coherent and effective policy framework for advancing the CBBE in Europe.

To validate the proposed policy options, a survey was conducted to identify, assess, and improve policy instruments to boost the transition in these sectors. The proposed policy instruments fulfilled different functions, one promoting the transition and the other one limiting the resource

use. Subsequently, survey takers were asked to indicate their preferences between two proposed policy approaches, each comprising different policy instruments.

2. METHODS

Identifying policies for a CBBE transition is challenging for many reasons. Among others, the transition is highly complex. It affects many policy areas (climate, industry, energy, environment, trade, agriculture, and forestry etc.) and touches on a wide range of existing policies. In addition to this, given the limited progress regarding the transition so far, more ambitious, and possibly new policies may be required.

To address this challenge, the policy analysis in SUSTRACK has followed a multi-step pathway that combines different methods. Table 1 provides an overview of the steps and the related methods.

Table 1: Methodology for identifying policies for a CBBE transition

Working step	Aim	Method	Related chapter or deliverable
Create a working definition of a CBBE	Narrow down tangible elements of the transition to focus and structure the subsequent policy analysis	Literature review: literature on circular economy and bioeconomy	Deliverable 5.1
Review policies	Identify existing policies, policy gaps and proposals for adjusting or new policies	Literature review: literature on transition policies in the SUSTRACK sectors	Chapter 3
Selection of policy options	Select a limited number of key transition policy options for each sector to enable stakeholder discussions	Literature review and analysis: environmental and resource economics literature	Chapter 5
First discussion of policy options with stakeholders (DESIGN conference)	Identify general strengths and weaknesses of the identified policy options	Focus group discussions	Chapter 6
Second discussion of policy options with stakeholders (IMPLEMENT conference)	Identify country specific opportunities, challenges and needs for adjustments of identified policies in each SUSTRACK sector	Focus group discussions	Chapter 7

Prioritisation of policy options	Identify priorities for policy actions in the SUSTRACK sectors	Survey (quantitative)	Chapter 8
Supplementary material: Discussion of model assumptions with stakeholders	Validate assumptions for modelling economic and ecological effects of the transition toward a CBBE	Focus group discussions	Chapter 4

2.1. Creating a Working Definition of a Circular Bio-based Economy

The CBBE is an abstract and notoriously fuzzy concept, not only because it is still in an early stage, but also many different visions and expectations are reported in the literature. To identify policy options that effectively advance the transition and contribute to CBBE goals, a clear definition is needed. This helps to navigate through many policies and policy options that are related to the transformation challenge. SUSTRACK [deliverable 5.1](#) provides a detailed account of the working definition and the methodical steps behind it. Figure 1 depicts a graphical illustration of the definition.

The definition’s purpose is to structure the various goals and means associated with the CBBE in order to identify leverage points for policymakers to create effective and consistent policies. Basically, the definition describes how the abstract goals and principles of the CBBE can be broken down into “policy means”. These means, such as recycling or using residues, provide a more tangible basis for designing policy instruments than rather vague overarching goals or principles such as sustainable resource management or efficient resource use.

Figure 1: SUSTRACK working definition of a circular bio-based economy

The policy leverage points (light green segment) most often mentioned in the reviewed literature include cascading use, R' strategies such as recycling and reuse, and the use of resources such as biomass and wastes. These CBBE elements provided the basis to guide and structure the policy review.

2.2. Creating policies for the transition

Step 1: Review of literature on circular economy and bioeconomy

In SUSTRACK, a framework was developed to review and identify new policy instruments that can help the transition to a more CBBE. This approach requires the identification of policy instruments in a literature review and characterising the instruments according to the following 4 aspects:

- 1) **CBBE principles** which include firstly, reduction of greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions either by decreasing and phasing out the use of fossil resources; secondly, the principle of resource use efficiency; thirdly, the decoupling of resource use from economic growth; fourthly, support material and/or energy use efficiency; fifthly stimulate circularity instruments such as stimulate the use of alternative and renewable resources (e.g. biomass). These principles are used to describe the instrument and explain how it addresses one or more of these principles.
- 2) **The CBBE means refer to the use of biomass and waste, residues, or by-products as well as cascade use and Rs** (reduce, reuse, refuse, recycle, rethink, repair).
- 3) **Providing solutions to overcome specific barriers** to transition. These barriers were discussed in D5.1 already and were categorised as 1) cultural, 2) environmental, 3) economic, 4) governance, 5) structural and 6) technical ones.
- 4) **Types of policy instruments**. These are categorised according to:
 1. **Direct regulation** - a command and control approach using mandatory standards and licences that require people/companies/market actors to change their behaviour and penalise them if they are found to be non-compliant. Examples of direct regulatory instruments in the bioeconomy include quotas, mandates, product standards, targets (quotas addressing government/economic sectors), green procurement rules and permitting and zoning instruments (e.g. territorial instrument such as drink water protection area or Nitrogen sensitive area). We also include here eligibility criteria such as biomass sustainability criteria in the EU-Renewable Energy Directive.
 2. **Economic instruments** - includes all instruments that change incentives (taxes, subsidies), but also quantity restrictions (tradable) quota, tariff rate quota), and charges. These instruments provide incentives for people to change their behaviour voluntarily (e.g. based on their own rational cost-benefit calculations). So, it includes all instruments that leave the decision about resource uses in the hands of market participants while changing prices for using a resource. Price changes can be induced directly via taxes, fees, charges, subsidies etc. or indirectly via tradeable permits.
 3. **Voluntary approaches** - could include codes of good practice, self-regulation and other industry-led initiatives. Financial incentive schemes could be part of these instruments. These approaches typically encourage rather than force people or companies to adopt the desired behaviour. The voluntary carbon market is an example.
 4. **Information and advice sharing systems or information instruments** - measure to raise awareness education and facilitate changes in behaviour.

5. **Market-based signalling approaches** - labelling, traceability, voluntary certification schemes and farm assurance schemes. These approaches are often related to informational problems (lack of information about product quality and food safety) hindering the proper functioning of markets.
6. Other measures/instruments not in the categories above such as platforms for collaboration, behavioural influencing instruments (e.g. nudging).

To identify the policy instruments a literature review was done. This first step involved the identification of relevant references in literature search in Scopus. The following search terms were used:

- policy/ policy instrument(s)
- transformation/ transition path/ pathways
- circular/bioeconomy
- incentives / pricing/regulation
- ... each combined with bioeconomy/ circular economy/ circular bioeconomy
- ... each combined with a sector name: construction, textiles, chemicals, and plastics

This resulted in a list of around 2000 relevant references. This list of references was then further processed with the AI tool ASReview to limit the list of references further to around 30-50 references per sector. The final references were then used to extract the good example policy instruments included in the database presented in Annex I in this report and also available through an excel document.

Step 2: Review of literature from resource and environmental economics on efficient resource use

In addition to literature on the circular economy and the bioeconomy, literature from resource and environmental economics was reviewed. The rationale for this was to:

- structure the subsequent policy analysis, selection, and prioritisation with the help of economic theory and
- include additional policy options from resource management research that are not necessarily framed under the umbrella terms of circularity or bioeconomy.

Resource economics examines how natural stocks of non-renewable natural resources can be exploited in an optimal (efficient) way, thus dealing with topics like overusing natural resources. Environmental economics has a similar focus but in relation to renewable natural resources such as biomass, which makes it relevant in regard to developing a bioeconomy.

Since CBBE-related framings and keywords are not widely used in economics, the literature review applied the snowball method:

- First, a Scopus search was conducted based on the CBBE-terms circularity, bioeconomy, and recycling. Scopus search results were sorted both according to the number of citations and relevance.
- Second, relevant results were included in the review and screened for further relevant references with the focus on seminal (widely cited) and review articles presenting the overall findings of the field. Relevance was determined by examining abstracts and keywords.
- Additionally, a second snowballing-based Scopus search was conducted based on the search terms “greenhouse gas reduction material uses” and “emissions reduction material uses”, as this is an important focus of SUSTRACK that turned out

- to be not covered extensively in the literature identified in the first snowballing-based search.
- Finally, a small number of selected literatures was added by the authors known to be relevant to the subject of CBBE transition based on their research experience.

The selected references are documented in Annex II.

Step 3: Selection of policy options

Identifying policy priorities can be facilitated by various means, such as multi-criteria analysis with stakeholders, where different policy instruments are compared based on their strengths and weaknesses. However, in the context of creating a CBBE, such a method would be challenging. The high number of policy options revealed in the review (step 2), unclear visions of how the CBBE should look like, and trade-offs arising between the various CBBE goals make it difficult to elicit clear and consistent stakeholder preferences about policies.

Therefore, SUSTRACK created a customised method to select consistent policy options for the transition based on (1) the prioritised transition barriers identified in WP1 (D1.3), an analysis of analytical challenges associated with the transition and possible solutions to these challenges. These solutions were either based on results from the literature review of step 2 or represent pragmatic heuristics. One key decision within this process was to prioritise not single policy instruments but, more fundamentally, between the policy types, direct regulation and market-based regulation. Both types include different potentially interchangeable instruments. For example, in a market-based policy approach, greenhouse-gas emissions can be reduced using taxes, emissions trading systems or subsidies. For each policy type, exemplary policy instruments were selected from the literature review conducted in step 2. This means that information and preferences collected from stakeholders in the subsequent steps (stakeholder discussions, survey) should be considered (and were assessed) more in regard to what they tell about types of policy interventions instead of single instruments. A detailed description of the full process of policy selection and underlying assumptions is documented in Chapter 5 of this report.

Step 4: Stakeholder discussions

Stakeholder engagement was designed as a structured, multi-stage process to co-create and prioritise policy actions for the case study sectors (textile, chemicals, plastics, and construction). To achieve this, a series of four high-level conferences—INSPIRE, DESIGN, IMPLEMENT, and DEPLOY—were organised, each building on the outcomes of the previous stage. These events provided a dedicated platform for dialogue with a wide range of stakeholders, including policymakers, industry representatives, researchers, NGOs, and citizens. The conferences combined plenary presentations, expert contributions, and participatory workshops, ensuring that the perspectives of diverse actors were systematically captured and integrated into the policy co-creation process.

The INSPIRE Conference initiated the process by presenting SUSTRACK's comprehensive literature review and the main analytical findings that served as the backbone for stakeholder discussions. Particular emphasis was placed on exploring the existing EU monitoring framework and its capacity to track the progress of a circular bio-based transition. Stakeholders were also introduced to case studies and preliminary findings, which served as concrete illustrations of sectoral challenges and opportunities. In addition, a first set of policy scenarios was presented and discussed, creating a shared knowledge base for subsequent engagement phases. Importantly, discussions during this stage also focused on identifying the limits, barriers, drivers, benefits, and gaps associated with

the sustainable transition, providing critical insights into the enabling and constraining factors that must be addressed in future policy design.

The DESIGN Conference further developed this foundation by focusing on the co-creation of transition pathways. An overview of the selected SUSTRACK value chains was presented, including process descriptions, market data, and relevant policy instruments. Expert case studies provided inspiration and highlighted practical experiences, good practices, and barriers encountered in moving towards a circular bio-based economy. The workshops facilitated in this phase generated a wide set of recommendations across policy, environmental, societal, and economic dimensions. The outcomes were consolidated in the closing event “Pathway to DESIGN the Circular Bio-Based Transition”, which transformed the workshop discussions into a set of preliminary policy recommendations. These results provide valuable input to the ongoing revision of the European Bioeconomy Strategy and to future policy developments.

The IMPLEMENT Conference marked the transition from vision-building to the concrete exploration of policy options. Keynote speakers outlined the policy landscape and future visions for the transformation of the case study sectors. Policy options identified by SUSTRACK were presented and assessed collaboratively with stakeholders, who discussed their strengths and weaknesses as well as potential additional approaches. The closing event “From Vision to Implementation: Shaping Policies to Boost Circular Bio-Based Transition” synthesised the outcomes of this process. It presented the main insights from the workshop series, introduced the monitoring methods and tools developed by SUSTRACK to support stakeholder action, and highlighted key findings from eleven sectoral case studies. The ultimate aim of this phase was to offer actionable knowledge and policy options capable of advancing the circular bio-based transition across Europe.

The process concluded with the DEPLOY Conferences, which shifted the focus from European-level visioning to national and local-level implementation. Deployment workshops were held in Italy, Spain, Germany, Slovakia, the Netherlands, and Belgium, making available to local stakeholders the resources, tools, and policy instruments developed throughout the project. These workshops facilitated the translation of European strategies into national contexts, bridging policy design and implementation across different governance levels. Stakeholders were supported in applying system thinking to reinforce the transition, in shaping policy instruments for sector-specific deployment, and in acquiring knowledge of project-developed methods, resources, and tools. As the final stage of the engagement process, the DEPLOY Conferences ensured continuity between the policy co-creation phases and their practical application within specific country contexts.

Step 5: Prioritisation of policy options

To identify and assess policy priorities that can accelerate the transition towards a CBBE in key sectors, a structured survey was conducted. The first step of the survey methodology included the preparation and validation of a questionnaire, drawing on insights from the INSPIRE, the DESIGN and the IMPLEMENT conferences.

The survey was programmed using Limesurvey, a robust open-source tool widely used in research. An internal test phase with consortium partners led to refinements based on their feedback, ensuring clarity and relevance of the final version.

The survey was launched during the IMPLEMENT Conference and distributed to various stakeholders through different channels, including:

- Project partners and advisory board members shared it with their networks;
- SUSTRACK promoted it via its website and social media channels;

- Additional outreach included emails to parallel project mailing lists, a news item on the EuBioNet website, and a post on the ECOSYSTEMX LinkedIn channel.

The survey consisted of several sections. The first part was related to the generalities of the respondents (category of stakeholder, country of origin, size of the organisation, and sector represented). Participants could select one of the following sectors: construction, plastics, chemicals, or textiles, and had the option to repeat the survey for a different sector.

Subsequent sections focused on assessing and ranking selected policy instruments that could either promote this transition or help limit resource use. To simplify the complexity of this policy challenge, the survey was structured around two overarching policy topics (as indicated in Chapter 5):

- Approach A: Boosting Circularity
- Approach B: Ensuring Sustainability of Biomass Use

Each approach included a set of policy instruments that reflected different types of interventions—either direct regulation or market-based mechanisms. These instruments were presented through structured storylines, allowing respondents to understand their potential strengths and weaknesses. Participants were first asked to rate each policy instrument individually using a scale from “fully recommend” to “not recommend at all.” Subsequently, they were asked to select the approach (Approach A or Approach B) they would recommend to support the transition in the four selected sectors and to further guide policymaking. Respondents were also asked to prioritise all challenges of each cluster as major, moderate, minor, or not a challenge.

3. LITERATURE REVIEW: RESULTS

3.1. Approach to Identify Policy Solutions to Transition to a Circular Bio-based Economy

The first literature review resulted in a database of 98 policy instruments which is included in Annex I.

Good example instruments typically aimed at phasing out fossil resources include the introduction of an ETS (Emissions Trading System) that is continuously broadened to a wider number of economic sectors and industries, and the introduction of a carbon tax/pricing system for a specific set of mostly fossil carbon products. In the EU, an ETS is already in place but is limited to the energy sector, specific energy-intensive manufacturing industries, as well as aircraft operators flying within the EU and departing to Switzerland or the United Kingdom. From 2024, the EU ETS also covers emissions from maritime transport. The EU plans to examine a possible inclusion of emissions from municipal waste incineration from 2028 (Art. 30 (7) Directive 2003/87/EC). Besides the EU ETS, similar systems also exist outside the EU, such as in Japan. In addition to ETS and other carbon pricing instruments, the development of national and regional strategies or plans are also widely seen as necessary to guide these regions towards a carbon-neutral future.

There are many policy instruments that stimulate more circular practices, which mostly target waste management and often include EU legislation or the national and regional transposition of EU directives such as the Waste Framework Directive, the EU Landfill Directive, the EU Packaging Directive, and the Single-Use Plastics Directive. There are also several examples of specific national and local policy approaches to enhance circular practices, such as the Erp Italia Tessile

and Cardato Recycled initiatives aimed at enhancing circularity in the textiles sector, the Packaging Law in Germany, the specific subsidy for gasification of waste streams in the Netherlands, and the repair bonus in Saxony.

Specifically for plastics, many EU-wide as well as national laws are in place, not only aiming at recycling and more circular use of plastics, but also at reducing plastic waste and especially losses of (micro-)plastics to the environment.

Several example instruments are included in the database that aim to stimulate the use and market penetration of biobased products in different sectors. For this, action plans at national and regional level are proposed, but also measures such as setting quotas for biomaterial use in certain sectors or promoting uptake through public procurement.

Instruments stimulating more resource-use efficiency can focus on recycling but may also enhance the circulation of scarce resources, such as phosphorus. For example, the German Sewage Sludge Ordinance sets a recycling quota of 50-80% by 2029. Resource-use efficiency can be stimulated through a wide number of instruments, several of which are included in the database. Recycling quotas for waste are often set in national and regional laws or only as indicative targets in strategies or action plans. Germany, for example, set strict recycling targets for municipal waste of 50% by 2020, rising to 65% by 2035.

At the EU level, several instruments are already in place, planned, or proposed. Examples of current instruments at the EU level include the Ecodesign Directive, which is proposed to be extended to more sectors, the EU Ecolabel Regulation, and Extended Producer Responsibility schemes (EPRs). The latter aims to hold manufacturers responsible for the waste generated by their products. By requiring manufacturers to take back and recycle their products, EPR schemes can incentivise them to design more sustainable products and reduce waste.

The database includes many examples of policy instruments that specifically aim at making the textiles sector more sustainable by stimulating more circular uses, but also by, for example, discouraging fast fashion and stimulating recycling, reuse, and repair.

The database also includes three types of instruments focusing on stimulating cascading use: putting (higher) taxes on the use of virgin materials, applying a VAT reduction on secondary material use, and prioritising wood uses for traditional forestry products before it is used for energy generation.

For detailed information and inspiration on good example policy instruments collected in the literature review, consult Annex I or the separate Excel file of this database. The information collected in the database has served as an important basis for the compilation of policy options and policy priorities for the transition towards a CBBE.

3.2. Resource and Environmental Economics

This section documents key findings from the review of literature from resource and environmental economics related to circularity and the bioeconomy. This review had two purposes: (1) Structure the policy analysis in SUSTRACK and (2) identify additional policy options that have not yet been associated with the CBBE transition.

3.2.1. Insights for structuring the policy analysis

The following list provides an overview on key information that was collected from the review to help advance the analysis and create effective, efficient and consistent policies for the transition in line with EU CBBE goals. For how this information was further processed in Sustrack, see Chapter 5 on the selection of policy options.

- Even if a complete recycling of materials would be technically feasible, it would often not be desirable. This is because recycling itself requires resources. Excessive recycling possibly consumes more resources than it saves (Baumol 1977; Wagner / Schlummer 2020). It can also cause substantial pollution and social problems (Tian et al. 2020; Gachenga 2022; Johansson 2023). As optimal recycling levels depend on the ratio of resources invested and resources saved and many more variables that may change over time (pollution, relative scarcity of resources involved etc.), it is very challenging to determine optimal recycling rates (e.g., Andersen 2007; Kinnaman 2014). The conclusion for Sustrack is that it may be helpful to also consider policy options that do not set politically defined recycling targets but rather change market conditions in a way that efficient levels of recycling emerge from these modified markets (internalisation of external effects that distort recycling markets).
- It is very challenging to decide what rate of resource extraction is inefficient (or unsustainable) (Krautkramer 1998). In efficient markets, resource extraction is efficient in the long run (Hotelling 1931), which can also be considered to meet relevant but not all criteria of sustainability (e.g., Krautkraemer 1998). This means that inefficient and possibly unsustainable resource use can be explained by market failures that provide leverage points for policy action (Da Cunha 2007). However, there are several market failures potentially related to resource extraction and use, making it very difficult to determine whether resources are actually overused and to what extent (Devarajan / Fisher 1981; Grimaud / Rouge 2003; Gaudet 2007, Kronenberg 2008). Over time, the focus of research on inefficient resource use has shifted away from the risk of premature depletion to climate change and other environmental impacts from resource extraction and use (Krautkraemer 2005). This implies that it may be more important to reduce climate and environmental impacts associated with resource extraction and use than to reduce resource consumption itself. This emphasises the climate mitigation goals of the CBBE. On the other hand, decoupling is also considered to be an important goal in both EU policy documents and the CBBE literature (see step 1 in the method section of this review). The conclusion for Sustrack policy analysis is that selected policies have to ensure both GHG reduction and limit total resource use.
- The need to employ policies that limit total resource use is also emphasised by studies from Bongers/Casas (2022) and Zink (2017). They show that even very high recycling rates do not necessarily curb extraction and consumption of virgin raw materials in a growing economy. Due to circular economy rebound effects, also other circular practices like re-use can lead to additional resource consumption. Therefore, the so-called R's might be a valuable element of a CBBE, but they are not sufficient for the transition to reach its goal. In Sustrack, therefore, a wider range of transition policies is considered that also addresses total consumption.
- The CBBE transition is burdened with several uncertainties and trade-offs. It was already mentioned above that it is difficult to determine an optimal level of recycling. This uncertainty is aggravated by the unclear policy definition of the CBBE goal "resource efficiency": If resource efficiency only refers to natural

resources, then efficiency (input/output-ratio) can be improved by employing more labour, e.g., for manual collection and sorting of waste. Increasing labour, however, might lead to an inefficiently high level of labour in the economy. Hence, increased natural resource efficiency would come at the cost of decreased efficiency in the total economy. This is only one example of unclear contours of the CBBE transition that leave room for different policy approaches. Therefore, before selecting policy options, ways to address these uncertainties have to be found. Another challenge are the manifold trade-offs potentially embedded in the transition. For example, if natural resource use efficiency is increased at the cost of inefficient labour use, this could increase product prices and thus weaken EU competitiveness (trade-off between (natural resource) efficiency and competitiveness). Several more uncertainties and trade-offs have to be considered in order to identify effective and efficient policies (see Chapter 5).

- Regarding such trade-offs, one important risk is related to the use of subsidies to support circular and bio-based products. This instrument type is likely to increase resource consumption because it incentivises faster disposal of goods and increases income that can be spent for additional consumption (Hoogmartens et al 2018; Gayanajake/ Iyer-Raniga 2025; Sorenson 2017). This undesired side effect of using subsidies for environmental purposes has already been noted by Baumol/Oates (1988/2005). This shifts the attention to alternative policies and policy leverage points: Instead of subsidising a desired product it may be more efficient (and sustainable) to focus on market failures and internalising them, thereby disincentivising undesired products (i.e., fossil-based products or those containing virgin raw materials) (Sorenson 2017). Another possible conclusion is that if (product or consumption) subsidies are used, these should be coupled with measures that restrict or mitigate total resource use.
- Structuring CBBE policies according to market failures can be a way of dealing with uncertainty, trade-offs and complexity. While intuitive policy making can aggravate trade-offs in complex policy settings (see the above example of using subsidies), deriving policies from market failures can help to build consistent policy sets that increase total resource use efficiency and thereby decrease trade-offs. This can be demonstrated using the example of forest biomass: Current EU policies promote the use of wood for energy under the Renewable Energy Directive (including zero-rating of bioenergy GHG emissions from burning wood in compliance with the directive's sustainability criteria in the EU ETS) to improve competitiveness of this renewable resource. However, policy analyses based on market failures have found under these conditions emissions savings from forest bioenergy in the energy sector will be lower at the margin than carbon losses in the land use sector LULUCF (van Kooten 1995; Lintunen/ Uusivuori 2016). That means that subsidising forest bioenergy aggravates the trade-off between the climate mitigation goals of these sectors, even if it is compliant with RED sustainability criteria. To minimise this trade-off between forest bioenergy and the LULUCF climate target, subsidies have to be removed. This also implies including GHG emissions from burning wood into carbon pricing policies such as EU ETS (ibid.). Research findings that point in the same direction are studies showing that simply increasing the use of forest biomass in sectors like construction or textiles does not reduce but rather increase total GHG emissions in the economy (Hurmekoski et al. 2023). This is because harvesting and processing wood goes along with substantial amounts of by-products that cannot be converted into wood products with long-term carbon storage. This leads to near term emissions that can easily offset or even exceed positive climate effects from wood use. For CBBE policies this means that, again, using subsidies to support the

transition (here: to a more bio-based economy) is risky and potentially counterproductive. If such policies are applied, they should be complemented with measures to limit the total use of biomass.

- It is not sufficient to increase recycling for an economy to become more circular. In some markets like textiles, other circular practices such as re-use are more relevant (Allwood 2014; Thomas 2003). Gajanayake and Iyer-Raniga (2025) emphasise that recycling and landfill diversion should be considered as lower order circular economy strategies because they are prone to rebound and other unintended side effects. Instead, higher order strategies like re-use and repurpose should receive more policy attention.

3.2.2. Additional policy options for the transition

Based on the analysis of market failures, economic studies highlight several policy options to advance the CBBE transition. The following list highlights market-based instruments that often play no prominent role in the CBBE literature (for implications of using this policy type see Chapter 5):

- Resource taxes can slow down the rate of extracting natural resources (Söderholm 2006; Compagnoni 2016; Da Vita 2004; Egger 2024; Hoogmartens et al. 2018; Ekvall et al. 2014). Such taxes are already used in several EU countries (Deserno/ Sterk 2024).
- Pollution or waste taxes can internalise environmental externalities related to resource extraction and waste disposal can also contribute to higher resource efficiency (Huhtala 1999; Lafforgue/ Lorang 2022; Pittel 2010; Sorenson 2017; Dubois 2013; Sahlin et al. 2007; de Weerd 2020; Ekvall et al. 2014; Matheson 2022).
- Carbon pricing is discussed as a means to reduce GHG emissions from material uses of carbon (Aidt et al. 2017; Bataille et al. 2018; Pollitt et al 2020; Cabarnard 2022; De Weerd 2020, 2024; Ooi et al. 2024; Skelton et al. 2017; Zibunas et al. 2022).
- Subsidies for recycling are often encouraged as well (Pittel 2010; Compagnoni 2016; Freire-Gonzalez et al. 2022; Liu / Li 2023; Egger 2024). However, as noted in the previous section, several studies advise not to employ such subsidies to avoid rebound effects.
- For an optimal use of forest biomass in the bioeconomy, a tax-subsidy scheme is proposed, with the tax being levied on carbon emissions from burning biomass and the subsidy supporting carbon removal in the land use sector (Lintunen/ Uusivuori 2016; Schindler et al. 2023).
- Next to internalising environmental externalities, market failures related to innovation should be addressed (Jaffe 2004). This can be facilitated by R&D support including support for scaling up production quantities (similar to feed in tariffs in the energy sector) (Aidt et al 2017; Bataille et al. 2018; Lavee 2007).
- Occasionally, direct (command & control) regulations such as quotas or bans are discussed by some sources. However, the use of such policy instruments is not recommended where a closer analysis is applied. For example, Söderholm and Lundmark (2009) conclude that Sweden's Wood-fibre act from the 1980s, which intended to prioritise wood use, did not enhance inefficient resource use.

4. INSPIRE CONFERENCE

4.1. Overall Structure and Main Objectives

Organised on 16 November 2023, the INSPIRE Conference represented a key milestone in the project's timeline. The event was specifically designed to engage stakeholders with the SUSTRACK project from an early stage and to initiate their active involvement in discussions around the transition towards a CBBE, bridging the project's research findings with ongoing developments and forward-looking perspectives. The conference provided a platform to foster dialogue among diverse stakeholders, aiming to align project results with future policy needs and to contribute to shaping more sustainable pathways for European industry and society.

The main objectives of the conference were multifaceted. Firstly, the event sought to support the development of future policy by presenting SUSTRACK's comprehensive literature review and key findings, which serve as the foundation for the project's broader discussions. An overview of SUSTRACK's outcomes and discoveries was shared, highlighting the main barriers, drivers, benefits, and gaps in the transition toward a more sustainable and CBBE. Additionally, the conference aimed to critically reflect on the existing EU monitoring frameworks, identifying current indicators and methodologies used to assess circularity and sustainability, as well as the limitations and gaps that still need to be addressed. A central part of the event was dedicated to the presentation and discussion of selected case studies and preliminary findings, offering concrete insights into sector-specific challenges and solutions. Finally, participants were actively involved in reviewing and refining the policy scenarios developed within the project, ensuring that SUSTRACK's policy recommendations are both evidence-based and aligned with real-world needs and stakeholder perspectives. These objectives were pursued with a clear focus on ensuring that SUSTRACK's work remains grounded in both scientific evidence and stakeholder realities.

The structure of the conference was designed to facilitate both knowledge sharing and interactive engagement (Figure 2). The event featured two plenary sessions dedicated to presenting the SUSTRACK project, its objectives, activities, and results achieved to date. In addition, four sector-specific co-creation workshops (dedicated to textile, chemical, plastics and construction) were organised in parallel sessions, in which participants making use of interactive tools such as MIRO Board and Mentimeter validated and prioritised specific subtopics, referring to 6 main societal objectives. Furthermore, four additional sector-specific policy scenario workshops were held, also in parallel sessions, with a focus on verifying the robustness of SUSTRACK policy scenarios and collecting further stakeholder inputs regarding policy goals and directions.

Figure 2: Structure of the INSPIRE conference

The outreach strategy for the event was successful in attracting a diverse group of stakeholders, representing the quadruple helix - academia, industry, public authorities, and civil society - with a particular emphasis on the textile, construction, chemicals, and plastics sectors. Participation also included representatives from other EU-funded projects with similar objectives, as well as members of the SUSTRACK Advisory Board. A total of 132 stakeholders registered to attend the INSPIRE Conference. Sectoral representation was fairly balanced, with registrations ranging from 50 in the construction sector to 69 in the chemical sector. Field representation, however, was less even, though not unusual for co-creation events. Of the 132 registrants, 129 disclosed their professional fields. 10 of the respondents work in NGOs or CSOs, while 11 and 33 are from the public and private sectors respectively. The majority, being 66 registered participants, are from academia. In total, 87 of the registered 132 participants took part in the discussions, offering valuable insights and perspectives that enriched the project's work.

To support the delivery and effectiveness of the sessions, a range of tools were employed, including PowerPoint presentations, MIRO Board for collaborative work, and Mentimeter for gathering immediate feedback and supporting prioritisation exercises. Access to the conference factsheet is provided at the following [link](#).

4.2. INSPIRE Conference Results

Co-creation workshops

During four sectorial co-creation workshops, with 2 parallel sessions, the participants were asked to prioritise societal objectives and subtopics related to their sector of interest. The participants were first asked to select the most important subtopics on MIRO board and then they were asked to indicate the importance of each subtopic under each societal objective on Mentimeter.

The low participation rate limited the robustness of results when observed from a sectorial perspective. However, from a cross-sectorial perspective emerged shared patterns that converged towards the prioritisation of specific subtopics within the overarching Societal Objectives (SO). These are summarised in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Summary of prioritised subtopics

Material use efficiency emerged as the subtopic of highest interest (higher number of votes overall). Other relevant cross-cutting subtopics are:

- Waste prevention reuse and recycling (Plastic, Textile and Construction) and
- Sustainable resource use (textile, plastic and construction).

On the other hand, Biodiversity seems of high interest only for construction, while GHG emissions only for plastic.

Chemical sector exhibits a different pattern in terms of relevant topics. Hazardous substances management is the most rated, followed by material use efficiency, innovation and investment, human health and soil quality.

As anticipated above, sectors specific conclusions cannot be drawn because of low response rate. However, we observed that Material use efficiency, Waste prevention reuse and recycling and Sustainable resource use emerged as areas of very high interest overall. Hence, these areas, including underlying indicators, will be promoted, i.e., special attention will be given to these, within the monitoring framework, and, ideally across the case studies.

In this line, the most relevant indicators in these subtopics, emerged during the second session, are (>2.5 average votes):

MATERIAL USE EFFICIENCY

- Resource use efficiency
- Material circularity
- Cascade factor

SUSTAINABLE RESOURCE USE

- Biobased material replacing non-renewable/fossil resources
- Fossil fuel use intensity
- Resource footprints

WASTE PREVENTION, RE-USE AND RECYCLING

- (Municipal) waste recycling and recovery rates
- Existence of procedures/practices for separating waste types from the waste stream to facilitate reuse, recycling or composting
- Share of product is actively being recovered and recycled (or Recycling rate of biobased products)
- Share of materials used in production process derived from recycling or recovery of biomass waste or by-product

Figure 4: Most relevant indicators in the cross-sectorial subtopics

The selected indicators will be promoted in the monitoring framework as “preliminary key indicators to report on” and special efforts will be dedicated to providing supporting information (including data) for their evaluation and interpretation.

Policy scenario workshops

During four sectorial policy scenario workshops, with 2 parallel sessions using as a tool MIRO board, the participants were asked to provide existing policy goals as well as additional new policy goals of their knowledge related to their sectors of interest.

During the four policy scenario workshops and in the discussion on available policies, existing targets and measures, as well as potential future policy interventions, two key observations emerged. First, the audience was, for the most part, not particularly forthcoming with proposals, which may reflect the generally more passive role that industries tend to play in target-setting for sustainability. Second, when discussing possible intervention options, as opposed to broader strategies, it became clear that these need to be formulated in a highly specific manner, a challenge that is difficult to address in a cross-cutting conversation about industrial sustainability.

The policy scenario workshops mainly provided information on how to define the pathways of change for the industries analysed. We grouped and synthesised this information into high-level scenarios that will inform both qualitative and quantitative policy analysis. The policy scenario workshop allowed us to verify, analyse and utilise the outcomes of the literature review carried out on existing strategies, policies, and targets.

The validated overarching policy goals from all four policy scenario workshops were compiled and are presented in Table 2 below.

Table 2: Results overarching policy goals

	Policy Goal 1: Emission and energy	Policy Goal 2: Raw material productivity and circularity	Policy Goal 3: Production processes	Policy Goal 4: Products and circular specifications
2030	EU (Renewable energy directive): EU gross final consumption of energy to be at least 45% from renewable energy sources	<p>GER (Resource efficiency programme): Total raw material productivity: Until 2030 every year 1,5% increase</p> <p>NL: (National circular economy aims): Reduction of EU27 Material footprint (RME) by 50%</p> <p>NL (NECP Update):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - consumption of primary raw materials is reduced by 50 %; - greenhouse gas emissions from production process and waste sector have been reduced to 36 Mton CO2 equivalent; - the sustainability of the industrial heat system has been increased to 300 °C; - electrification and CO/CO2 reuse have been implemented; - CSS shall be deployed in a cost-effective manner; - is sustainable hydrogen production on the path to implementation; - bio-feedstocks are considered to be standard 	EU (Framework sustainable finance): Rise circular material use rate of all materials to increase the average to at least 25%, by increasing the durability, repairability, upgradability, reusability or recyclability of products, and by remanufacturing, preparing for reuse and recycling of used materials and products	ITA (National Circular economy strategy): 2035: the strengthening of upstream circularity strategies such as ecodesign and extending the lifespan of products and parts
2050	EU (Green Deal): No net emission of greenhouse gas emissions in EU Reduce transport-related greenhouse gas emissions by 90%	NL: (NECP Update) Industrial raw materials, products and processes are net climate neutral and 80 % circular	EU (Framework sustainable finance)/NET (National circular economy aims): Reduce EU27 Material footprint (RME) by 75%	EU (Sustainable bioeconomy in the EU): 1% increase of European wood-based products in the market share of the global construction, textile and plastics markets

Furthermore, 14 additional policy goals were gathered during the sectoral workshops that had not been previously identified. No additional policy goals were discussed for the chemical sector. Results for the other sectors are listed below.

EU plastics sector

1. Less use of plastics in agriculture (mulch films, foil tunnels etc.)
2. No fossil-based plastic products till 2050 (recycled plastic and exchange through bio-based products, + CCU)

EU textile sector

1. Fortify local/ regional infrastructures to enable sharing of textiles (or other resources)
2. Obligation for full recycling/reuse/refurbish of unsold textile/fashion (now 30% of fashion in never sold)
3. Supporting regenerative agricultural methods to grow/produce bio-based fibres (wool can be also used as long-term fertilizer)
4. Increase incentives for bio-based materials in the sector
5. Apply carbon tax on all fashion products (and other products) for GHG emissions in full product delivery chain

EU construction sector

1. Oblige/stimulate insulation of all rented houses by 2030/2050
2. Establishment of a (mandatory) Digital Product Passport for construction products on European level with - besides others - information regarding repair, reuse, recycling as well as biomass content
3. Buildings renovation quota/targets
4. Incentives for the deployment of bio-based materials in construction
5. Vacancy management to maintain old buildings and availability of buildings for prolonged usage

Dutch construction sector

1. Guiding goal: by 2030, the Netherlands will use 50% less primary abiotic raw materials (minerals, metals and fossils)
2. As many sustainable renewable raw materials are used as possible; products and raw materials are reused; and hardly any waste exists

4.3. Reflections

The INSPIRE Conference, initially designed as a full-day event, proved to be too long, overwhelming, and broad to keep stakeholders engaged until the end. This experience taught us to split future activities into smaller, more focused events; an approach we subsequently implemented for the DESIGN and IMPLEMENT conferences. A recurring challenge was the lack of active participation in interactive sessions, often due to participants' more generalist backgrounds compared to the technical focus of the discussions. For future events, we recognised the need to broaden participation during plenary presentations, while selectively inviting experts to interactive sessions based on the specific nature of input required. Another key takeaway concerns the framing of questions and content delivery. Both the complexity of the CBBE and the abundance of existing policy goals make it difficult for stakeholders to identify clear priorities. Furthermore, technical language and a lack of structured guidance in the co-creation sessions may have hindered

meaningful contributions. In future, we plan to simplify and contextualise questions, provide clearer briefings on the use of interactive tools (such as Miro or Mentimeter), and allocate sufficient time for discussions. Offering pre-structured policy options as a starting point, rather than expecting participants to generate them from scratch, may lead to more productive exchanges.

While the discussion did not go as planned, some useful insights were collected, namely that while many existing policy targets already address recycling and emissions reduction, participants raised novel ideas worth pursuing, such as increasing the reuse of buildings and ensuring that product prices reflect their contribution to a CBBE. These insights highlight the importance of complementing outcome-based goals with structural changes to market frameworks. The integration of such perspectives will be valuable in shaping the next stages of the SUSTRACK initiative and advancing the transition towards a more sustainable economic model.

5. SELECTION OF POLICY OPTIONS FOR TRANSITIONING TOWARDS A CIRCULAR BIO-BASED ECONOMY

This section describes the approach to select policy options as a basis for identifying policy priorities for a CBBE in the EU. These policy options are used in SUSTRACK for stakeholder discussions and a survey to identify strengths and weaknesses of various policies as well as preferences.

- Section 5.1 outlines the challenges of selecting policies for such a complex transition. Based on these challenges, lessons in regard to what should be considered when deriving policies are compiled.
- Section 5.2 provides a brief overview on the methods used to collect policy options for the transition including ways to incorporate the lessons learned from the previous chapter on transition challenges.
- Section 5.3 presents the results in terms of selected policy options for the transition. It includes tabular overviews of complementary policies (policy sets) and provides brief descriptions of the individual policy instruments.

5.1. Challenges for Creating Bioeconomy Policies

Creating a CBBE constitutes a substantial challenge for policymakers. This challenge includes (but is not limited to) the high complexity of the transition, the vagueness of several of its targets and elements, contradicting sub-targets and the lack of a sound theoretical foundation despite an increasing wealth of literature on the subject. These policy challenges are briefly outlined here to provide a background for the approach chosen in this project.

Challenge 1: Complexity

- Large scope: Unlike, for example, the energy transition, which requires the substitution of a limited amount of fossil energy resources, the CBBE transition seeks to modify several economic sectors encompassing a large number of products, including chemicals, textiles, construction, automotive, electrical and electronic equipment and many more. This also implies that several policy fields are affected, including land use policy, industrial policy, climate policy, environmental policy, trade policy etc. These policy fields already feature a large number of existing

policies. For example, the knowledge platform www.circularlaw.nl lists more than 150 legal acts EU level related to creating a circular economy. This risks substantial administrative burdens for firms and governments as well as risks for conflicting regulations. Finally, there is a large number of barriers impeding the CBBE transition, ranging from economic to cultural, social and environmental challenges (see [D1.2](#)).

- **Changes to production and consumption patterns:** The energy transition is focused on the substitution of certain production inputs and consumption goods (fossil energy resources). It therefore often requires limited changes to how we produce or consume goods (e.g., companies switch to renewable energy supply and consumers exchange fossil-based cars with electric cars). By contrast, the CBBE transition does not only seek to substitute fossil resources but questions the mode of how goods are produced and how consumers acquire, use and discard them. For example, the EU obligation to use a certain amount of recycled material in cars is coupled with an obligation to collect used cars (extended producer responsibility). This in turn incentivises car producers to design cars in a way that makes their recycling easier (production changes). For consumers, a circular economy might entail increased efforts to buy second-hand products from other private households via self-organised second-hand markets, instead of buying new goods from manufacturers sold at retail. Or, instead of buying, they might increase repair activities, leading to changes in how they organise their leisure time plus in an increased demand for repair-related skills (consumption changes).
- **Different resource types:** Unlike the energy transition, the CBBE-transition requires us to think not only about fossil and renewable resources, but also about extracting, using, and re-using non-fossil non-renewable resources such as minerals and metals. Each resource category poses distinct challenges regarding their sustainable management: While biomass policies have to make sure that biomass use does not exceed natural regeneration rates and energy policies focus on phasing out the use of fossil resources, policies targeting a sustainable use of minerals and metals relate to the question of depletion rates of natural deposits. As 100 % recycling and reuse is often impossible due to physical, technological, or economic constraints, CBBE policies have to define and implement a sustainable way of extracting (or importing) virgin raw materials. And while it is clear that renewable resources (and sufficiency measures like energy savings) have to completely substitute fossil resources, there is no clear vision yet about the extent renewables such as biomass can or should replace the demand for virgin minerals or metals that will remain in a CBBE.

Challenge 2: Vague targets and elements

While there are many definitions of what constitutes a circular economy or a bioeconomy (Kirchherr, 2017), and even though EU strategies and action plans note various elements and principles of the transformation, several substantial features of a CBBE are still rather vague. This leads to substantial leeway (or uncertainty) for creating policies that will support the CBBE transition:

- **Unclear degree of recycling:** Despite a broad consensus that recycling constitutes a key feature of a CBBE, there are no clear ideas on how much recycling is actually required or sustainable in the long term. While some recycling is plausible for many resources, 100 % recycling is usually not feasible or both economically and ecologically questionable. Excessive recycling processes can consume more resources and cause higher pollution than using virgin raw materials (Baumol 1977,

Tian 2020). It remains unclear, however, what a desirable recycling rate is for which type of resource (see also the issue of a lack of theoretical foundation below). For policies this means that it is uncertain, e.g., to which level recycling quotas should be raised in a CBBE for sectors like plastics, automotive or others.

- Unclear sustainability boundaries - biomass: A second uncertainty concerns the question how much biomass can or should be consumed in a CBBE. With biomass being a key resource to substitute fossil carbon, there is also a high risk that this substitution process leads to an unsustainable amount of biomass consumption - both in energy and material use sectors. For example, Hurmekoski et al. (2023) show that a strong increase of biomass use in the construction and textile sectors can lead to an increase in total GHG emissions instead of a decline. Regulations such as the EU Renewable Energy Directive (RED) therefore include sustainability criteria such as greenhouse gas emission thresholds. However, these thresholds remain arbitrary as long as they are not clearly linked to climate targets in the EU land use sector LULUCF or biodiversity goals of regulations such as the EU Nature Restoration Law. The revised RED II now includes a link to LULUCF climate targets, but how this link is to be implemented remains vague and limited to energetic uses of biomass.
- Unclear sustainability boundaries - minerals and metals: Regarding minerals and metals, the mostly academic discourse on the sustainable rate of resource extraction has not yet created visible impacts in EU policies, at least not in terms of binding quantitative targets. The EU Critical Raw Materials act addresses some non-renewable resources, but rather with a focus on securing their supply instead of rethinking (global) long-term sustainability. There is no discernible EU position on how much extraction or consumption of virgin minerals and metals should be reduced. This leads to substantial uncertainty in regard to the future shape of the CBBE and subsequent policy needs: For example, the Circular Economy Strategies of Germany and the Netherlands include targets to reduce the demand of all primary resources by (about) 50 %¹, and EU discussions have indicated the need to further reduce demand by 75 % compared to 2015 until 2050. These numbers indicate the need for a dramatic shift in economic activities. As studies such as Bongaerts (2020), Hoogmartens (2018) or Zink (2017) indicate, this economic shift might require more than policies for recycling and reuse. These studies suggest that even high recycling rates do not necessarily reduce the consumption of raw materials in a growing economy, and that recycling and reuse markets may result in rebound effects that also increase total resource consumption. Hence, depending on how much EU countries choose to reduce virgin resource consumption, additional policies might be necessary that directly limit consumption instead of circular practices only.
- Unclear substitutability concept: The notion of substitutability is a key concept in thinking about sustainability. It refers to the question whether the loss of a certain resource can be compensated for by another resource (strong vs. weak sustainability). For example, bio-based plastics are considered by many as a satisfactory substitute for fossil-based plastic. However, other replacements are more difficult to judge. For example, can a loss of (some) biodiversity be justified by income increases in a bioeconomy making extensive use of biomass? Or is reducing resource consumption by limiting working time (and thus possibly income)

¹ NL: <https://www.government.nl/topics/circular-economy/circular-dutch-economy-by-2050>

GER:

https://www.bundesumweltministerium.de/fileadmin/Daten_BMU/Download_PDF/Abfallwirtschaft/nationale_kreislaufwirtschaftsstrategie_bf.pdf.

justified by corresponding increases in environmental quality and leisure? Again, this leaves considerable leeway for CBBE policies, which, for example, may or may not include measures for working time reduction or more or less stringent policies for biodiversity protection.

- **Unclear resource term:** Cost-efficient resource use is a key goal of EU-CBBE policies. Related policies such as the EU Circular Economy Action Plan, however, avoid clearly defining which resources are subsumed under this goal. Most importantly, it remains open whether this refers to natural resources only or also includes labour. This creates considerable uncertainty in regard to the future shape of the CBBE and, consequently, policy needs. For example, in many areas natural resource intensity (and thus dependency) can be decreased considerably by labour-intensive practices such as repairing and recycling. In other words, many natural resources can be saved by substituting them with labour. However, if the goal “cost-efficient resource use” also includes labour, the amount by which substitute natural resources can be substituted for with labour will be limited (i.e., natural resources will be replaced only if using labour is less costly).
- **Unclear decoupling target:** Another strong uncertainty for creating CBBE policies is related to the goal of decoupling resource use from economic growth, which is included in many definitions of the circular economy and also in the EU Circular Economy Action plan. While the notion of decoupling is intuitive, implementing this target with policy measures is challenging as long as it is unclear whether it refers to absolute or relative decoupling. Both options may lead to substantially different versions of a CBBE. This is because absolute decoupling, defined as a reduction of resource use in absolute terms, requires rethinking *existing* production and consumption, while relative decoupling could be achieved by decreasing only the resource intensity of *future* economic growth, while leaving many existing practices unchanged. Hence, it can be assumed that absolute decoupling requires much more stringent and possibly fundamentally different policies that focus much more on established economic structures.

Challenge 3: Trade-offs

The above-mentioned example of whether (some) biodiversity losses can be justified by increased wealth provides an example for the large number of trade-offs embedded in a CBBE that has multiple targets. Often progress in regard to one target comes at the costs of other targets. This challenges policy makers, as there are no clear guidelines on how to deal with such contradictions and, again, blurs the contours of the CBBE. Some exemplary trade-offs can be illustrated using the targets of the EU Bioeconomy Strategy from 2018 - food security, sustainable resource management, supply security, climate change mitigation and adaptation and strengthening competitiveness and jobs creation:

- **Sustainable resource use vs. competitiveness:** In some instances, sustainable resource use might require *reducing* the total consumption of a certain resource. Increasing the EU’s competitiveness, however, requires competitive (i.e. relatively low) resource and product prices that tend to *increase* resource consumption.
- **Climate change mitigation vs. supply security:** To mitigate climate change, EU member states seek to increase the production and use of renewable energy such as wind or solar or battery-electric vehicles. Many of these technologies incorporate so-called rare earths or other critical raw materials. This development can increase dependency on non-EU-countries because many of these resources are not available in the EU in sufficient quantities. Another trade-off concerns bioenergy, which can

contribute to reducing dependency on (foreign) fossil fuel resources but also comes at the risk of increasing greenhouse gas emissions if used excessively.

- **Climate change mitigation vs. food security:** While protecting the climate can be beneficial for global food security in many ways, there are also potential trade-offs. One example is the EU target on increasing carbon removals in the land use sector. One of the relevant options here is increasing the forest area in the EU, which may reduce the available land for food production.
- **Competitiveness vs. job creation:** Connected to the CBBE transition are hopes for both increased competitiveness and more jobs. While innovative technologies can contribute to both goals, there are also possible tensions. For example, a circular economy is often believed to go along with increased rates of re-use, repair, and recycling. These processes are often time- and labour intensive, e.g., when waste has to be sorted manually or when electronic devices have to be disassembled in order to enable repair. This is one reason for these practices often not being competitive and expanding them with the help of policies might create additional jobs but also increase costs and thus undermine competitiveness.

Challenge 4: Lack of theoretical foundation

To minimise uncertainties, contradictions and trade-offs, a theoretical framework can provide guidance on how to structure consistent CBBE policies. However, despite a growing amount of literature on the CBBE most analyses remain fragmented and lack a coherent theoretical framework. Interestingly, existing approaches that could be used to create such a framework are often neglected, possibly due to the lack of communication between the various academic disciplines engaging in the CBBE transition. For example, resource economics has a long tradition of theorising the optimal use of non-renewable resources and, increasingly, also turns to the question of how much recycling is reasonable in a CBBE (e.g. Bongaerts 2020). These approaches are firmly rooted in economic welfare theory that can provide solutions to some questions such as how to manage trade-offs. However, such insights often remain limited to their disciplinary domain and seldomly enter the broader CBBE discourse. This lack of theoretical foundation is more than an academic issue: It obfuscates policy pathways and comes with a high risk of ineffective or even contradictory policy measures as well as unintended consequences. The following examples illustrate this risk:

- As already mentioned, recycling should not be expanded indefinitely. Without clear theoretical guidance, setting high recycling rates can lead to situations where recycling processes consume more resources than they help to save (Kinnaman 2014).
- Recycling is often viewed as a key circular practice to limit the use of virgin raw materials. However, there is no clear link between these two variables - virgin resource consumption can increase even in scenarios with high recycling rates (Compagnoni 2016, Bongaerts 2022; Gajanayake et al. 2025). If recycling is supported by subsidies this can even result in increased resource consumption because subsidies increase the income of firms or private households and thereby their consumption (Hogmaartens 2018; Philippidis 2023). Zink (2017) labels such effects as “circular economy rebound”, referring to the energy rebound (Jevons paradox) that leads to increased energy consumption despite energy savings due to income increases from these savings.
- A similar risk is attached to biomass use: Many proposals to support (even subsidise) material uses of wood in the bioeconomy can be found. While substituting some emission-intensive materials may indeed contribute to climate change mitigation,

a substantial increase in wood consumption risks increasing total greenhouse gas emissions (Hurmekoski 2023). This is because wood from forests is usually not transferred completely into long-term material applications. Much carbon is lost along the way during harvesting or processing wood. Hence, losses in forest carbon storage can easily exceed gains of carbon storage in harvested wood products if too much wood is harvested. Without a clear theoretical framework, however, it is very challenging to decide which harvest levels are too high.

These examples do not disqualify recycling or biomass uses in the construction sector as useful measures for the CBBE transition. They illustrate, however, the risk that intuitive policymaking without a sound theoretical foundation results in conflicting policies and unintended consequences that may compromise key transition targets.

5.2. Insights from SUSTRACK Outcomes

In the scope of the SUSTRACK project, some policy priorities for a CBBE transition were proposed to the above-mentioned challenges.

Addressing complexity

- The SUSTRACK project has limited its focus to the following secondary sectors: construction, plastics, chemicals and textiles. It largely excludes other secondary sectors and the tertiary sector (services). Policies related to primary sectors (agriculture and forestry) are included only if they provide crucial links to the CBBE transition in the selected secondary sectors. The energy sector was not considered as energy and energy-related climate policies are already evolved, which leads to a high risk for new policies to be overlapping, redundant or contradicting.
- Existing policies and proposals for new policies were collected with the help of an extensive literature review (see Chapter 3). Review of existing policies was limited to EU legal acts and binding policies, excluding strategies, action plans or similar overarching policy acts. National or regional policies (or policy ideas) were included if they have not yet an equivalent at EU level, to make use of member states as ‘policy laboratories’ for the EU.
- Regarding the multitude of transition barriers, SUSTRACK has identified 14 key challenges with the help of stakeholders and prioritisation methods such as Analytical Hierarchy Process (see [D1.3](#)). While the condensed barriers do not directly translate into specific policy instruments, some provide additional guidance for selecting and designing policies (Table 3).

Table 3: Prioritised transition barriers and implications for transition policies

Transition barrier	Policy implications
Competing political interests with fossil-based industries (big lobbies etc.)	Policy selection and design has to consider distributional effects and contribute to minimising transition costs. Both implies considering acceptance and efficiency as criteria to select and assess policy options.
Social and technical lock-ins to the current linear system	Innovations - technical and social - play a key role for overcoming lock-ins. Transition policies should therefore specifically support innovation.

Fragmented regulatory framework across European countries and at national/ regional level	Seeking consistent policy solutions at EU level can contribute to harmonising the policy landscape despite fragmented national policies.
Regulatory complexities and lack of support for the transition at government level	Regulatory complexities are addressed via applying consistent theoretical elements for policy analysis and policy instrument selection, see section on lack of theoretical foundation below.
Limited long-term policy reliability	Policy reliability can be improved by identifying consistent, comprehensive and acceptable policies. This is addressed by applying elements of a theoretical framework for transition policies (see below) and by selecting policies that distribute financial burdens of the transition to different stakeholders (firms, private households and governments).
Legislative limitations for applications of materials when classified as waste	Legal limitations are considered by collecting legal barriers for the transition from the literature and stakeholder discussions. These will be used as additional criteria to select policy priorities.
Increasing complexity of materials and their combinations	Material complexity can be addressed by innovation policies (e.g., to support innovative recycling technologies) and by considering the regulatory degree of freedom of different policies when selecting policy priorities. For example, market-based policies typically provide a higher degree of freedom for distinguishing between materials that can be recycled or not than direct controls such as recycling quotas.
Lack of clarity around policy targets and trajectories	The lack of clarity concerning transition targets and trajectories can be addressed by various means such as policy flexibility (see next section: Addressing vagueness).

To further narrow the focus of the analysis, the selection of policy options to accelerate the CBBE transition was limited to legally binding and ‘hard’ policies. This excludes voluntary measures and other ‘soft’ policies such as information instruments including labels or educational measures. These have to be considered on top of the policy options discussed by SUSTRACK.

Addressing vagueness

Generally, SUSTRACK does not address vagueness by making decisions that democratically legitimised EU policymakers have not yet reached. For example, the SUSTRACK project cannot decide on behalf of the EU or its member states whether the CBBE transition targets absolute or relative decoupling.

Instead, vagueness is addressed by policy flexibility. Taking the example of relative vs. absolute decoupling, this means that selected policies feature a degree of freedom to implement one goal or the other. For example, when discussing the option of a recycling quota or a tax, no suggestion is made concerning the specific level of the quota or the tax rate. This leaves space for policymakers to adjust these instruments according to decisions made in the EU or national policy process. Regarding another example, the sustainable use of biomass, this could imply that policymakers are responsible for deciding how restrictive, e.g., sustainability criteria will have to be designed to meet this goal.

Regarding the vagueness resulting from the substitutability question (weak vs. strong sustainability), SUSTRACK policy proposals focus on a broad set of instruments that do not necessarily guarantee strong sustainability. This means that no specific policies are included that specifically focus on the protection of (possibly) non-substitutable goods such as biodiversity. Consequently, if policymakers conclude that (a certain minimum of) biodiversity cannot be offset by advances in the bioeconomy (e.g. climate protection from replacing fossil fuels), SUSTRACK policy recommendations must be complemented with additional measures that restrict the use of these goods or resources (e.g., separate biodiversity policies).

In addition to policy flexibility, which at least partially leaves the burden of vagueness in the hands of policymakers, SUSTRACK also outlines policy pathways that can help to reduce vagueness, complexity and uncertainty - i.e., to implement optimal recycling rates or sustainable biomass uses (see below the section on “lack of theoretical foundation”).

Addressing the lack of theoretical foundation

It is not possible to develop, test and apply a comprehensive theoretical framework for a circular bioeconomy within a single project like SUSTRACK. Therefore, we make use of existing theoretical concepts that can help to identify policy priorities for the CBBE. As the transition centres on the issue of resource use, we here transfer concepts and theoretical insights from economics, a scientific discipline focused on optimal resource allocation.

While it is beyond the scope of this report to provide a comprehensive overview of relevant economic theory, Table 4 summarises selected economic concepts, premises, and findings relevant for a CBBE transition and outlines their implications for identifying suitable policies.

Table 4: Selected economic premises and findings relevant for a CBBE transition

Economic concept, premise or finding	Details	Relevance for CBBE transition	Policy implications
Efficiency criterion	Rooted in welfare theory, economics focuses on efficient resource uses (e.g., maximising output from a given input). This includes private as well as public goods, e.g., climate and water. It can provide guidance in dealing with trade-offs between goals such as economic growth and environmental protection.	Applying the efficiency criterion can help to minimise trade-offs within a CBBE . For example, recycling can save resources and reduce emissions, but recycling processes also require resources and may cause emissions. An economic perspective can help to create policies that consider both costs and benefits of recycling and thus lead to optimal recycling rates (e.g., Kinnaman 2014).	Selecting CBBE policies should not only consider effectiveness but also efficiency. This can help to choose between different policy options with similar effectiveness. For example, while quotas are often effective instruments, their contribution to cost efficiency can be limited as they tend to ignore the varying cost structures of different firms or regions.

Role of markets	Markets are institutions that can be used to allocate resources in complex societies with the help of prices instead of planning (Hayek 1945)	Given the high complexity of the CBBE transition, policymakers can profit from reflecting more closely where markets can support managing this complexity. Steering the transition centrally via detailed requirements for firms and consumers risks policy overload and rising bureaucracy.	Policies that create or manage markets can support coping with the high complexity of the transition. For example, emission trading systems for fossil carbon the question of where and how emissions should be best reduced to firms, thus relieving governments from creating complex, centralised policy solutions such as emissions thresholds.
Concept of market failures	The concept of market failures stipulates that efficient resource use is often undermined by structural market barriers, such as externalities arising from certain features of public goods or from market power of monopolists.	The idea of market failures can help to identify causes of inefficient resource use and based on this, effective leverage points for transition policies. For example, Lintunen and Uusivuori (2016) show that cost-efficient use of forest biomass can be reached by addressing biomass-related climate externalities via carbon pricing and carbon removal subsidies.	Analysing market-failures can reveal additional policy options that address market structures instead of market outcomes. For example, instead of prescribing a recycling target (quota) it may also be effective (and efficient) to support market innovations and change the competitiveness of recycled material.
Macroeconomic policy effects	Many policies do not only affect the firms or consumers they address but have side effects on other markets or the behaviour of market participants. For example, paying subsidies for reducing emissions will often reduce a single firm's	Macroeconomic policy effects can reduce or offset benefits from transition policies. Taking the example of subsidies, Hogmaartens et al. (2018) indicate that paying subsidies for recycling may incentivise consumers to substitute products	Macroeconomic side effects suggest that promoting the CBBE transition should not make extensive use of subsidies or other policies that tend to increase resource demand (e.g., biomass quotas).

	<p>emission intensity (lower individual emissions), but can also increase the number of firms in a market (higher total emissions compared to other policy solutions, Baumol/Oates 1988).</p>	<p>earlier with new ones, thus contributing to higher resource consumption. Zink and Geyer (2017) and de Weerd (2024) show that recycling and reuse can result in rebound effects (i.e., higher total resource use), for example when used products do not replace existing products but expand consumption to new groups (e.g., people who cannot afford a new but a used phone).</p>	<p>Where such policies are employed, policies should be added that limit total resource use by encouraging reducing consumption or re-use of products (e.g., Allwood 2014). Another option to avoid undesired side effects is to apply policies that (further) restrict the use of fossil resources instead of directly supporting renewable or other sustainable solutions.</p>
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Addressing trade-offs

As with vagueness, many trade-offs cannot be solved within SUSTRACK. Especially where different goods are involved that are no substitutes (e.g., economic growth [income] versus certain environmental goods) a final decision has to be found by policymakers.

For some trade-offs, applying the theoretical fragments outlined above can help to find balanced solutions. This concerns mostly the efficiency criterion: Shaping policies in a way that maximises resource efficiency strikes a balance between all substitutable goods that can be measured at the same scale. For example, using biomass can contribute to economic growth and jobs in a CBBE but also increase greenhouse gas emissions if used excessively. All the related policy goals - economic growth, job creation and climate change mitigation - can be expressed on a monetary scale (national income GDP, labour income, climate change damage costs or mitigation costs). Maximising resource use efficiency implies that biomass is used in a way that maximises the aggregate benefits of all three goal dimensions. Put differently, it is not possible to increase or decrease biomass use without reducing overall welfare. In more practical terms, this means that policy solutions that can be expected to contribute more to cost-efficient resource uses are also those that help minimising trade-offs between several key CBBE goals (i.e., climate change mitigation, sustainable resource management, economic growth and jobs).

Hence, the aim of minimising trade-offs in SUSTRACK has been included by integrating policy solutions that support the CBBE transition in a cost-efficient way. This has two practical consequences: First, market-failures were identified that pose barriers to a cost-efficient CBBE transition, using a literature review. Second, market-based policy solutions (e.g., taxes, emissions trading, subsidies) were collected that help to correct these market failures, as this type of instrument is usually considered to be more cost-efficient than direct regulation (e.g., quotas, thresholds, bans).

5.3. Selection of Policy Options

The existing situation for selecting policies to transform sectors like construction, textiles, chemicals or plastics is paradoxical. On the one hand, each sector is already subject to an extensive amount of EU and national regulations that are increasingly difficult to oversee and assess in their individual effects.¹ On the other hand, progress towards a circular bioeconomy in the EU remains limited. Despite increasing collection and recycling of plastics, total plastic waste generation keeps increasing (European Parliament, 2018). The share of biomass in the construction sector was only 3% in 2022 (Cardellini & Mijndonckx, 2022). Only 1 % of clothing material used in the EU is recycled into new clothing (EC, n.d.). Tens of thousands of chemicals, many of them hazardous, continue to pose a key barrier for circular practices (EEA, 2024).

The lack of transition progress against the background implies that existing policies are insufficient, either in terms of scope (relevant economic activities and social practices are not covered) or depth (existing policies are ineffective or not ambitious enough in their level of intervention, e.g., the level of recycling quotas). To cover both aspects, existing policies and proposals for new policies were considered. The steps of selecting policy options for further assessment with stakeholders in SUSTRACK are described in Table 5.

Table 5: Policy selection steps

Step in policy selection	Details	Challenges addressed by this step
1) Policy review	An extensive, AI-assisted literature selection and subsequent review was carried out for each sector (for details see Chapter 3). The literature was screened for existing policies and proposals for new policies.	Complexity
2) Analysis of market failures	A second literature review was carried out to structure policy needs associated with the transition, using the economic concept of market failures. As relevant literature is scattered among several economic sub-disciplines and journals and as relevant content is framed by a variety of terms beyond circularity or bioeconomy, a mix of keyword search (web of science) and snowball method was applied to identify useful articles. In total, 70 economic papers related to	Lack of theoretical foundation, Trade-offs

¹ For example, EU regulations such as the Packaging and Packing Waste Regulation, the Directive on single-use plastics, the Ecodesign for Sustainable Products Regulation and other legal acts include recycling targets, extended producer responsibilities for the collection of plastic packaging waste, product standards such as the requirement to attach bottle caps, a requirement to reduce consumption of certain single use plastics and bans of a certain array of this product type, a quota to use recycled material in the production of certain beverage bottles or in cars, a quota to reduce the amount of plastic bags, labelling requirements, requirements to improve recyclability, durability, reusability etc., bans and thresholds regarding the use of certain hazardous substances, various waste regulations such as restrictions on landfilling or emissions regulations concerning water and air pollution of plastic producers. Many more regulations address feedstock producers (fossil or bio-based) and consumers of plastic products (e.g., incentives or labels to encourage reusable plastic packaging, for increasing separate waste collection, for repairing plastic-containing products, for re-selling or buying used products etc.). As plastics are ubiquitous in modern economies, a wide range of additional policies might also be highly relevant that unintentionally impact plastic consumption. For example, with cars being a major source of plastic use, subsidies for battery-electric vehicles, city tolls, car-related emissions performance standards etc. may change the total demand for this mobility option and thus the amount of plastic used in the transport sector.

	<p>circular resource use or efficient use of biomass where selected based on abstract screening. Textbox 1 presents key findings that were used to shape the subsequent methodical steps. Furthermore, this second literature analysis was used to identify further policy options that may not have entered the CBBE discourse yet.</p>	
3) Structuring by policy type	<p>A key question for policy makers is the choice of policy type. Different policy approaches may vary substantially in regard to effectiveness, efficiency, administrative burdens, costs for governments, firms and private households, acceptance and other aspects relevant for policy selection. To reduce complexity, SUSTRACK mostly focuses on policy options of two key policy types - direct regulation and market-based regulation (see Textbox 2). Subsequently, in this step, policy options were narrowed down to these two types and classified accordingly. This step supports isolating strengths and weaknesses of policy approaches for the CBBE transition that rely more on one type or the other.</p>	Complexity, Trade-offs, Vagueness
4) Structuring by policy function	<p>One conclusion from step 2 is that transition policies have to fulfil two separate functions: They have to support circular practices and biomass uses, and at the same time limit resource use. This helps to limit trade-offs of a CBBE transition (e.g., between competitiveness and sustainable resource use). Using policy functions as guidance also helps navigating within the complexity of the transition. Therefore, in this step policies identified in steps 1 and 2 were categorised according to one of these functions.</p>	Complexity, Trade-offs
5) Structuring by policy aim	<p>Another conclusion from step 2 is that transition policies can and should be considered separately, depending on their main aim - promoting circularity or efficient biomass use. Again, this helps to better navigate the complex CBBE transition. Therefore, policies were categorised according to these aims.</p>	Complexity
6) Creation of policy sets	<p>Steps 1 to 5 have laid the foundation for a clear structuring of policy options. This structure has been visualised in the form of policy sets (Table 5). Existing policies and policy options collected in both literature reviews have been assigned to these sets to enable structured discussions with stakeholders on strengths and weaknesses of each policy. To limit the complexity (number of policies included in the factsheets), a series of internal workshops was conducted to identify policies that best represent the respective type, function and aim of the factsheets. This selection was based on the analysis of the case studies in SUSTRACK (especially WP3) and previous stakeholder input. To give an example, for improving biomass use in the plastic sector (aim) via direct regulation (type) to promote the transition (function), several options have been identified in the</p>	Complexity

	<p>literature review, mainly from the packaging plastics subsector: recycling quotas, product bans, extended producer responsibility, product standards, ecodesign criteria and labelling requirements. For the function transition promotion in the non-packaging plastics subsector, the options recycling quota and ecodesign criteria have been selected. Reasons for this selection included that existing EU legislation already established a framework on ecodesign criteria, making this policy option highly compatible to the current policy framework. Regarding the recycling quota, this was chosen over other options such as product bans because a ban is more closely related to the function of limiting the resource use (and was therefore shifted to the respective section of the factsheet).</p>	
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Textbox 1: Market-failures related to a circular bioeconomy

From an economic perspective, various market-failures undermine a more circular economy based on efficient biomass use. Analysing these market-failures can provide insights for policy gaps, policy leverage points and consistent policy mixes. Many but not all market failures vary according to the type of resource that is considered:

- **Fossil fuels:** The use of fossil fuels is associated, among others, with negative climate externalities (e.g., Stern 2007). One consequence is a reduced competitiveness for fossil-free products and practices that help reduce resource-related emissions such as reuse. Hence, internalising these externalities can contribute to the CBBE transition. In the EU, the key policy instrument to reduce fossil-fuel related externalities is the EU Emission Trading System. This instrument and others such as emissions performance standards for cars, however, are limited to energy uses of fossil fuels. The literature review revealed that policies that internalise externalities from material uses of fossil carbon in textiles, plastics, chemicals, or construction are mostly absent.
- **Biomass:** Similar to fossil fuels, an efficient use of biomass is undermined by climate externalities, but in two ways. The first externality relates to climate damages from biogenic greenhouse gas emissions (negative externality), the second externality is associated with the carbon uptake in growing biomass (e.g., Lundgren 2008; Lintunen and Uusivuori 2016). These externalities have various effects that impact the CBBE transition: They tend to decrease the carbon sink of forests below their efficient level, thus decreasing supply of biomass. This results in higher prices for biomass in the long term, which undermines the competitiveness of bio-based products. They also lead to competitive advantages of energy uses of biomass over material uses, thereby undermining efficient wood cascading (Miettinen). In addition, biomass extraction and use can cause externalities from impacts on biodiversity or due to air pollution.

- Minerals and metals: Even more market failures can affect the extraction, use and reuse of non-fossil, non-renewable resources (e.g., Gaudet 2007, Kronenberg 2008). Examples are externalities from environmental pollution associated with mining, externalities from landfilling, market power, insecure property rights or myopic behaviour on capital markets. While the aggregate effect of these market failures is difficult to assess, they point to possible leverage points for circular economy policies. For example, environmental externalities can provide a conceptual and legal starting point for policies to discourage the use of virgin resources, thus favouring circular practices.
- Innovations: Independent of the type of resource, a key market failure is knowledge externalities, leading to a suboptimal supply of innovations (e.g., Jaffe 2004, Acemoglu 2016; Dries 2019). As innovations play a key role in developing the CBBE, innovation policies should have a prominent role in a transition policy mix.

From a policy perspective, three major conclusions can be drawn for selecting CBBE policies:

1. In addition to directly supporting circular practices and bio-based products, their competitiveness can and should also be improved with **policies limiting the use of fossil carbon also for material purposes**. This can substantially reduce the costs both for public budgets and firms with CBBE-oriented business models.
2. Creating a CBBE mainly by supporting recycling and biomass use risks intensifying related market failures, thus increasing trade-offs within a CBBE. For example, subsidising the use of biomass might decrease fossil greenhouse gas emissions but also lead to inefficient (and unsustainable) biomass uses. Therefore, policy support for renewable or recycled resources should be complemented with **policies that prevent excessive use of resources, both non-renewable and renewable**.
3. The analysis of market failures also indicates separate causes for insufficient circularity and an inefficient allocation of biomass within an economy. This means that despite circularity and biomass use serving the same goals, policy support for both transition aspects can and should be developed separately. This can help to avoid policy overlaps or inconsistencies.

Textbox 2: Direct regulation versus market-based instruments

The choice of the dominant *policy type* for the CBBE transition can have substantial impacts on several aspects such as transition costs, administrative burdens, regulatory complexity and public budgets. A major difference that separates direct regulation (e.g., quotas, bans, thresholds, product standards) from market-based instruments (e.g., taxes, subsidies, emission trading systems) concerns the nature and locus of intervention. While direct regulation classifies economic actions into legal and illegal (nature: coercion), market-based instruments do not. Instead, they make undesired (inefficient) economic actions less competitive (nature: incentivisation). This difference also implies that direct regulation often specifies the outcome of economic actions in high detail (e.g., a specific pollution concentration in air or water

emissions of individual firms). By contrast, market-based regulation is often limited to modifying more general market rules but not the outcome of the markets (e.g., the pollution of individual firms is uncertain if regulated by taxes or emission trading systems).

Regarding the bioeconomy and other major economic transitions, this implies that relying mainly on direct regulation requires policy makers to know (define) the characteristics of the desired transition very closely, such as the level of recycling quotas or a list of products that will be banned from markets. For example, the EU Single-Use Plastic Directive bans certain products such as cotton buds or plastic straws. This approach requires policy makers to anticipate that these products are not a part of a future EU CBBE. This regulatory approach therefore requires substantial information on the transition outcomes and is prone to a dense web of specific regulations characterised by high bureaucracy (Hayek 1945; Zorpas 2024). As Söderholm (2009) notes: “A major problem with these [direct regulation] types of policy interventions is that they typically underestimate the information requirements needed to foster efficiency and they tend to view resource allocation as a static problem”.

By contrast, market-based regulation often requires less information but comes with uncertainty regarding precise market results. This uncertainty is both a weakness and a strength. The weakness is that uncertainty makes it more challenging for market participants to anticipate, e.g., the future level of recycling - as this is determined by market prices - and thus the required recycling capacities or competitive production quantities of products that are difficult (expensive) to recycle. At the same time, uncertainty is a substantial strength, as it provides more freedom to markets and can substantially reduce information requirements for policy makers and bureaucracy. For example, as it will be very challenging to limit waste from complex products made of composite materials via product bans or recycling targets, it may be more promising to modify resource prices via market-based instruments: “Creating simpler waste streams with less variety is more likely to occur when materials have sufficient value that companies will collaborate to simplify their return” (Allwood 2014:475). Wood cascading provides another example that illustrates possible benefits of a market-based policy approach: Directly modifying market prices with such instruments does not require any knowledge on how such cascades will look like, including if certain sources or types of forest biomass enable higher value creation in material or energy uses (as currently defined as criterion for policy support in the EU Renewable Energy Directive). It also does not require centrally collected information on life-cycle greenhouse gas emissions of wood products to determine their best use for climate change mitigation. Instead, all information about value creation and emissions can be embedded in market prices via carbon pricing and rewarding carbon storage (Lintunen and Uusivuori 2016; Miettinen et al. 2024).

This does not mean that market-based instruments are generally superior to direct regulation. Next to market uncertainty, this intervention type can have other potential drawbacks such as problematic distributional effects, which can undermine policy acceptance (e.g., Freire-Gonzales 2022). In general, policy mixes combining market-based instruments and direct regulation often have the potential to alleviate drawbacks of each policy type (e.g., De Weerd 2024). However, for highly complex policy challenges such as the CBBE transition, the potential of market-based instruments in regard to lower information requirements and decreasing bureaucracy should receive more attention.

For each sector two policy sets were created: one for boosting circularity and one for promoting efficient biomass use. Both policy sets are structured similarly (see Figure 5).

		Direct regulation	Market-based instruments
Promoting transition			
Limit resource use			

Figure 5: Policy set structure

5.4. Policy Sets for the Transition

5.4.1. Textile policy sets

Textiles are already the object of various regulations in the EU, including minimum quality standards from the EU Ecodesign for Sustainable Products Regulation, the waste hierarchy embedded in the EU Waste Framework Directive or the EU Textile Labelling Regulation requiring the provision of information on fibre compositions of textile products. Despite such efforts, progress toward circular practices and the substitution of fossil resources with biomass remain slow. In 2022, only 1 % of clothing material originated from recycled textiles (EC, n.d.). More than half of fibres and yarns used by EU industry is still made from fossil feedstocks (EEA, 2025).

In a direct regulation policy setting, options for accelerating the transition towards a CBBE in the textile sector include quotas for the use of bio-based feedstocks and recycled material in addition to existing policies such as ecodesign criteria and the EU ban on the destruction of unsold goods. As quotas and bans shift the transition costs to industry and consumers, pull measures such as public procurement criteria preferring, e.g., fossil-free textiles could be added - thus shifting part of the costs to public households. To make sure that biomass-quotas do not result in excessive or ecological harmful biomass use, they could be complemented with sustainability criteria similar to those for bioenergy in the EU Renewable Energy Directive, possibly in the form of a Renewable Materials Directive. Due to the high share of imported textiles, the quotas should also be applied to imports.

In a market-based policy setting, innovation subsidies take the lead of promoting the transition. Innovation here refers not only to research and development activities but also to introducing innovative textiles to markets until their production volume enables exploiting scale effects. It is important to note that both economic theory and model-based results do not suggest the use of product subsidies, i.e. broad financial support for recycled or bio-based textiles. Using such subsidies risks excessive (inefficient) textile and biomass use including increasing greenhouse gas emissions (Hoogmartens 2018, Hurmekoski et al. 2023). To support (non-innovative) circular and fossil-free textile production, environmental externalities related to fossil feedstocks and waste disposal should be internalised. This could be facilitated with taxes on “fast fashion” (indirectly supporting durable, high-quality textiles) and on fossil content. As fossil content has to be labelled already, information is available for national governments to implement such a tax.

Policy set: Biomass use

	Direct regulation	Market-based instruments
Promoting transition	<p>Quota for use of bio-based (and recycled) feedstock in textile production and imports</p> <p>Public procurement of textiles without fossil-based content</p>	<p>Innovation subsidy for developing new technologies and practices for bio-based textiles including support for market penetration of innovative products</p>
Limit resource use	<p>Sustainability criteria for biomass to be eligible to the quota, public procurement (e.g., EU Renewable Material Directive following the EU Renewable Energy Directive)</p>	<p>Environmental tax on “fast fashion” textiles, fibres, yarns, and fabrics, e.g., including for non-sustainable cotton products to limit waste and pollution</p>

Policy set: Circularity

	Direct regulation	Market-based instruments
Promoting transition	<p>Quota for use of recycled (and bio-based) material in textiles production and imports</p> <p>Ecodesign criteria for mandatory durability, reparability and recyclability standards (incl. for imports)</p>	<p>Innovation subsidy for innovative textile reuse or recycling practices and technologies, including support for market penetration of innovative products</p> <p>“Green VAT” Reduced Value-Added Tax on re-used or recycled textiles</p>
Limit resource use	<p>Ban on Destruction of Unsold Goods (Existing EU instrument) as part of polluter pays principle to discourage overproduction</p>	<p>Carbon tax on the use of fossil feedstocks in textiles production</p>

5.4.2. Chemicals policy sets

Chemicals are a major barrier for a circular economy. They might accumulate during recycling processes or lead to the persistence of hazardous substances in the economy that should be phased out (Bodar et al. 2018; Johansson 2023). Next to this toxicity risk, chemicals are often based on fossil feedstocks, thus contributing to climate change.

The double challenge of toxicity and greenhouse gas emissions complicates policy solutions for a CBBE. Recycling processes may help to reduce greenhouse gas emissions at the cost of increased toxicity due to accumulation of hazardous substances. This has already led to less ambitious thresholds for hazardous substances in recycled materials under EU REACH (Johansson 2023). Other challenges include:

- Benefits of chemicals' treatment or recycling are often uncertain (e.g., according to Bodar et al. 2018, recycling of lead from ray tubes creates up to 3 times more volume of hazardous waste with no recovery option currently available).
- Bio-based chemicals are not necessarily less harmful than fossil-based chemicals (Bodar et al. 2018).
- There are tens of thousands of chemicals, the vast majority hazardous, but only 15 % are covered by existing regulations such as REACH due to de minimis rules (Johansson 2023). In addition to this, while the risks of individual chemicals registered under REACH are known, this does not apply to the combined effects of chemicals in products or the environment.
- Many chemicals combine high risks and high benefits for society. Restricting these substances therefore imposes high cost to society if no less harmful alternatives are available. The ongoing debates around banning glyphosate or certain PFAS from EU markets illustrate this dilemma.

In 2022 the EU published the framework Safe and sustainable by design (SSbD). The framework provides guidance for producing innovative chemicals that minimise damages to human health and environment. Applying the framework is voluntary, however, thus rendering its impact uncertain.

To support the effectiveness of the SSbD-framework with direct regulation, financial support could be extended for developing chemicals consistent with its provisions and introducing them into markets. In parallel, to limit the use of the large amount of hazardous chemicals that are not banned via classification as substances of very high concern, but pose barriers for reuse or recycling of products, concentration thresholds for various product categories may be applied. In a similar way, REACH permission criteria can be extended to cover not only hazards during the use phase of a product but also consider its potential re-use, repair or recycling. An additional policy option is to extend the EU SCIP database on hazardous substances in products to substances that inhibit circular practices.

To accelerate the substitution of biomass for fossil feedstocks, a quota could be applied. To include other renewable options such as hydrogen, it could be created as a minimum share of non-fossil feedstocks. Alternatively, a greenhouse gas emissions reduction quota could be used. To ensure sustainable biomass use, the quota can be complemented with sustainability criteria for material applications of biomass.

Regarding the support of bio-based chemicals, a mixed policy approach has also been suggested by stakeholders in SUSTRACK workshops. This would combine incentives in the form of a tax reduction ("Green Value Added Tax") with biomass sustainability criteria. As making bio-based chemicals competitive via (indirect or direct) subsidies may be limited by the availability of public

budgets this approach could be combined with a phase out for fossil feedstocks - either in form of an increasingly ambitious quota or a ban. Sustainability criteria for biomass will possibly have to be more restrictive than in the direct regulation scenario, because a product subsidy is likely to increase the demand for biomass more than innovation support.

A policy approach featuring market-based instruments would consist of financial support for the development and market introduction of innovative bio-based chemicals as well as chemicals in line with the EU SSbD framework. Phasing out fossil fuels and limiting biomass use to a sustainable level with the help of incentives could take the form of a carbon price for fossil feedstocks and for low-value biomass uses. Restricting environmental pollution and health risks may be addressed by a pollution tax with tax rates varying to the estimated average damage of key substances of concern. This way, substances such as PFAS could be reduced without having to ban them entirely (via classification as substances of very high concern) or by defining and implementing various concentration thresholds depending on the type of PFAS or the value of the product containing these chemicals.

Policy set: Biomass use

	Direct regulation	Mixed policy approach	Market-based instruments
Promoting transition	Quota for non-fossil feedstock shares in chemicals production - leading to phase out of fossil feedstocks, e.g. in 2050 Additional: innovation subsidies for development and market penetration of non-fossil chemicals	Product subsidy for non-fossil chemicals, for example “green VAT” (reduced Value-Added Tax) Additional: phase out of fossil feedstocks leading to a final ban, e.g. in 2050	Innovation subsidy for innovative non-fossil chemicals, including supporting market penetration of novel products
Limit resource use	Sustainability criteria for biomass to be eligible to the quota (e.g., EU Renewable Materials Directive following the EU Renewable Energy Directive)	Sustainability criteria for biomass to be eligible to the subsidy (e.g., Renewable Materials Directive following the Renewable Energy Directive)	Carbon tax for fossil feedstocks in chemicals production and for low-value biomass uses

Policy set: Circularity/Toxicity

	Direct regulation	Market-based instruments
Promoting transition	Innovation subsidy for developing low-risk chemicals and toxic-free products according to EU-SSbD*-framework and decontamination technologies (*: Safe and Sustainable by Design)	Innovation subsidy For developing low-risk chemicals and toxic-free products according to EU-SSbD*-framework and decontamination technologies (*: Safe and Sustainable by Design)
Limit resource use	Thresholds for key Substances of Concern in products that inhibit reuse, recycling etc. REACH: extended criteria for chemicals permission that consider recycling, reuse etc. of products SCIP Extension Extension of EU SCIP database to chemicals inhibiting circularity	Pollution tax on key Substances of Concern that pose major risks to health or environment and thus inhibit circularity (e.g., lead, PFAS, flame retardants)

5.4.3. Plastics policy sets

As mentioned above, there are already several legal acts in the EU seeking to align plastic production and use with CBBE goals. The majority addresses packaging plastic, which is reflected in the fact that collection and recycling rates of this type of plastic is considerably higher than in the case of non-packaging plastic, even though the latter makes up 60 - 75 % of total plastic demand in the EU (EEA, 2022). Therefore, the following policy options focus on contributing to the CBBE transition in the non-packaging sector.

Using direct regulation to make non-packaging plastic demand more circular and to encourage use of bio-based plastics, quotas might be challenging. They create strong and inelastic demand, while the availability of sustainable biomass feedstock in quantities that are relevant to this sector as well as the amount that can be recycled remain uncertain. Therefore, the factsheet proposes a hybrid policy approach of incentives for bio-based plastics and a quota for the use of recycled plastic for major sources of non-packaging waste. The latter takes up the recently decided EU quota for recycled plastic in cars, which could be extended to other relevant waste sources such as electrical and electronic equipment. With non-packaging plastic often constituting only a (sometimes marginal) share of many products, such quotas should be coupled with ecodesign criteria that facilitate disassembling multi-component products to enable repair or recycling. Again, the EU Ecodesign for Sustainable Products Regulation already provides a respective framework. Extending product bans under the EU Single-Use Plastics Directive can help to limit total plastic consumption and direct recycled material to products with high added value.

Concerning biomass use, the large amount of non-plastic packing produced and consumed suggest rigorous arrangements to limit the use of this feedstock to sustainable levels. In addition to

sustainability criteria for material biomass uses (with compliance being a condition for receiving the subsidy) a cap for total biomass use in the sector could be considered.

Market-based policies in this sector could feature financial support for innovative technologies or practices related to producing bioplastics or to circularity (including reduce, re-use, repair and recycle) to offset the tendency of markets to undersupply innovations. Again, there should be no broad support for non-innovative bioplastics or recycled plastic as this risks inefficient and possibly unsustainable levels of demand for biomass and fossil feedstocks. In addition, reconciling the high (and rising) demand for plastics with limited sustainable biomass quantities and to reduce fossil greenhouse gas emissions, a carbon price should be levied. Regarding the vast variety of products and the challenge to identify the carbon content of composite materials, the price should be applied upstream on fossil feedstocks used to produce plastic (intermediate) products. The price should also apply to low-value bioplastics to limit biomass use, account for biomass-related externalities especially of forest biomass (Lintunen and Lundgren 2016) and redirect biomass to high value uses in the sector. A carbon price for plastics probably has to be set up apart from existing EU emission trading systems (EU ETS) for various reasons. One is that price levels in both ETS sectors (energy/industry and effort sharing sectors including buildings and transport) will most likely remain far too low to incentivise relevant reductions of fossil feedstock use in the plastics sector (Zibunas et al. 2022). The second is that indirectly covering plastics-related greenhouse gas emissions via integrating the waste sector into EU ETS can be expected to be of limited effectiveness. This is because ETS incentives are often not correctly transmitted to (plastics) producers but confounded via lump-sum waste fees for private households. Put differently, as long as waste disposal companies do not align waste fees according to the carbon content of waste, ETS-induced price increases will be dispersed to (household) waste in general, thus providing no incentive for consumers to specifically reduce their consumption of plastic products.

Policy set: Biomass use

	Direct regulation	Market-based instruments
Promoting transition	Product subsidy paid to producers of durable non-packaging plastic final or intermediate products made from biomass meeting sustainability criteria	Innovation subsidy for new bioplastics technologies and for innovative durable bioplastic products to support their market penetration
Limit resource use	Sustainability criteria for receiving the product subsidy. E.g., mandatory greenhouse gas reductions, exclusion of biomass from areas with high carbon or biodiversity value, restriction to durable products etc. Additional: Cap for share or total quantity of biomass used in the sector	Carbon price on emissions from low-value biomass uses, e.g. from bioenergy and single-use / non-durable bioplastics products

Policy set: Circularity

	Direct regulation	Market-based instruments
Promoting transition	<p>Quota for use of recycled content for producers of non-packaging plastics (e.g., major waste sources such as cars, electrical devices etc.)</p> <p>Ecodesign criteria for non-packaging plastic products to improve ease of repair, recycling etc.</p> <p>Public procurement</p>	<p>Innovation subsidy for new technologies, practices and products connected to the re-use, repair or recycling (etc.) of non-packaging plastics</p>
Limit resource use	<p>Product bans of additional single-use and short-life plastic products or product parts where sustainable and low-cost alternatives incl. reuse and repair are available</p>	<p>Carbon price for use of virgin fossil feedstocks as production input, to be paid by producers of non-packaging plastics</p>

5.4.4. Construction policy sets

According to the EU Environmental Agency, buildings account for one third of EU's material footprint. Around 20-25 % of the life cycle greenhouse gas emissions related to buildings are embedded in building materials (EEA, 2024). Only 3 % of building materials are renewable resources (Cardellini & Mijndonckx, 2022) and mineral waste from construction and demolition has increased between 2010-2022 (Eurostat, 2025). These figures illustrate that next to EU policies to reduce greenhouse gas emissions related to energy use in buildings, additional steps have to be taken to make the sector more sustainable. The EU Waste Framework Directive already requires member states to increase recycling and material recovery of (non-hazardous) construction and demolition waste to at least 70 % by the end of 2025. While EU member states have made considerable progress in this regard, many exceeding the mandatory recycling/recovery-rate (Moschen-Schirmek et al. 2023), this is often achieved by substantial 'downcycling', i.e., by using the materials in lower value applications such as road construction. For example, while the Netherlands' recycling/recovery-rate is around 90 %, less than 10 % of the materials from buildings are used again for this purpose (Conde et al. 2022). This implies that circularity in a sense that substantially extends high value uses of virgin materials is still very limited in this sector and that further policies are required.

In a direct regulation setting, additional policies could include quotas (or mandatory EU targets) for using biomass and recycled materials in new buildings or for refurbishments. In such a scenario, eligible biomass should be subject to stringent sustainability criteria that are closely coupled with climate targets in the LULUCF-sector, to avoid overusing forest carbon sinks (Hurmekoski 2023). The SUSTRACK bioeconomy factsheet for the construction sector also contains a subsidy for refurbishing buildings in cases where this is less resource intensive than new buildings. This can also contribute to containing private household expenditures for rents or home ownership. Regarding mineral resources, (additional) ecodesign criteria that address the material dimension of buildings could be created to support future high-value re-use or recycling. Similarly, mandatory

standards for deconstruction based on existing recommendations from EU’s Construction and Demolition Waste Protocol could accelerate circular practices in the sector.

In a setting relying on market-based instruments, support for research, development and innovation would take the lead of promoting the CBBE transition. Support measures could involve developing and using innovative bio-based materials or novel technologies related to re-using materials, using recycling materials, employing recycled materials or promoting material efficiency. As mentioned in the section on the textile sector above, no direct subsidies should be paid for employing (non-innovative) bio-based or recycled material, as this risks increasing sectoral demand to an inefficiently high level, provoking conflicts, e.g., with LULUCF climate targets. On the contrary, to further reduce the carbon footprint of the sector, EU carbon pricing should be extended to GHG emissions embedded in construction materials that are not yet subject to EU ETS or national carbon pricing measures. This should include embedded biogenic emissions embedded in forest biomass except for materials that ensure long-term carbon storage. To further encourage carbon storage and improve social acceptability, such materials could receive additional financial support in the form of carbon credits (e.g., EU ETS allowances) or otherwise. Finally, a tax on non-renewable virgin raw materials such as sand or gravel (including imports) can help to alleviate the pressure on natural reserves and improve the competitiveness of circular measures.

Policy set: Biomass use

	Direct regulation	Market-based instruments
Promoting transition	Quota/target for use of bio-based material in new buildings including higher targets for public procurement	Innovation subsidy for development and uses of innovative bio-based construction materials
Limit resource use	Sustainability criteria for biomass to be eligible to the quota (e.g., EU Renewable Material Directive following the EU Renewable Energy Directive) Subsidy for refurbishment of buildings	Carbon tax on all lifecycle GHG emissions of building materials that are NOT part of current carbon pricing (EU-ETS I+II) including the carbon content of short-life biomass materials. Carbon credit / subsidy Bio-based building materials that ensure long-term storage of carbon (e.g., 50+ years) are exempt from the tax and receive a credit / subsidy.

Policy set: Circularity

	Direct regulation	Market-based instruments
Promoting transition	<p>Quota/target for use of recycled materials in new buildings</p> <p>Ecodesign criteria For building companies on design, construction and use of materials. Aim should be to design for reuse, disassembly, physical durability, adaptability and repair and minimising material intensity.</p>	<p>Innovation subsidy for innovative circular technologies or practices (e.g., use of recycled materials)</p>
Limit resource use	<p>Demolition Standards Requirements for the demolition of buildings, that increase chances for re-use, upcycling and recycling of materials, and thus encourage waste reduction and possibly refurbishment</p>	<p>Material tax on the use of virgin raw materials for construction (e.g., gravel, stone, sand) including imports</p>

6. DESIGN CONFERENCE

6.1. Overall Structure and Main Objectives

Between July and September 2024, SUSTRACK organised the “Pathway to DESIGN the Circular Bio-Based Transition” series of workshops and a concluding conference. These events were conceived to achieve several objectives. Firstly, they aimed to present a comprehensive overview of the selected SUSTRACK value chains - chemicals, construction, textiles, and plastics - by providing detailed process descriptions, market information, and an outline of relevant policy instruments as a foundation for discussions. Secondly, the events sought to inspire participants through concrete case studies presented by sector experts who shared their perspectives, good practices, and the challenges and barriers they face in advancing the transition towards a circular bio-based economy. Finally, the workshops served as a forum to discuss and formulate recommendations for supporting this transition, considering policy, environmental, societal, and economic dimensions. These discussions culminated in the closing DESIGN conference, which aimed to translate the outcomes of the workshops into concrete policy recommendations for both industrial and political stakeholders, thereby contributing to a more informed and coordinated path forward for the circular bio-based transition.

The structure of the workshop series consisted of four sector-specific co-creation workshops, each dedicated to one of the SUSTRACK targeted value chains (textile, chemical, plastics and construction). During these workshops, SUSTRACK experts presented SUSTRACK selected sectorial case studies, while 179 stakeholders contributed with 20 inspirational pitches and nurtured rich

interactive discussions exploring policy, environmental, social, and economic dimensions of the circular bio-based economy, capturing valuable challenges, good practices, and recommendations through MIRO Board. The plenary closing event, gathering 123 experts, synthesised the insights collected during the workshop series. This “split” format (Figure 6) was intentionally designed to foster engagement and active participation while avoiding the fatigue typically associated with lengthy online events, as it was experienced with the first INSPIRE conference. The conference factsheet is available at the following [link](#).

Figure 6: DESIGN conference structure

The profile of participating stakeholders reflected the quadruple helix approach, drawing together experts and stakeholders from the textile, construction, plastics, and chemical sectors, representing research, industry, policy, and civil society. In total, 302 participants engaged in the workshop series and final event. To support the facilitation of these events, interactive tools such as the MIRO Board and PowerPoint presentations were employed to structure discussions, gather feedback, and present key information effectively.

6.2. DESIGN Conference Results

6.2.1. Textile sector

This section summarises the key challenges and recommendations identified during the co-creation workshop for the textile sector. The insights are presented for the textile sector as a

whole first and followed by the specific insights for the case studies on manmade cellulosic fabrics (MMFC) like lyocell and Latxa wool from the Basque country in Spain.

Whole Sector Analysis

Policy Dimension

Challenges:

The transition of the textile sector towards a CBBE is hindered by several policy-related challenges. First, gaps in policy guidance on sustainability claims, particularly with respect to recyclability, product footprints, and microplastics, create uncertainty and risk of greenwashing, making it difficult for both businesses and consumers to navigate credible options. Second, recycling processes and the use of innovative bio-based materials often entail significantly higher costs, yet these investments are not adequately rewarded or incentivised in current market structures, reducing their competitiveness against conventional products. Finally, structural overconsumption, fuelled by fast fashion business models and persistently low prices, continues to drive the sector's overall environmental footprint upwards, counteracting efforts to achieve circularity and sustainability.

Recommendations/ Good practices:

To address the aforementioned challenges several recommendations were proposed by stakeholders. First, collaboration structures, such as labelling schemes, certification systems, and supporting regulation, should be established to ensure that sustainability claims within the EU are transparent, credible, and verifiable. Second, extended producer responsibility (EPR) fees should be differentiated and increased for unsustainable fibres, thereby creating stronger economic incentives for both producers and consumers to shift towards more sustainable materials and practices. Finally, dedicated policies are needed to stimulate education and the sharing of information on sustainable and unsustainable production and consumption patterns, for example through the development and implementation of digital product passports.

Sustainability Dimension (Environmental and Social)

Challenges:

The textile sector is confronted with several pressing environmental challenges. A key barrier is the lack of transparency and traceability across value chains, which makes it difficult to identify, measure, and address sustainability impacts in a credible way. In addition, significant research and innovation gaps persist in relation to sustainable practices, limiting the development and large-scale deployment of solutions that could reduce environmental pressures throughout the sector.

Recommendations/ Good practices:

The following good practice examples were identified during the co-creation workshop to address the environmental and social challenges of the textile sector. The introduction of digital product passports (DPP) together with robust certification schemes can enhance transparency, traceability, and the credibility of sustainability information throughout value chains. In parallel, Horizon Europe funding should be further leveraged, and investment support accelerated across

all stages of development, from early research to market deployment, to close innovation gaps and bring sustainable practices to scale.

Market Dimension

Challenges:

The textile sector also encounters significant market barriers to sustainability. Repairing garments, while environmentally beneficial, increases overall costs and struggles to compete with the low prices of fast-fashion products. Similarly, the production of bio-based fibres continues to face higher costs compared to conventional plastics, limiting their competitiveness and slowing down wider market uptake.

Recommendations/ Good practices:

To address these market distortions, targeted fiscal measures are needed. Stakeholders proposed introducing a tax on ultra-fast fashion brands to help internalise the environmental and social costs of unsustainable business models. In addition, the implementation of a “Green VAT” by for example lowering the VAT rate to 10% for sustainable businesses and products would create tangible economic incentives to stimulate both sustainable production and consumer demand.

Case study analyses

Case Study 1: Lyocell

Policy Dimension

Challenges:

The case study on Lyocell highlights several policy challenges. At present, there is no equal level playing field for man-made cellulosic fibres (MMCFs) compared with synthetic fibres, which limits their competitiveness. In addition, certification systems for biomass converted into Lyocell remain underdeveloped, reducing trust and transparency along the value chain.

Recommendations/ Good practices:

To overcome these challenges, policy instruments are needed to facilitate MMCFs, such as lyocell, entering the market more easily and to level the playing field with synthetic fibres. Furthermore, existing certification systems should be expanded—or new ones developed—that better reflect the specificities of the Lyocell process, thereby increasing credibility and market acceptance.

Sustainability Dimension (Environmental and Social)

Challenges:

Lyocell production also faces sustainability concerns. Ensuring the sustainable sourcing of raw materials remains a key challenge, particularly in securing traceable and responsibly managed biomass. Moreover, fibre blends present significant obstacles for recycling: blends of MMCFs with elastane are particularly difficult to recycle, even at very low percentages, creating a bottleneck for circularity.

Recommendations/ Good practices:

Promising practices are emerging to address these issues. Several companies, such as Spinova, Saxcell and Lenzing, are already demonstrating the feasibility of using residual or waste streams as feedstock, thereby minimising reliance on virgin raw materials. At the same time, investments and new technologies are being developed to tackle the recycling of complex fibre blends, although progress is not yet advancing at the required speed.

Market Dimension

Challenges:

On the market side, stakeholders highlight that there are currently no mechanisms that reward the lower environmental impact of MMCFs, which limits their recognition and uptake. Additionally, the costs of recycling MMCFs remain higher than those of synthetic fibres, creating an unfavourable economic comparison.

Recommendations/ Good practices:

To address these market-related challenges, awareness-raising campaigns are needed to better inform consumers about the lower environmental impact of MMCFs, thereby stimulating demand. In parallel, policy support is required to reduce the cost gap in recycling between MMCFs and synthetic fibres, at least until MMCFs have reached a sufficiently large market share to compete on equal terms.

Case Study 2: Latxa Wool

Policy Dimension

Challenges:

The Latxa wool case study reveals several policy-related challenges. A large share of wool produced in the EU remains unused or wasted due to the limited availability of facilities for washing and processing. This situation is compounded by unresolved technical and pollution challenges. In addition, there is a need for a clear regulatory framework that encourages recycling over the use of virgin materials.

Recommendations/ Good practices:

To address these challenges, aid policies should be established to support industrial washing facilities and related technology developments. Priority should also be given to protecting and supporting existing laundry facilities to ensure continuity and capacity. Complementary measures could include the introduction of carbon taxes on products, alongside mechanisms such as extended producer responsibility (EPR), certification schemes, labelling, and digital product passports to stimulate sustainable practices.

Sustainability Dimension (Environmental and Social)

Challenges:

Sustainability challenges are also significant for Latxa wool. The washing of wool is resource-intensive, requiring substantial water and chemical use. Moreover, there is a lack of a clear framework for recyclability, including guidance on life cycle assessment (LCA), which hinders consistent evaluation of environmental impacts.

Recommendations/ Good practices:

Addressing these challenges requires coordinated efforts across multiple EU countries to identify optimal locations and methods for wool washing, fostering collaboration and knowledge sharing among stakeholders. Additionally, comprehensive environmental evaluations, including LCA, life cycle costing (LCC), social LCA (S-LCA), and eco-design assessments, should be applied to ensure that sustainability considerations are integrated throughout the wool value chain.

Market Dimension

Challenges:

From a market perspective, the EU currently faces challenges due to insufficient industry to process Latxa wool at scale. Collection systems for wool, including classification skills, represent a challenge for establishing commercially viable washing and processing operations.

Recommendations/ Good practices:

To overcome these challenges, collaboration among stakeholders is essential to improve processing technologies and facilitate wool washing within the EU. Strengthening networking among textile actors will help create a more integrated value chain and support the commercial development of sustainable wool processing.

6.2.2. Chemical sector

This section summarises the key challenges and recommendations identified during the co-creation workshop for the chemical sector. The insights are presented for the chemical sector as a whole first and followed by the specific insights for the case studies on waste-to-methanol and bio-based monoethylene glycol (MEG) from forest and agriculture biomass.

Whole sector analysis

Policy dimension

Challenges:

A key challenge is the lack of dedicated regulatory support for biobased products, in contrast to biobased energy under the Renewable Energy Directive (RED). This regulatory gap incentivises the energetic use of products like ethanol or methanol over their conversion into derivative chemicals for replacing petrochemical products. Policymaking is often unstable and fragmented, which undermines investor confidence and slows the market growth of biobased chemicals, particularly for upscaling efforts that require significant time, cost, and risk tolerance. Current policy frameworks focus on decarbonisation, whereas the chemical sector needs a shift toward *defossilisation*, given its reliance on carbon. This also demands robust carbon tracking and accounting, which is challenging due to the complexity of global, multi-partner value chains.

Recommendations/ Good practices:

A structural recommendation from stakeholders is greater policy coherence through international regulatory alignment in order to maintain competitiveness and prevent production shifts to less circular, lower-cost regions such as Asia, with the Carbon Border Adjustment Mechanism seen as a useful tool. Governments should articulate a clear, unified vision with concrete objectives and actions, enabling industry to deliver fitting solutions that balance business needs with societal

goals. Targeted policy support—such as premiums, mandates for biobased chemicals, or penalties like carbon taxes on virgin fossil inputs—can create a secure environment for investment, market entry, and growth. Promoting renewable carbon cycles that circulate between the biosphere, atmosphere, and technosphere is also essential, supported by transparent carbon tracking and close collaboration across value chains.

Sustainability Dimension (Environmental and Social)

Challenges:

The chemical sector remains heavily dependent on virgin fossil feedstocks, while biobased chemicals must demonstrate their sustainability—an obligation not applied to petrochemicals. Unlike bioenergy and biofuels, which are covered by sustainability criteria under the Renewable Energy Directive (RED), there is no common EU framework for biobased chemicals. A lack of data and knowledge hinders comprehensive sustainability assessments, particularly for economic and social performance, which remain underexplored compared to environmental aspects. Furthermore, the absence of a harmonised Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) methodology leads to inconsistencies, especially regarding differing approaches to biogenic carbon accounting in cradle-to-gate versus cradle-to-grave evaluations.

Recommendations/ Good Practices:

Raising awareness through education can help communicate the benefits of a sustainable bioeconomy and the risks of continuing fossil-based practices. Harmonised evaluation methods across value chains, supported by common EU-level guidance, would improve comparability and steer sustainable development. Expanding the Safe and Sustainable-by-Design (SSbD) framework for biobased chemicals can strengthen knowledge on their performance across all sustainability pillars. The European Standard EN18027 offers useful guidance for conducting comparative LCAs of biobased and fossil-based products, and revising the EU's Product Environmental Footprint (PEF) method in line with this—particularly on biogenic carbon accounting—would ensure fairer comparisons.

Market Dimension

Challenges:

Significant financing hurdles for biobased chemicals still exist, which are often based on new, immature technologies and face “first mover” risks due to the absence of established supply chains. While public funding can partially support capital expenditure for first-of-a-kind plants, it rarely covers operational costs, which vary depending on feedstock supply and demand, creating further investor uncertainty. Cost-competitiveness remains a barrier, as fossil-based chemicals are already mature and optimised, while biobased alternatives face higher production costs. Additional challenges include linking previously unconnected sectors, volatility in biomass prices and availability, and competition for feedstocks from other industries such as food, feed, and fuels—raising concerns for long-term supply towards 2050.

Recommendations/Good Practices:

Good practices identified include ensuring adequate public financing for pioneering chemical plants, engaging with the sustainable finance sector to create market incentives, and building infrastructure for using secondary resources and industrial or agricultural residues, thereby supporting circular economy goals. Stakeholders also stressed the importance of clearly defining the problems to be addressed and conducting realistic assessments of ambitions.

Case Study Analyses

Case Study 1: Waste-to-Methanol

Policy Dimension

Challenges:

Persistent misconceptions and conflicting views on waste treatment methods have been identified as a major policy barrier. For example, the European Commission currently classifies gasification under energy recovery in the waste hierarchy, despite its potential to achieve a recycled carbon content of up to 90%, compared with 30-40% energy valorisation in energy recovery. This misclassification has not prevented funding but has complicated local permitting, prompting industry lobbying to recognise gasification as a recycling pathway. In the Netherlands, the absence of a unified political vision on waste further complicates progress towards the 2050 circularity goal, with debates over whether waste gasification represents an improvement over dominant incineration practices, and concerns about future waste stream availability and potential displacement through imports. Regulatory inconsistencies and unclear calculation rules also pose obstacles. Under RED II, only the biogenic fraction of a product is considered, excluding non-biogenic waste—a gap partially addressed in RED III for Renewable Fuels of Non-Biological Origin (RFNBOs) and recycled carbon fuels meeting specific GHG savings criteria. Additional inconsistencies exist between RED II and the International Maritime Organization's carbon accounting methodologies, and sector-specific rules in packaging, vehicles, and textiles impose closed-loop recycling requirements that are not compatible with mixed municipal solid waste, making feedstock selection and product outcome predictions challenging.

Recommendations/Good Practices:

Proposed solutions include introducing blending obligations for products like green gas and plastics, which are already under discussion at the EU level and could stimulate material applications of waste-based methanol. Harmonising regulatory calculation methodologies through full life cycle emission accounting, supported by default values for use and end-of-life phases while avoiding oversimplification, was also recommended. Additionally, shifting sustainability regulation upstream—by imposing thresholds on base chemicals for parameters such as toxicity, CO₂ impact, and recycled content—could simplify compliance and ensure consistent sustainability performance across all producers.

Sustainability Dimension (Environmental and Social)

Challenges:

Sustainability benefits of waste valorisation are often unevenly distributed. For instance, when a municipality diverts waste from incineration to methanol production, it can claim the resulting emission savings, while the chemical producer may face higher processing emissions, making it harder for them to benefit despite net global or regional savings. Companies also struggle to retain specialised knowledge on solid feedstock gasification as experienced staff retire, and limited R&D capacity means sustainability assessments often focus narrowly on CO₂ emissions due to legal requirements, neglecting other environmental and social aspects. Comparisons between municipal solid waste (MSW) treatment methods can be misleading. Gasification is sometimes unfavourably compared to mechanical recycling, assuming cost-effective waste separation is feasible, when in reality it is often impractical and energy-intensive, leading to incineration as the default. Although waste-to-syngas conversion is energy-intensive, it can be electrified, but current RED II rules

require using historical national electricity mixes, which in countries like the Netherlands still have high fossil shares. This approach fails to reflect increasing renewable energy shares and can distort comparisons with alternative waste processing or syngas production methods.

Recommendations/Good Practices:

Recommendations include developing a consistent, harmonised methodology for assessing the environmental impacts of different MSW treatment methods and introducing mechanisms to ensure that the benefits of waste valorisation are fairly shared among all parties involved.

Market Dimension

Challenges:

Waste-based methanol production faces two main non-level playing fields. First, there is a significant cost gap between methanol from biogenic, waste, and fossil feedstocks, with little economic incentive to choose non-fossil options unless buyers are willing to pay a premium. Second, EU market conditions favour methanol's use as an energy carrier—especially in sectors like maritime shipping covered by the extended ETS—over its application as a chemical or material. Financing is another major hurdle for scaling waste-to-methanol technologies, as investors prefer long-term off-take agreements for supply security, while companies often seek flexibility in rapidly evolving green chemistry markets. This has led some producers to favour the more favourable investment climate in the USA.

Subsidy structures also pose challenges. For instance, at the national level, schemes like the Dutch DEI+ can cover up to 50% of project costs but often fall short for both large and small initiatives due to high technical and financial risks. At the EU level, funding mechanisms such as the European Innovation Fund support large-scale sustainable projects but involve complex application processes and restrictive rules, with more favourable conditions for renewable energy production than for recycling or reuse of waste for material applications. This regulatory imbalance makes energy uses of methanol more financially attractive, even though end-use allocation can be unclear in practice.

Recommendations/Good Practices:

To close the cost gap between fossil- and waste-based methanol, stakeholders suggested either penalising fossil products to reflect their full environmental costs or lowering the price of biobased and waste-based alternatives through targeted public funding, especially for first-of-a-kind chemical plants. Such measures would recognise the value of waste and support investment in more sustainable production. Additionally, creating infrastructure to feed waste streams into industrial processes is seen as essential for enabling broader use of waste in biobased products and fostering an effective after-use economy.

Case Study 2: Bio-MEG from forest and agriculture biomass

Policy Dimension

Challenges:

At the time of this case study analysis and discussion the EU still lacked a dedicated policy framework to drive the transition of the chemicals and materials sector toward renewable carbon sources— whether biomass-derived, CO₂-based, or recycled. While energy and transport have clear decarbonisation targets, chemicals and materials are often overlooked, with current regulations

focusing mainly on emissions reduction rather than upstream material transformation. This results in unclear market incentives for biobased alternatives, and without mandatory biobased content targets, industries like packaging, textiles, and automotive have little reason to adopt bio-MEG. The absence of lifecycle-based carbon accounting further weakens recognition of bio-MEG's environmental benefits compared to fossil-based MEG. Recycling challenges persist, particularly for textiles, where blended fabrics and chemical additives hinder fibre separation, and for PET packaging, where mechanical recycling suffers from quality degradation over cycles. While chemical recycling can recover monomers like bio-MEG for high-quality PET, it remains energy-intensive and requires technological and economic improvements.

Recommendations/Good Practices:

Positive policy developments include the European Commission's initiative on sustainable carbon cycles, which promotes alternative carbon sources to balance the chemical sector's need for carbon with CO₂ reduction goals. Other relevant frameworks are the EU policy on biobased, biodegradable, and compostable plastics, the Packaging and Packaging Waste Regulation, and the Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability Towards a Toxic-Free Environment, all of which can support the uptake and integration of bio-MEG in different value chains.

Sustainability Dimension (Environmental and Social)

Challenges:

Key sustainability concerns for bio-MEG production include feedstock-related risks such as deforestation, biodiversity loss, and insufficient use of certification schemes. Unsustainable sourcing—especially of sugar-based crops like sugarcane or corn—can drive land-use change, soil degradation, and food security issues, particularly in regions with weak environmental governance. Not all producers follow rigorous standards like FSC or PEFC. The refining process also generates wastewater and residues that must be treated to avoid environmental contamination and health risks. Circularity remains a challenge, as PET recycling systems do not distinguish between fossil- and biobased MEG, and unlike biofuels, bio-MEG remains embedded in materials such as plastics and textiles, making carbon recirculation more complex.

Recommendations/Good Practices:

Sustainability can be improved through the use of residual biomass or high-yield algae systems to reduce reliance on arable land. Strengthening certification schemes to include biodiversity and social impact criteria would ensure more responsible sourcing. On the recycling side, investing in chemical recycling technologies to depolymerise bio-MEG-based plastics into monomers for repolymerisation, and enhancing mechanical recycling with better sorting and processing methods, can help maintain material quality and support circularity.

Market Dimension

Challenges:

Bio-MEG production faces significant risks from raw material cost fluctuations driven by climate variability, pests, and diseases, which can disrupt feedstock availability and cause biomass price volatility. This unpredictability, compounded by competition from other industries for the same feedstocks, undermines profit margins, complicates long-term planning, and deters investment by portraying the sector as high-risk. Bio-MEG also struggles to compete with cheaper petrochemical MEG, with oil price volatility further influencing competitiveness. Scaling up production is capital-intensive, requiring substantial financial backing. While EU and national funding opportunities

exist—such as Germany’s €2.8 billion programme to decarbonise industry through 15-year subsidies for sectors like chemicals, accessing these funds still involves navigating complex funding landscapes, and high costs remain a barrier to widespread adoption.

Recommendations/Good Practices:

To improve supply stability and reduce exposure to market volatility, companies like Avantium and Braskem diversify their biomass sources, use agricultural residues and non-food crops, and secure long-term supplier contracts. Integrating multiple stages of bio-MEG production —such as UPM’s approach— can lower costs through process integration, energy efficiency, and co-production of other biochemicals to boost competitiveness. Public-private partnerships also play a key role, with examples like UPM’s Leuna biorefinery in Germany benefiting from regional authority support to facilitate infrastructure investment for bio-MEG production.

6.2.3. Plastics sector

This section summarises the key challenges and recommendations identified during the co-creation workshop for the plastics sector. The insights are presented for the plastics sector as a whole first and followed by the specific insights for the case studies on polylactic acid (PLA), polypropylene (PP) from used cooking oil, and cellulose acetate (CA).

Whole Sector Analysis

Policy dimension

Challenges:

The plastics sector faces several policy-related challenges, such as a lack of a harmonised definition for bio-based plastics and polymers. Furthermore, the absence of a favourable regulatory framework for bioplastics (e.g., no incentives for renewable carbon) and a missing strategy for valorising bio-based versus fossil-based plastics are significant hurdles. Additionally, some bio-based materials, like CA, are governed by different regulatory frameworks, adding to the complexity of policies governing the sector. Stakeholders also highlighted that existing biodegradability tests are insufficient to comprehensively assess environmental impacts, particularly concerning microplastic release. The limited availability of bio-based raw materials and the higher production costs associated with the production of biopolymers compared to their fossil-based counterparts add to the complexity of designing fitting policies for the plastics sector.

Recommendations/ Good practices:

To address these challenges, it is recommended to leverage existing frameworks such as the EU Plastics Strategy, Circular Economy Action Plan, and the EU Communication 2022 on bio-based, biodegradable, and compostable plastics. Building on directives like (EU) 2015/720 (lightweight plastics carrier bags) and EU 2019/904 (Single Use Plastics Directive - SUP) is also viewed as crucial by the stakeholders. Implementing mandatory bio-based content to complement mandatory recycled content (e.g., in PPWL, ELV) and providing financial support (e.g., incentives for bio-based materials, support for scaling up TRL >5) from the government are vital steps. Additionally, creating a legally binding framework with clear sustainability criteria and incentives for labels and externally audited third-party certification systems is essential. The bioeconomy strategy should be improved by removing limitations and constraints, such as focusing solely on marine biodegradable materials. Finally, providing a coherent and fact-based definition of bio-based

polymers across all policy frameworks, shifting from political definitions (e.g., in SUPD) to fact-based ones that differentiate between polymer types, is highly recommended.

Sustainability Dimension (Environmental and Social)

Challenges:

From a sustainability perspective, a key challenge for the sector is the difficulty in clearly communicating the benefits of bio-based plastics. Contributing to this issue is the lack of understanding of the environmental impact of bio-based plastics at EoL. In this context the stakeholders specifically mentioned the lack of understanding of biodegradation processes and their environmental impacts due to inadequate test methods. Other challenges highlighted during the workshop are the insufficient multi-stakeholder research into the circular bio-based economy and the lack of end-of-life possibilities and infrastructures for proper treatment of bio-based and biodegradable plastic waste. Furthermore, a lack of transparent chain of custody and sustainable sources for bio-based feedstock (e.g., potential competition with food) poses a significant challenge.

Recommendations/ Good Practices:

To foster sustainability, it is recommended to promote transparency and consumer awareness of bio-based products. A comprehensive sustainability assessment of products across their entire life cycle should be promoted. Additionally, supporting the development of circular economy models and cascading uses for biopolymers is viewed as crucial. Lastly, the stakeholders highlighted that promoting the proactive integration of local stakeholders and authorities can contribute significantly to sustainable practices.

Market Dimension

Challenges:

With regard to the market, the plastics sector faces several challenges. First, the stakeholders point to the consumer confusion regarding bio-based plastics. Adding to the consumer confusion and contributing to a low demand of bioplastics is the fact that they are more expensive than their fossil counterparts, partly due to the lack of monetisation of environmental costs. The stakeholders note that the high costs and low availability of bioplastics are also linked to several market-related bottlenecks, including low investments, long time to market, and the low availability of well-equipped specialised tech parks and plants open to (small) third parties. A lack of involvement from end-of-life stakeholders to guarantee proper treatment of bioplastic waste and a lack of market pull measures to promote willingness to use products containing circular materials further complicate market adoption.

Recommendations/ Good Practices:

To strengthen the market for bio-based plastics, it is recommended to establish incentive schemes that enhance the use of biomass for materials, including minimum bio-based plastics content targets for key applications to create market pull. Enhancing the quality and quantity of collected biowaste suitable as feedstock for plastics production is also vital. Finally, implementing mandatory separate collection of organic household waste for organics recycling in all EU Member States is a key recommendation.

Case Study Analyses

Case Study 1: Polylactic acid (PLA)

Policy Dimension

Challenges:

For PLA only one specific policy challenge was mentioned that isn't included in the challenges for the whole sector listed above. This challenge is the insufficient support for the use of compostable plastics in food and soil applications.

Recommendations/ Good Practices:

To address this challenge, it is recommended to support the use of compostable plastics for food and soil applications and to improve legislation related to fertilisers and microplastics.

Sustainability Dimension (Environmental and Social)

Challenges:

For PLA, one of the central sustainability challenges concerns the limitations of current biodegradability certifications. Existing certification schemes largely focus on measuring full degradation and the total amount of CO₂ released during the process. While these parameters provide some assurance, they do not fully reflect the complexity of how PLA and similar materials behave in diverse real-world environments such as soil, marine ecosystems, or industrial composting facilities. Crucially, there is a lack of certification systems that adequately address "readily biodegradable" materials, which degrade more quickly and under a broader range of conditions than conventional plastics but do not always reach the strict standards of full degradation. This gap creates uncertainty for producers and consumers alike, undermining confidence in the environmental benefits of PLA and slowing down its wider adoption in sustainable markets.

Market Dimension

Challenges:

The PLA case study highlights several market-related challenges. Scaling up production capacity remains difficult, not only because of complex and often slow bureaucratic procedures but also due to limited availability of suitable land for establishing production sites. These constraints delay expansion and hinder the ability of producers to respond to growing demand. In addition, the sector faces high initial investment costs combined with a lengthy time-to-market, which discourages new entrants and slows down the commercialisation of PLA-based products.

Recommendations/ Good practices:

To address these challenges, it is crucial to increase PLA production capacity through supportive policies and streamlined administrative processes that facilitate investment in new facilities. At the same time, a stronger understanding of the chemical and physical characteristics of PLA should be developed, ensuring that research and innovation are directed towards the most feasible applications. For example, PLA is not well suited for textiles, but holds significant potential in other product categories where its performance characteristics can be fully utilised.

Case Study 2: Polypropylene (PP) from used cooking oil

Policy Dimension

Challenges:

The PP from used cooking oil case study highlights notable policy-related challenges. Collection systems for used cooking oils are currently inefficient, particularly at the household level, where a significant portion of waste oil is either discarded improperly or not collected at all. Furthermore, industries making use of PP derived from used cooking oils face a lack of clear market regulation, which creates uncertainty and limits the scaling up of such practices.

Recommendations/ Good practices:

To address these challenges, improvements to oil waste regulations are essential. Clearer frameworks and stronger enforcement mechanisms could help to increase the collection rate of used cooking oils and provide industries with the regulatory certainty needed to invest in processing capacities and market development.

Sustainability Dimension (Environmental and Social)

Challenges:

From a sustainability perspective, improper disposal of used cooking oil represents a serious environmental challenge. When released into sewage systems or the environment, waste oil acts as a pollutant, leading to blockages, water contamination, and broader ecological damage.

Recommendations/ Good practices:

To mitigate these impacts, efforts should focus on significantly improving the separate collection of organic waste, with specific emphasis on used cooking oils. Enhancing collection infrastructure, combined with awareness-raising campaigns for households and businesses, would help ensure that waste oil is redirected into valuable circular applications rather than causing environmental harm.

No market dimension challenges or recommendations were identified by the stakeholders during the co-creation workshop.

Case Study 3: Cellulose acetate (CA)

Policy Dimension

Challenges:

The CA case study highlights several policy-related challenges. Circularity strategies for CA need to be developed in line with the specific requirements of different market sectors, yet new market entries are often obstructed by complex and restrictive regulations. At the same time, policy frameworks addressing bio-based materials remain insufficiently coherent, creating fragmentation and uncertainty for businesses aiming to innovate and scale circular solutions.

Recommendations/ Good practices:

To address these challenges, coherence and clarity of policy frameworks should be improved, with particular attention to strengthening the interconnections between different regulatory areas. In parallel, policies should promote the development of bio-based and biodegradable polymer

materials with unique properties, such as a high softening point, to enhance the competitiveness and applicability of CA across diverse market sectors.

Sustainability Dimension (Environmental and Social)

Challenges:

The production of CA presents notable sustainability challenges. The process is highly energy intensive, requiring substantial amounts of both electricity and heat. Moreover, the production process is often too complex to fit within the parameters of some existing sustainability certification schemes, creating difficulties in ensuring transparency and credibility for environmental performance.

Recommendations/ Good practices:

Several measures can help address these challenges. Opportunities exist to utilise excess heat from CA production to supply surrounding industrial partners and even residential households, thereby increasing overall efficiency. Tackling plastic pollution, and specifically the issue of microplastics, requires the development of biodegradable and non-persistent CA materials. Continuous improvements in energy efficiency and process optimisation are also essential to minimise environmental impacts. Collaboration with certification providers will be critical to adapt existing schemes and share best practices for complex production processes. Finally, advancing bio-based and biodegradable polymer materials with unique properties, such as a high softening point, can strengthen the sustainability profile and competitiveness of CA.

Market Dimension

Challenges:

From a market perspective, CA faces two key challenges. First, its production costs remain higher than those of fossil-based counterparts, which restricts competitiveness. Second, many applications of CA involve its use as part of a composite, complicating recycling processes and limiting its potential contribution to circular economy objectives.

Recommendations/ Good practices:

To overcome these challenges, stronger collaboration is needed between research organisations and industrial partners for the joint development of products and services. Such partnerships can help identify feasible applications where CA's unique properties provide a competitive advantage, while also driving innovation to address cost and recycling constraints.

6.2.4. Construction sector

This section summarises the key challenges and recommendations identified during the co-creation workshop for the construction sector. The insights are presented for the construction sector as a whole first and followed by the specific insights for the case studies on Cross Laminated Timber (CLT), Biochar as an additive for concrete, and Hemp insulation.

Whole Sector Analysis

Policy dimension

Challenges:

The widespread adoption and market integration of bio-based construction products are significantly hindered by insufficient regulatory support tailored to their unique characteristics. Existing regulations are primarily designed for geo- and fossil-based materials, failing to account for the distinct properties and environmental benefits of bio-based alternatives. This regulatory misalignment creates barriers to certification, standardisation, and large-scale use, placing bio-based materials at a disadvantage. As a result, their entry into the market becomes more challenging, despite their potential to contribute to sustainable construction practices. Developing targeted policies that recognise and support the specific needs of bio-based construction products would not only encourage innovation but also build greater confidence among industry stakeholders.

Recommendations/ Good practices:

Facilitating knowledge exchange and mutual learning through collaborative initiatives like SUSTRACK plays a crucial role in fostering innovation and the adoption of best practices in sustainable construction. Projects like this create valuable opportunities for stakeholders to share insights, address common challenges, and co-develop effective strategies for promoting bio-based materials. Strengthening such networks accelerates the transition toward a more sustainable and resilient built environment. At the same time, adapting regulatory frameworks to reflect the unique properties of bio-based materials is essential for ensuring fairer treatment and fostering innovation. By acknowledging their environmental and performance advantages, policymakers can establish a more supportive and inclusive regulatory landscape that encourages the widespread use and integration of bio-based construction solutions.

Sustainability Dimension (Environmental and Social)

Challenges:

The adoption and development of sustainable and innovative construction practices are often hindered by a lack of sufficient knowledge, as education and traditional training methods remain largely focused on fossil-based materials. This continued reliance on conventional approaches limits awareness and understanding of alternative, eco-friendly solutions, thereby slowing the transition to more sustainable construction methods. Additionally, the shortage of skilled workers and the lack of formal training programs across the bio-based materials value chain pose significant barriers to the industry's growth. Addressing these gaps in knowledge and workforce development is essential for supporting the widespread adoption of bio-based materials and advancing sustainable construction practices.

Recommendations/ Good Practices:

Achieving social and professional community acceptance is vital for the widespread adoption of new materials and sustainable construction practices. Overcoming scepticism, dispelling misconceptions, and clearly communicating the long-term benefits of bio-based solutions are key to building trust and encouraging industry-wide uptake. Engaging stakeholders through targeted education, advocacy, and real-world demonstrations can effectively integrate sustainable materials into mainstream construction. To support this shift, expanding education and training in bio-based construction is essential. Comprehensive programs that equip architects, builders,

and other professionals with the necessary knowledge and skills will help close the current expertise gap. Investing in specialised training initiatives, apprenticeships, and certification programs will cultivate a skilled workforce capable of driving innovation and advancing environmentally responsible building practices.

Market Dimension

Challenges:

The transition to a more sustainable construction industry is hindered by several interconnected challenges. A key issue is the insufficient focus on designing long-lasting buildings with circularity and recyclability in mind. This oversight results in excessive material waste, inefficient resource use, and a higher environmental footprint. Without incorporating principles such as durability, material reuse, and end-of-life planning, buildings contribute significantly to resource depletion and landfill accumulation, slowing the adoption of innovative and eco-friendly construction practices. Another major challenge lies in optimising the use of local material streams. Fragmented supply chains, the absence of standardised quality control, and limited infrastructure for large-scale processing make the use of local materials inefficient and costly compared to traditional, widely available alternatives. These barriers limit the potential for more sustainable and localised construction practices. Access to capital is also a significant constraint for the development and commercialisation of new bio-based products. High perceived risks, regulatory uncertainty, and unclear market demand make investors and financial institutions hesitant to fund these innovations. This financial gap restricts opportunities for research, development, and scaling, slowing down the growth of the bio-based sector.

Furthermore, the absence of a strong lobbying presence for bio-based products contributes to an imbalance in policy and market support. Fossil-based industries have long benefited from influential advocacy that shapes regulations, subsidies, and incentives in their favour. In contrast, bio-based alternatives struggle to receive comparable attention, limiting their growth and broader adoption. Finally, the relatively small size of the bio-based market prevents it from benefiting from economies of scale and technological learning effects—critical factors for reducing costs and enhancing efficiency. Without increased production volumes and broader market integration, bio-based products remain less competitive, both economically and operationally, compared to conventional materials. Addressing these systemic barriers is essential for enabling a more resilient, innovative, and environmentally responsible construction industry.

Recommendations/ Good Practices:

Integrating a variety of bio-based materials—such as bamboo, wood, natural fibers, and mycelium—into construction and design poses several challenges, particularly in terms of material compatibility, performance consistency, and the lack of standardised guidelines. While these materials offer significant sustainability benefits, their distinct properties require specialised knowledge to ensure they work effectively together in structural applications. The absence of clear regulations, certification processes, and performance benchmarks further complicates their adoption, making it difficult for builders and designers to confidently incorporate them into mainstream projects.

Additionally, applying systems thinking in building design remains a complex task. Evaluating a building's entire life cycle—from material sourcing and construction to use and eventual demolition—demands a holistic understanding of various interrelated factors, including environmental impact, energy consumption, resource efficiency, and social implications. These factors often involve trade-offs that are difficult to balance without robust decision-making tools.

The lack of standardised frameworks and tools for life cycle assessment (LCA) across all building stages further limits the practical application of this approach. Addressing these challenges requires a fundamental shift in design practices toward greater collaboration, targeted education, and the development of comprehensive, user-friendly LCA tools to support the creation of buildings that are safe, sustainable, and optimised throughout their entire lifespan.

Case Study Analyses

Case Study 1: CLT

Policy Dimension

Challenges:

A significant barrier to the widespread adoption of timber in construction across the EU and national levels is the persistent lack of knowledge and expertise regarding its use. This knowledge gap hinders the development of effective policies and best practices needed to unlock timber's full potential as a sustainable building material. Compounding this issue, existing building norms and standards often favour conventional materials, creating regulatory environments that are unfavourable to timber construction. These standards typically fail to account for the unique properties and environmental benefits of timber, thereby limiting its integration into mainstream building practices.

Current fire safety regulations present a major challenge to the use of timber as well, as they frequently rely on outdated assumptions that do not reflect recent advancements in timber technology. Innovations such as engineered wood products and fire-resistant treatments have significantly improved the safety and performance of timber-based structures, yet regulatory frameworks have been slow to adapt. These outdated restrictions not only constrain the application of modern timber solutions but also impede progress toward more sustainable construction methods. Addressing these regulatory and knowledge-based obstacles is essential for promoting timber as a viable and environmentally responsible alternative in the construction sector.

Recommendations/ Good Practices:

Revamping building norms and regulations to support the use of bio-based materials is a critical step toward fostering a more sustainable construction industry. Modernising standards to acknowledge the performance, safety, and environmental advantages of materials such as timber, hemp, and other bio-based solutions can drive innovation, reduce dependency on carbon-intensive materials, and accelerate the shift toward a circular, low-carbon economy. To ensure consistency and transparency across the sector, it is also essential for governments to provide clearer, more comprehensive, and directly actionable guidelines for assessing embodied carbon emissions in construction materials. Standardised methodologies will allow for more accurate comparisons and informed decision-making throughout the design and building process.

Equally important is the integration of biogenic carbon assessment into these frameworks. By recognising the carbon sequestration potential of bio-based materials—such as the ability of timber or hemp to store atmospheric carbon—alongside their embodied emissions, policymakers and industry professionals can gain a more holistic understanding of these materials' true climate impact. This approach enables more accurate evaluations of sustainability performance and supports the broader adoption of climate-positive construction practices.

Sustainability dimension

Challenges:

Common misconceptions surrounding the use of wood and other bio-based materials in construction often focus on perceived shortcomings in durability, fire safety, and environmental impact, particularly with regard to the sustainability of wood harvesting practices. These concerns persist despite significant technological advancements and the implementation of responsible sourcing methods that effectively address such issues. A major contributing factor to these misconceptions is the general lack of awareness about the quality and biodiversity of European forestry. Many people remain unaware that European forest management is guided by strict standards that emphasise sustainable harvesting, biodiversity conservation, and ecosystem restoration. This limited understanding can undermine confidence in European timber as a renewable and environmentally responsible construction material. Current LCAs frequently fail to capture the full environmental value of bio-based materials. Key aspects such as carbon sequestration, biodegradability, and the positive impacts of sustainable sourcing are often overlooked. Land use indicators in particular tend to reflect negatively on wood, despite sustainable forestry practices that mitigate these concerns. This leads to incomplete and sometimes misleading evaluations of bio-based materials' environmental performance.

To further strengthen the case for bio-based construction, attention must also be given to material safety throughout the lifecycle. Ensuring the use of non-toxic adhesives in engineered wood products and other composite bio-based materials is essential—not only for protecting human health during construction and use but also for minimising environmental harm at the end of a building's life. Addressing these knowledge gaps and improving assessment frameworks is critical for advancing the adoption of bio-based materials and supporting the broader transition to sustainable construction.

Recommendations/ Good Practices:

Implementing dynamic LCAs and refining the land use indicator are key steps toward providing a more accurate and comprehensive evaluation of the environmental impacts of bio-based products. Unlike static assessments, dynamic LCAs can reflect changes in land management practices over time, offering a clearer and more realistic picture of the long-term sustainability benefits of materials such as wood. This approach would enhance the credibility and visibility of bio-based materials in sustainable construction. At the same time, promoting a broader shift toward a bio-based mindset is essential for driving the adoption of renewable, biodegradable, and low-carbon material choices. By embedding sustainability at the core of material selection and design practices, the construction industry can stimulate innovation, reduce environmental impact, and contribute to the development of a more circular and resilient economy.

Further research into bio-based adhesives is also critical for advancing sustainable building practices. Developing high-performance, non-toxic alternatives to conventional adhesives can reduce environmental and health risks while improving the durability and lifecycle performance of bio-based construction materials. To support transparency and informed decision-making, incentivising producers to develop Environmental Product Declarations (EPDs) through tax benefits or public support would be highly effective. Such measures would encourage wider adoption of sustainable practices across the supply chain, promote eco-friendly materials in the market, and empower stakeholders to make choices based on verified environmental performance data.

Market dimension

Challenges:

The absence of uniform European standards in the construction sector presents a significant barrier to efficiency and collaboration. With each country maintaining its own interpretations or specific regulatory features, cross-border projects face increased complexity, time delays, and additional costs. This fragmentation undermines the seamless integration of sustainable practices and technologies, particularly for bio-based construction methods that benefit from broader market access and shared best practices. Timber construction, while increasingly recognised for its sustainability and speed—especially when paired with off-site manufacturing—still faces challenges in areas such as insurance. Concerns about fire resistance often lead insurers to demand additional safety measures or impose higher premiums on timber projects. However, advancements in fire-resistant treatments and engineered wood products now offer effective solutions to mitigate these risks. As awareness of these innovations grows, insurance models can evolve to become more supportive of timber construction, thereby improving affordability and accessibility.

Another hurdle arises in the financial structuring of public projects. Payment terms are typically aligned with the slower timelines of traditional concrete construction, creating mismatches when applied to faster wood-based building methods. This misalignment can strain cash flow and hinder project progress. Adapting payment structures to reflect the accelerated schedules of timber construction would help unlock its full potential and facilitate broader adoption. In addition, the current lack of standardisation in Environmental Product Declarations (EPDs) across European countries creates inconsistencies in how environmental impacts are assessed and compared. This variability hampers informed decision-making and complicates sustainability evaluations. Establishing harmonised EPD standards would enhance transparency, support consistent comparisons across markets, and promote more sustainable choices throughout the construction industry.

Recommendations/ Good Practices:

Introducing carbon credits for bio-based materials would offer a powerful incentive for their adoption by formally recognising their role in carbon sequestration and emission reduction. By assigning value to the environmental benefits of materials such as timber, hemp, or mycelium, a carbon credit system could accelerate the transition to a low-carbon economy in construction and manufacturing. This would not only encourage innovation in sustainable materials but also help align financial and environmental goals across the value chain.

In the context of fire safety, shifting the regulatory focus from fire resistance to fire reaction is a key step toward enabling the broader use of bio-based materials. Evaluating how materials behave during a fire—such as their combustibility and smoke production—offers a more nuanced and performance-based assessment. This approach balances safety with innovation, allowing sustainable materials to meet fire safety standards without being unfairly penalised by outdated or overly rigid criteria.

At the policy level, establishing comprehensive European norms is essential for unifying regulations and practices across member states. Standardisation would reduce administrative burdens, streamline construction processes, and promote fair competition, making it easier for sustainable practices and products to gain traction across borders. Consistent norms would also enhance investor and consumer confidence in bio-based construction solutions. Additionally, implementing restrictions on the export of unprocessed timber from the EU would promote local value creation. Encouraging in-region processing supports the European timber industry, generates jobs, reduces transportation emissions, and fosters the development of high-value, sustainable products within

the EU. This policy would also strengthen the region's role as a leader in sustainable construction. The establishment of European-wide recognised EPDs with CE marking would provide a standardised and credible framework for assessing the environmental impact of construction materials. This would ensure transparency, improve comparability, and facilitate informed decision-making across the sector, reinforcing trust in sustainable materials and supporting their widespread adoption throughout Europe.

Case Study 2: Biochar as an additive for concrete

Policy Dimension

Challenges:

The lack of standards for innovative concrete products presents a major barrier to the widespread adoption of bio-based concrete solutions. Without clear guidelines, high-performing materials struggle to gain market access and regulatory approval. In addition, the certification process for components like biochar in concrete remains lengthy and complex, further hindering the development and integration of these sustainable alternatives into mainstream construction practices.

Recommendations/ Good Practices:

A shift from the current recipe-based standards to performance-based standards is recommended to better support innovation and the adoption of sustainable construction materials. Performance-based approaches allow for greater flexibility in meeting functional requirements, enabling the use of advanced and bio-based materials that may not fit within traditional specifications.

Several EU-level frameworks and initiatives are regarded as positive examples of supportive policy measures. These include the Construction Products Regulation, the EU Emissions Trading System, the Carbon Removal Certification Framework, the EU Green Deal, the EU Taxonomy for Sustainable Activities, and the Sustainable Carbon Cycles initiative. These instruments are seen as valuable steps toward fostering sustainability, transparency, and carbon reduction across the construction and materials sectors.

Sustainability dimension

Recommendations/ Good Practices:

Carbon accounting mechanisms, such as the Carbon Removal Certification Framework, are recognised as good practices for supporting the transition to a low-carbon economy. These frameworks help quantify and verify carbon removal efforts, providing transparency and accountability in emission reductions. By establishing clear criteria and certification processes, such initiatives promote the use of sustainable materials and encourage the adoption of climate-positive practices across the construction sector.

Market dimension

Challenges:

A persistent challenge in the biochar sector is the difficulty of securing biomass feedstock from suppliers that can deliver consistent quality and supply, along with predictable and manageable costs. Variability in feedstock availability, composition, and pricing creates uncertainty in production planning and limits the scalability of biochar applications, particularly in construction

and other industrial uses. Establishing more reliable and standardised biomass supply chains is essential for supporting the growth and commercial viability of biochar-based solutions.

Recommendations/ Good Practices:

To address the high cost of biochar and the limited willingness of customers to pay a premium, increased incentives for conducting pilot projects are essential. These mechanisms would promote early adoption by enabling customers to explore and validate the performance and benefits of biochar-based solutions in practical, real-world settings. By reducing the financial risk associated with initial implementation, pilot projects can help build market confidence, showcase the value of biochar applications, and pave the way for broader acceptance. In turn, this would stimulate demand, support commercialisation efforts, and contribute to the development of a more competitive and sustainable biochar market.

Case Study 3: Hemp insulation

Policy Dimension

Challenges:

Regulatory uncertainties and inconsistent restrictions across regions are significantly limiting the potential of industrial hemp as a sustainable and innovative building material. These legal barriers impede the widespread adoption of hemp-based construction solutions and slow the pace of industry development. Compounding this issue is the lack of targeted incentives at the EU level for hemp insulation and other renewable, plant-based building materials. Without dedicated support mechanisms, these sustainable alternatives struggle to scale up and compete with conventional materials, hindering innovation and market growth. The absence of harmonised EU standards further restricts market access for many hemp-based products, as they are often unable to obtain the CE marking—a key requirement for regulatory approval and broader market acceptance. While efforts are underway to secure European Technical Assessments (ETAs) and push for the introduction of CE marking at both national and EU levels, the current regulatory gap continues to limit the uptake of these materials across Europe. Additionally, current methods for assessing thermal performance fail to account for hempcrete’s unique hygro-thermal properties, such as moisture regulation and long-term insulation behaviour, resulting in an incomplete evaluation of its real-world performance. Addressing these regulatory and technical challenges is crucial to fully realising the role of hemp in advancing sustainable construction across Europe.

Recommendations/ Good Practices:

Revising thermal performance testing standards for bio-based materials is essential to accurately reflect their hygrothermal and hygroscopic behaviours. Existing methods often neglect the effects of moisture absorption and release, which are critical to understanding the long-term thermal efficiency and real-world performance of materials like hempcrete. Updating these standards would provide a more accurate and comprehensive evaluation of their capabilities. At the same time, greater education and a shift in public and professional perception are urgently needed to overcome persistent misconceptions about industrial hemp. Many remain unaware of its versatility, environmental benefits, and broad potential across industries, particularly construction. Raising awareness through accurate information and targeted outreach can foster broader acceptance and unlock its value in sustainable development. Reducing production and processing barriers within Europe is also crucial to enable the industrial hemp sector to scale effectively. Furthermore, promoting hemp as part of crop rotation systems enhances soil health, reduces erosion, and supports sustainable farming by improving aeration, nutrient cycling, and

weed suppression. Integrating hemp into agriculture not only benefits ecosystems but also provides farmers with an economically viable and environmentally responsible alternative.

Sustainability dimension

Challenges:

The lack of knowledge and awareness surrounding industrial hemp, combined with the lingering stigma attached to hemp products, poses a significant barrier to their widespread adoption. Many individuals continue to conflate industrial hemp with its psychoactive relative, cannabis, leading to misconceptions about its safety, legality, and usefulness. This confusion undermines public trust and limits acceptance, even within industries that could benefit from hemp's sustainable qualities. To overcome these barriers, it is essential to educate both the public and industry stakeholders about the clear distinctions between industrial hemp and other cannabis varieties. Highlighting the environmental, economic, and functional benefits of hemp-based products can help shift perceptions and unlock the material's full potential as a key contributor to sustainable development.

In parallel, addressing broader environmental challenges requires a fundamental shift toward sustainable practices and innovative solutions. Emphasising the use of eco-friendly materials and technologies not only reduces environmental impact but also fosters economic growth and long-term resilience. Prioritising sustainability in design, manufacturing, and construction practices can drive meaningful progress toward a more circular and resource-efficient economy. By embracing innovation and environmentally responsible approaches, we can build a more sustainable future that balances ecological stewardship with economic opportunity.

Recommendations/ Good Practices:

Focusing on long-term construction developments that emphasise sustainability, resilience, and future-proofing is essential for creating buildings that can adapt to environmental challenges and evolving societal needs. By integrating eco-friendly materials, energy-efficient designs, and flexible structural systems, these developments can maintain their relevance and performance over time. This approach not only reduces the environmental footprint of the built environment but also ensures that future generations inherit structures that are durable, efficient, and adaptable. Achieving such forward-thinking construction goals depends on a strong, well-supported bio-based supply chain. From raw material cultivation to end-product manufacturing, every stage plays a critical role in delivering sustainable solutions. Strengthening this supply chain enhances the quality, efficiency, and market impact of bio-based materials, which are key to meeting the demands of resilient and environmentally responsible construction. A well-integrated supply chain also drives innovation and supports the broader shift toward circular economic models across multiple industries.

Central to this effort is the promotion of local procurement of bio-based feedstock. Sourcing materials regionally reduces the environmental impact of long-distance transportation, encourages sustainable agricultural practices, and supports local economies. By reinforcing local supply chains, we not only minimise carbon emissions but also enhance community resilience and create a more self-sufficient, sustainable production system. This localised approach complements broader construction and supply chain strategies, forming a cohesive path toward a greener and more resilient built environment.

Market dimension

Challenges:

The absence of standardised guidelines for bio-based materials significantly hampers their broader adoption and certification. Without clear and universally accepted standards, manufacturers struggle to ensure consistent product quality and meet regulatory requirements. This uncertainty slows the development and market introduction of bio-based materials, limiting their potential impact. Establishing standardised guidelines would streamline certification processes, boost consumer confidence, and accelerate the widespread use of these sustainable alternatives. Bio-based materials, such as hemp insulation, are often subjected to the same regulations and constraints as fossil-based materials without taking their environmental benefits and additional characteristics into account. This outdated regulatory approach fails to acknowledge the unique advantages of bio-based options, including better thermal regulation, reduced environmental impact, and enhanced sustainability. Updating regulations to reflect these distinct characteristics would encourage greater adoption of bio-based materials and support the shift toward greener, more efficient building practices.

Additionally, the limited availability of industrial-scale hemp processing facilities across the EU restricts the growth of the hemp-based materials industry. The lack of sufficient infrastructure for large-scale processing leads to high production costs and inefficient supply chains, further hindering the widespread use of hemp-based products. Expanding processing capabilities would increase the availability of raw materials, lower costs, and facilitate the scaling of sustainable construction solutions throughout Europe.

Recommendations/ Good Practices:

There has been steady growth in market awareness among final users, architects, builders, and real estate developers, with a notable spike in the past two years. This increasing interest may signal the beginning of the long-anticipated exponential growth in the adoption of sustainable, hemp-based materials. As more stakeholders recognise the benefits of these eco-friendly alternatives, the market is poised for further expansion, potentially transforming the construction industry and driving broader sustainability efforts.

6.3. Closing Event

The closing event of the “Pathway to DESIGN the Circular Bio-Based Transition” marked the conclusion of a series of workshops dedicated to co-creating policy pathways for the transition of four carbon-intensive sectors—textiles, construction, plastics, and chemicals. The event brought together experts and stakeholders from research, industry, policy, and civil society to transform the workshop outcomes into concrete policy recommendations, with the aim of supporting industrial and political actors in advancing the circular bio-based economy.

Building on the contributions of more than 175 stakeholders and the presentation of 20 case studies throughout the workshop series, the closing event presented a comprehensive synthesis of the main takeaways. These included the mapping of key challenges, identification of good practices, and formulation of recommendations across policy, environmental, social, and economic dimensions. This synthesis provided a consolidated knowledge base on sector-specific barriers and opportunities, as well as inspiration for future actions.

In addition to presenting workshop outcomes, the event showcased SUSTRACK’s methodologies and tools for monitoring the transition toward a circular bio-based economy. Particular attention

was given to the dynamic scenario-based tool (GEM model), which enables systemic analysis of existing trends and proposed interventions by simulating transformative modelling scenarios. This approach offers valuable insights to inform both industry practices and policy development. Furthermore, the event highlighted SUSTRACK’s contributions to EU-level bioeconomy policy, ensuring that project findings are aligned with, and feed into, ongoing policy processes.

The closing event was organised in a conference format with interactive sessions to maximise stakeholder participation. This format facilitated dialogue and enabled the collection of feedback from diverse actors, which in turn served to fine-tune SUSTRACK’s methodologies and tools to better respond to industry and policy needs.

The expected outcomes of the event were threefold: to provide actionable knowledge in the form of good practices, barriers, challenges, and recommendations; to capture stakeholder perspectives for refining project outputs; and to generate policy recommendations with the potential to inform the revision of the European Bioeconomy Strategy. In this way, the DESIGN closing event provided a bridge between co-creation activities and concrete policy support, reinforcing the project’s contribution to the sustainable transition of key European industrial sectors.

6.4. Main Takeaways

Drawing on lessons from the INSPIRE Conference, the DESIGN phase introduced a revised format with four targeted workshops followed by a closing event. This shorter, thematic structure kept stakeholders more engaged and allowed discussions to focus on sector-specific issues in chemicals, construction, textiles, and plastics. The closing event then consolidated outcomes into actionable recommendations.

Stakeholder participation also improved. Experts were invited to interactive sessions based on their specific knowledge, while plenary parts remained broader, ensuring both inclusiveness and technical depth. This approach addressed the challenges of INSPIRE, where generalist participants sometimes struggled with technical content.

The use of interactive tools such as Miro and Mentimeter was another success. Clearer guidance and structured facilitation encouraged active engagement, resulting in more relevant and usable inputs. With contributions from over 175 stakeholders and 20 case studies, the DESIGN conference series produced a comprehensive mapping of challenges, good practices, and recommendations across policy, environmental, societal, and economic dimensions.

Overall, the DESIGN Conference confirmed the value of adapting the engagement process: shorter, better targeted sessions, improved facilitation, and structured interactive tools created a more productive environment and generated outcomes that are directly actionable for policy and practice.

7. IMPLEMENT CONFERENCE

7.1. Overall Structure and Main Objectives

Between February and March 2025, SUSTRACK organised the “From Vision to Implementation: Shaping Policies to Boost Circular Bio-Based Transition” series of workshops and a concluding conference. These events, following a format similar to that of the DESIGN conference (Figure 7), were conceived to achieve several interconnected objectives. Firstly, they aimed to gain insights

from keynote speakers who outlined the challenges of the transition, the evolving policy landscape, and future visions for the transformation of the four key sectors addressed by SUSTRACK - chemicals, textiles, plastics, and construction. Building on this, the workshops served as a platform to explore policy options identified by the SUSTRACK project that could contribute to accelerating the circular bio-based transition in these sectors. Participants were actively engaged in evaluating the strengths and weaknesses of these proposed policy options, as well as in discussing further opportunities and policy approaches that could support the shift towards a more sustainable economic model. Each workshop also contributed to SUSTRACK’s broader effort to foster dialogue with stakeholders from some of the most carbon-intensive sectors beyond energy, promoting a co-creation process grounded in sector-specific realities. The format of the workshops was carefully designed to maximise engagement and facilitate meaningful discussions. Each session opened with keynote speakers who provided concise presentations outlining the current transformation status, key challenges, and sector-specific perspectives. This was followed by presentations from the SUSTRACK consortium, which detailed the project’s methodology for identifying relevant policy options and presented the selected policies for further consideration. The workshops then moved into an interactive session using MIRO Board, where participants were encouraged to actively discuss the proposed policy options, suggest alternatives, and share insights on potential impacts of implementation on their sectors, as well as broader implications for politics and society.

The series culminated in the IMPLEMENT Conference, held online on 21 March 2025, which presented an overview of the main takeaways from the workshops, SUSTRACK’s methods and tools to monitor and support the transition, and the key findings from the 11 case studies developed across the four sectors. These outcomes contributed to shaping actionable policy recommendations for both policymakers and industry stakeholders, reinforcing the project’s ambition to translate vision into implementation for a circular bio-based future.

Figure 7: IMPLEMENT conference structure

The target audience for these workshops primarily included policy experts and stakeholders from the textile sector, with representation from policy-making bodies, research organisations, industry, and civil society. A total of 201 participants took part in the workshops and the final conference. To facilitate interaction and ensure a structured and engaging discussion process,

tools such as the MIRO Board and PowerPoint presentations were employed. These tools supported the collection of feedback, the visualisation of ideas, and the structured presentation of content throughout the sessions. The conference factsheet is accessible through the following [link](#).

7.2. IMPLEMENT Conference Results

7.2.1. Textile Sector

This section provides a summary of the key strengths, weaknesses, and additional recommendations identified for the proposed policy instruments targeting the textile sector, as discussed during the co-creation workshop. The findings are organised into two groups: first, the circularity policy set, followed by the biomass policy set, which includes both direct regulatory measures and market-based instruments.

Policy set: Circularity

Policy Set	Circularity	
	Direct regulation	Market-based instruments
Promote transition	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Quota for use of recycled (and bio-based) material in textiles production and imports ➤ Ecodesign criteria for mandatory durability, reparability and recyclability standards (incl. for imports) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Innovation subsidy for innovative textile reuse or recycling practices and technologies, including support for market penetration of innovative products ➤ "Green VAT" Reduced Value-Added Tax on re-used or recycled textiles
Limit resource use	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Ban on Destruction of Unsold Goods (Existing EU instrument) as part of polluter pays principle to discourage overproduction 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Carbon tax on the use of fossil feedstocks in textiles production

Policy instrument: Quota for use of recycled (and bio-based) material in textiles production and imports

Quotas for recycled and bio-based materials were seen as one of the most effective long-term instruments to achieve absolute reductions in resource use. They provide a clear incentive for investment in recycling technologies, while also stimulating traceability and certification. In addition, they can raise the value of recycled feedstock and support the development of advanced sorting techniques, particularly for textile-to-textile recycling.

At the same time, participants noted that the success of such a policy depends on careful design. Current limitations in scalable technology, lack of ecodesign, and unsustainable consumer behaviour make it difficult to meet ambitious targets. The low quality of many textiles further hampers recycling potential. Concerns were also raised about the risk of creating scarcity in the market for sustainable materials, the need for robust tools to verify compliance, and the likelihood of increased bureaucracy. As highlighted during the discussion, uniform EU guidelines would be essential to ensure consistency across Member States and to provide clarity on product requirements.

Policy instrument: Ecodesign criteria for mandatory durability, repairability, and recyclability standards (incl. for imports)

Mandatory ecodesign criteria were broadly recognised as an important measure to improve product durability and recyclability. Examples such as uniforms and rental textiles already demonstrate that durability can be achieved when there are commercial drivers, and many saw this as a pathway to enable larger-scale textile recycling.

However, a number of challenges were raised. Clear definitions are needed, since durability can be understood in both material and consumer-related terms. Introducing mandatory rules could be costly and bureaucratic, as durability and repairability are difficult to measure and monitor in practice. There was also scepticism about whether technical requirements alone can reduce overall consumption, which many felt should be addressed through complementary instruments. Furthermore, unlike standardised materials such as steel, textiles and garments may be too diverse to regulate effectively through universal technical rules.

To address these issues, participants suggested accompanying measures, such as stricter guidelines on fibre blending to improve recyclability, and better systems for handling textile waste across EU borders. Given the dispersed availability of textile waste, large and well-sorted streams will be needed to support recycling. Finally, some emphasised the importance of extending responsibility to consumers as well as producers.

Policy instrument: Ban on destruction of unsold goods (existing EU instrument) as part of polluter pays principle to discourage overproduction

The ban on the destruction of unsold goods was generally regarded as a useful step in discouraging overproduction and fostering a lower-consumption mentality.

Nevertheless, participants questioned its overall effectiveness. Concerns included the risk of leakage, with unsold textiles being exported outside the EU, and doubts about its ability to reduce the prevalence of synthetic textiles. There was also a risk that recycling systems could become focused on unsold items rather than post-consumer waste, which was seen as a more pressing challenge. Others underlined that the measure may increase administrative burdens for companies in textile supply chains without addressing the root problem of overproduction.

For these reasons, it was suggested that the ban should be complemented by instruments that directly target consumption at its source, ensuring it contributes meaningfully to waste reduction.

Policy instrument: innovation subsidy for innovative textile reuse or recycling practices and technologies, including support for market penetration of innovative products

Innovation subsidies were highlighted as a helpful short-term measure to make circular solutions more competitive. By lowering the initial barriers for novel reuse and recycling practices, such subsidies can accelerate the development and uptake of new technologies, while also supporting the market penetration of innovative textile products. In this sense, the instrument is seen as a practical way to stimulate experimentation and scale promising approaches that may otherwise struggle to compete with conventional production models.

Policy instrument: “Green VAT” reduced value-added tax on reused or recycled textiles

A reduced VAT on reused or recycled textiles was viewed as an important lever for behavioural change, particularly in encouraging consumers to choose circular options over new products. By

shifting purchasing incentives, this measure could increase demand for recycled textiles and reused garments, thereby supporting the expansion of second-hand markets and end-of-life innovations.

It was further noted that such a measure could help attract and retain innovative recycling technologies in the EU. However, scaling these technologies to meet rising demand remains a key challenge, and a Green VAT would likely need to be accompanied by broader structural measures to ensure sufficient supply of recycled textiles.

Policy instrument: Carbon tax on the use of fossil feedstocks in textiles production

A carbon tax on fossil feedstocks was described as a potentially powerful measure, drawing on experience from energy markets where such approaches have proven effective. Implemented through the existing EU Emissions Trading System and complemented by the Carbon Border Adjustment Mechanism (CBAM), this instrument could incentivise best practices while penalising high emitters. Despite expectations of resistance, it was considered effective in driving behavioural change and shifting the sector towards more sustainable feedstocks.

Nonetheless, several weaknesses were identified. There were concerns that textile production might relocate outside the EU, reducing the instrument’s effectiveness. Some argued that responsibility should not rest solely with manufacturers but also with brands, who play a major role in shaping production choices. Others stressed the importance of considering the realities of manufacturers when designing the measure. Finally, participants cautioned that higher consumer prices could result, with disproportionate impacts on low-income groups who may struggle to afford essential textiles.

Policy set: Biomass

Policy Set	Biomass	
	Direct regulation	Market-based instruments
Promote transition	<p>➤ Quota for use of bio-based (and recycled) feedstock in textile production and imports</p> <p>➤ Public procurement of textiles without fossil-based content</p>	<p>➤ Innovation subsidy for developing new technologies and practices for bio-based textiles including support for market penetration of innovative products</p>
Limit resource use	<p>➤ Sustainability criteria for textiles to be eligible to the quota, public procurement (e.g., EU Renewable Material Directive following the EU Renewable Energy Directive)</p>	<p>➤ Environmental tax on "fast fashion" textiles, fibers, yarns and fabrics (e.g., including for non-sustainable cotton products) to limit waste and pollution</p>

Policy instrument: Quota for use of bio-based (and recycled) feedstock in textile production and imports

Quotas for bio-based and recycled feedstock were described as potentially effective in steering the textile sector away from fossil-based materials. Participants noted that such measures should

also explicitly target natural plant- or animal-based fibres to ensure a broader impact across feedstock types. However, controlling compliance within a globalised market would come at very high administrative and monitoring costs. Suggestions were made to design quotas that cover not only bio-based but also recycled and CO₂-based textiles, thereby broadening the policy's scope and fostering innovation across different sustainable feedstock pathways.

Policy instrument: Public procurement of textiles without fossil-based content

Public procurement was seen as a way to create reliable demand for environmentally certified products, giving market signals that favour sustainable textiles. However, concerns were raised that this could create scarcity if sustainable alternatives are not sufficiently available to meet procurement needs. Workshop discussions highlighted the importance of linking procurement measures with efforts to grow the market for recycled and bio-based textiles, so that supply and demand evolve in tandem.

Policy instrument: Sustainability criteria for textiles to be eligible to the quota, public procurement (e.g., EU renewable material directive following the EU renewable energy directive)

Sustainability criteria were highlighted as an opportunity to embed traceability and certification systems, strengthening accountability along the textile value chain. This would ensure that textiles qualifying for quotas or procurement schemes meet clear environmental standards. At the same time, participants stressed the need to distribute the costs of transition fairly across the value chain. For instance, spinners and fabric producers should not bear disproportionate burdens arising from stricter requirements or higher costs. One suggestion was to subsidise fibre recycling using revenues from fees levied on sold products, thereby balancing the responsibilities between different actors.

Policy instrument: Innovation subsidy for developing new technologies and practices for bio-based textiles including support for market penetration of innovative products

Innovation subsidies for bio-based textiles were considered a strong driver to attract new companies to the EU market, spurring technological advancement and the commercialisation of sustainable alternatives. At the same time, participants recognised potential resistance from fossil-based industries and large fashion companies that may feel threatened by these shifts. Concerns were also raised that relying on subsidies alone may not be sufficient in the long term. Rather than making innovators dependent on public support, measures that stimulate market demand for sustainable textiles were seen as a more durable solution.

Policy instrument: Environmental tax on “fast fashion” textiles, fibres, yarns and fabrics (e.g., including for non-sustainable cotton products) to limit waste and pollution

An environmental tax on fast fashion was identified as a way to help more responsible brands secure a greater market share, while discouraging unsustainable practices such as excessive production of low-quality garments. However, defining “fast fashion” in a regulatory context was viewed as a major challenge, with risks of overly broad or ambiguous interpretations. Some participants also warned that consumers could perceive such taxation as an infringement on personal choice, potentially leading to resistance. Alongside fiscal measures, awareness-raising and education about sustainable textiles were recommended, including basic consumer literacy on the environmental impacts of different fibres and production methods.

Additional policy instruments

Additional instruments recommended during the conference are the following:

- Policy 1: Introduce tax on textiles that are more challenging to recycle because of mixed fibre composition
- Policy 2: Obligation to separate textiles
- Policy 3: Right to repair
- Policy 4: Recycling quota - minimum share of textile consumed or wasted to be recycled to fibres
- Policy 5: Take-back system for textile garments in shops
- Policy 6: Tax credits/ low VAT for repair services
- Policy 7: Deposit or refund system for textile products

7.2.2. Chemical sector

This section provides a summary of the key strengths, weaknesses, and additional recommendations identified for the proposed policy instruments targeting the chemical sector, as discussed during the co-creation workshop. The findings are organised into two groups: first, the circularity policy set, followed by the biomass policy set, which includes both direct regulatory measures and market-based instruments.

Policy set: Circularity/ Toxicity

Policy instrument: Innovation subsidy for developing low-risk chemicals and toxic-free products according to the EU Safe and Sustainable by Design (SSbD) framework, including decontamination technologies.

Participants viewed this measure as a valuable tool for encouraging early-stage adoption of innovative technologies, particularly in the middle of the supply chain or among brands. Linking the funding source to a pollution tax was suggested as one way to sustain such support. Providing

public funding to test and assess new innovations was seen as relatively low-risk, since it focuses on generating reliable, publicly available data rather than financing large-scale production.

Several complementary measures were proposed to maximise impact, such as setting a minimum biobased content requirement for new chemicals; streamlining the review process for potential biobased platform chemicals; and targeting innovation funding at safer alternatives to restricted chemicals that also meet a biobased content threshold. Additional ideas included promoting Environmental Preferable Purchasing through multi-attribute certifications (e.g., cradle-to-cradle) aligned with sustainable chemistry goals, establishing restricted substances lists (RSLs) or safer chemistry criteria, and creating a comprehensive database of safer chemical ingredients with biobased content information and manufacturer details.

Policy instrument: **Thresholds for key Substances of Concern** in products that inhibit reuse and recycling, complemented by **Extended REACH criteria** to consider end-of-life recycling, and an **expanded EU SCIP database** to include substances inhibiting circularity.

While the proposal to set thresholds for substances that limit circularity was generally well-received, participants cautioned against relying solely on static lists of substances of concern. Such lists can quickly become outdated, and even newer alternative chemistries may still impede reuse or recycling. To address this, it was suggested to complement list-based approaches with criteria based on chemical properties or hazard characteristics, drawing from multiple authoritative sources. A dynamic update process would be necessary, alongside a defined phase-out period for substances newly added to relevant lists to give industry time to adapt.

Policy instrument: **Pollution tax on Key Substances of Concern** that pose significant health or environmental risks and inhibit circularity (e.g., lead, flame retardants, PFAS)

This measure was recognised as a potentially strong driver for reducing the use of highly problematic substances, but participants noted significant challenges in tracking circularity and toxicity reductions across complex, global supply chains. Monitoring compliance could be resource-intensive and costly, raising questions about feasibility. Clarification would also be needed on the tax's scope—specifically, whether it would apply equally to imported chemicals and products manufactured outside the EU. Reference was made to the Washington State MTCA (Model Toxics Control Act) as an example worth examining.

Policy set: Biomass

Policy instrument: Quota for non-fossil feedstock shares in chemical production, with a complete phase-out of fossil feedstocks by 2050

Quotas are seen as a potentially powerful instrument, especially if introduced gradually, starting, for example, with a 5-10% biobased share and integrated into legislation already under development, such as the ELVR(End-of-life Vehicle Regulation), PPWR (Packaging and Packaging Waste Regulation), and ESPR (Ecodesign for Sustainable Products Regulation). Given the urgency of the EU’s competitiveness challenges, quotas could accelerate the shift away from fossil feedstocks. However, implementation would be complex, particularly for SMEs, due to the need to manage separate targets for recycled, biobased, and captured carbon. A key condition for success would be ensuring that viable, industrially mature biobased alternatives are available before quotas take effect.

Policy instrument: Innovation subsidy for the development and market penetration of non-fossil chemicals or product subsidy for non-fossil chemicals (e.g., green VAT, reduced tax rates)

Product subsidies, such as Spain’s fossil plastic tax, were cited as effective tools for incentivising alternative feedstocks and driving companies to reduce overall packaging use. Coupling such measures with high product quality standards could extend product lifetimes, thereby lowering demand for new goods. However, innovation subsidies alone may not deliver market uptake if there is no viable operational business case; operational expenditure (OPEX) subsidies would also be needed. More broadly, both innovation and product subsidies face the limitation that they are not sustainable long-term solutions—industry must ultimately remain profitable without ongoing public support.

Policy instrument: Sustainability criteria for biomass eligible under the quota (e.g., an EU Renewable Materials Directive modelled on the Renewable Energy Directive)

Well-designed sustainability criteria could optimise the use of existing biomass, reduce land-use-change-related emissions, and make ambitious targets feasible—nova-Institute estimates that a fourfold increase in biomass use for chemicals (from 5.5% in 2023 to 20% in the EU27) is possible. However, biomass scarcity and high inter-sectoral competition remain major concerns, and global availability is unlikely to meet the combined demands of energy, chemicals, and other sectors. Annex IX of the RED was seen as overly prescriptive, with a preference for feedstock-agnostic criteria. Participants noted that creating cascaded value chains could help address biomass availability, while the Green Claims Directive will be key to ensuring transparency in ecolabels and claims. Using biomass waste from other sectors was highlighted as a win-win approach, reducing waste, promoting circularity, and lowering demand for virgin biomass.

Policy instrument: Carbon tax on fossil feedstocks and low-value biomass uses for chemical production

A carbon tax was viewed as a straightforward way to raise the price of fossil-based products, encouraging consumers to switch to sustainable alternatives. While no major weaknesses were identified, participants stressed that the Carbon Border Adjustment Mechanism (CBAM) for the chemical industry will be essential to maintain an international level playing field and prevent carbon leakage.

Additional policy instruments

Additional instruments recommended during the conference are the following:

- Policy 1: Ban for incineration of recyclable waste
- Policy 2: Product passport with information on hazardous substances
- Policy 3: Loan guarantees for developing innovative low-toxicity chemicals

A ban on incinerating recyclable waste would preserve valuable materials for reuse and recycling, provided that sufficient infrastructure and sorting systems are in place. Introducing a product passport containing hazardous substance information could improve supply chain communication, making it easier to manage chemical safety and enable higher rates of safe material recovery. Loan guarantees could help companies pilot or scale production processes that use safer chemistries with a minimum biobased content, while also covering transition costs from existing formulations. Complementary measures to make green products more competitive—such as lowering administrative burdens, reducing energy costs through renewable investments, and commoditising secondary resources—were also highlighted. The focus on transparency, infrastructure, and cost competitiveness aligns with earlier workshop discussions, suggesting that policy effectiveness will depend on combining these tools into a coordinated package rather than implementing them in isolation.

7.2.3. Plastics sector

This section provides a summary of the key strengths, weaknesses, and additional recommendations identified for the proposed policy instruments targeting the plastics sector, as discussed during the co-creation workshop. The findings are organised into two groups: first, the circularity policy set, followed by the biomass policy set, which includes both direct regulatory measures and market-based instruments.

Policy set: Circularity

Policy Set	Circularity	
	Direct regulation	Market-based instruments
Promote transition	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Quota for the <u>use of recycled material</u> for producers of non-packaging plastics (e.g., major waste sources such as cars, electrical devices etc.) ➤ Ecodesign criteria for <u>non-packaging plastic products</u> to improve ease of repair, recycling etc. ➤ Public procurement 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Innovation subsidy for <u>new technologies, practices and products</u> connected to the re-use, repair or recycling (etc.) of non-packaging plastics
Limit resource use	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Product bans of additional single-use and short-life <u>plastic products or product parts</u> where sustainable and low-cost alternatives incl. reuse and repair are available 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Carbon price for <u>use of fossil feedstocks</u> as production input, to be paid by producers of non-packaging plastics

Policy instruments: Quota for the use of recycled material in non-packaging plastics (e.g. cars, electrical devices, etc.) and Ecodesign criteria for non-packaging plastic products (improving ease of repair, recycling, etc.)

Quotas for the use of recycled material in non-packaging plastics, such as those applied in cars and electrical devices, can play an important role in creating market demand for secondary raw materials. By targeting major waste streams beyond packaging, such quotas have the potential to reduce reliance on virgin plastics while stimulating innovation in sorting, processing, and quality assurance. In doing so, they can help strengthen collection systems and improve the efficiency of recycling infrastructures. However, implementation remains difficult in the absence of harmonised definitions and norms across the EU. Without a common understanding of what qualifies as “recycled content” and how it should be measured, there is a risk of fragmentation, uneven enforcement, and limited effectiveness. Industries may also struggle to comply in cases where high-quality recycled plastics are not available at sufficient scale, creating additional uncertainty. To address these concerns, one option would be to develop clear criteria first and then identify certifications or methodologies that can meet—or even exceed—these requirements. Such an approach would support accountability while also providing flexibility by highlighting equivalencies rather than relying solely on strict harmonisation.

Ecodesign criteria for non-packaging plastic products can serve as another important driver of circularity, embedding principles of reparability, recyclability, and reuse directly into product development. By encouraging producers to consider the full lifecycle of their products, ecodesign criteria stimulate innovation in design and materials, while also aligning closely with broader EU circular economy objectives. This approach has the potential to deliver systemic change, yet the process of developing criteria is lengthy and complex. While they will eventually provide strong incentives, the impact may not be fully felt until the next decade. Another key weakness is the lack of harmonisation of definitions and norms, which again risks regulatory fragmentation if not addressed early in the process.

Policy instruments: Public procurement and Innovation subsidy for new technologies, practices and products connected to the re-use, repair or recycling etc. of non-packaging plastics

Public procurement can serve as a valuable policy tool by creating demand for sustainable plastic products and applications, particularly in non-packaging sectors. By leveraging the purchasing power of public authorities, procurement policies can help signal market demand and provide a stable outlet for circular products. This is considered a good measure to keep the European plastics industry and start-ups competitive, supporting their transition towards more sustainable practices.

Similarly, innovation subsidies aimed at new technologies, practices, and products connected to the reuse, repair, or recycling of non-packaging plastics play a critical role in fostering competitiveness. By reducing financial risks for innovators and early adopters, such subsidies can accelerate the development and scaling of solutions that contribute to circularity. Like public procurement, they were seen in the co-creation workshop as an effective way to keep industry and start-ups competitive in an increasingly global market.

Policy instrument: Product bans of additional single-use and short-life plastic products or product parts where sustainable and low-cost alternatives incl. reuse and repair are available

Product bans targeting additional single-use and short-life plastic products, or product parts where sustainable and low-cost alternatives—including reuse and repair options—are available, can be an effective measure to reduce plastic consumption and promote circularity. When combined with dedicated budgets for education to support behavioural change, such bans become even more feasible, particularly for products that are already in decline. This approach was identified as a practical strength during the co-creation workshop, as it can directly influence consumption patterns while encouraging the adoption of sustainable alternatives.

However, several challenges must be considered. It is essential to ensure that viable alternatives truly exist, since plastics are often used for properties that other materials cannot easily replicate. Additionally, the measure could face international trade complications under World Trade Organisation (WTO) rules, potentially triggering retaliation from non-EU countries. Consumer acceptance is another critical factor, as bans may be met with resistance if perceived as restrictive or inconvenient. Careful design, clear communication, and complementary support measures will therefore be necessary to maximise effectiveness and minimise unintended consequences.

Policy instrument: Carbon price for use of fossil feedstocks as production input, to be paid by producers of non-packaging plastics

Introducing a carbon price for the use of fossil feedstocks in the production of non-packaging plastics aims to incentivise a shift towards lower-carbon and more circular alternatives. By internalising the environmental costs of fossil-based materials, this policy could, in theory, encourage producers to adopt sustainable feedstocks and support the transition to a circular plastics economy.

However, a key challenge arises when applying the carbon price to single-use bioplastics. These materials are already less competitive than fossil-based alternatives, and adding a carbon cost could inadvertently increase their price, effectively reinforcing the market dominance of fossil-based plastics rather than encouraging substitution. This creates a situation where the policy could unintentionally establish an additional challenge for bio-based materials, counteracting the intended goal of promoting more sustainable inputs.

To improve the policy's effectiveness, complementary educational measures are recommended. Raising awareness about the environmental impacts of non-essential single-use plastics, alongside broader education on plastic production processes and circularity principles, could help create a shared understanding of how plastics relate to environmental sustainability. Developing this

common knowledge base is crucial for enabling informed decision-making by both producers and consumers, and for supporting the broader objectives of circularity in the plastics sector.

Policy set: Biomass

Policy Set	Biomass	
	Direct regulation	Market-based instruments
Promote transition	<p>► Product subsidy paid to producers of durable <u>non-packaging plastic</u> final or intermediate products made from biomass meeting sustainability criteria (↓)</p>	<p>► Innovation subsidy for <u>new bioplastic technologies</u> and for innovative durable bioplastic <u>products</u> to support their market penetration</p>
Limit resource use	<p>► Sustainability criteria for receiving the product <u>subsidy</u>. E.g., mandatory greenhouse gas reductions, exclusion of biomass from areas with high carbon or biodiversity value, restriction to durable products etc.</p> <p>► Additional: Cap for share or total quantity of biomass used in the sector</p>	<p>► Carbon tax on <u>emissions from low-value biomass uses</u>, e.g. from bioenergy and single-use / non-durable bioplastics products</p>

Policy instrument: Product subsidy paid to producers of durable non-packaging plastic final or intermediate products made from biomass meeting sustainability criteria

Offering a product subsidy for durable bio-based non-packaging plastics aims to incentivise the production of sustainable materials and accelerate the adoption of bio-based alternatives in the plastics sector. By rewarding producers who meet sustainability criteria, this policy seeks to encourage investment in environmentally preferable materials and support the transition toward a bio-based economy.

However, a notable challenge identified by the conference attendees lies in the additional bureaucracy required to provide evidence for eligibility. Producers must navigate complex documentation and verification processes, which adds cost and administrative burden. Coupled with the existing uncertainty stemming from incoherent policy frameworks, this creates an environment where the intended benefits of the subsidy may be partially offset by procedural hurdles. Effective implementation will require streamlining requirements and ensuring alignment with broader policy frameworks to reduce unnecessary complexity and support biopolymer producers.

Policy instrument: Innovation subsidy for new bioplastic products and for innovative durable bioplastic products to support market penetration

Innovation subsidies targeting bioplastics are intended to stimulate research and development, enabling new technologies and products to reach the market. By supporting durable bioplastics, the policy seeks to foster technological advancements and encourage scaling-up of sustainable materials.

A key limitation discussed during the workshop is that focusing exclusively on durable products neglects the single-use plastics sector, which is responsible for a large share of waste and

microplastic pollution. Excluding producers of single-use biodegradable alternatives may hinder innovation where it is most needed and could slow the transition to a fully bio-based and circular plastics economy. To address this, subsidies could be expanded to support technologies such as second-generation waste processing or smaller-scale innovations, for example PHA production from methane in farms or wastewater treatment plants. This would enable a broader range of producers to contribute to sustainable solutions while supporting market penetration of bioplastic technologies.

Policy instrument: Sustainability criteria for receiving the product subsidy, e.g. mandatory greenhouse gas reductions, exclusion of biomass from areas of high carbon or biodiversity value, restriction to durable products, etc.

Sustainability criteria underpinning the product subsidy aim to ensure that bio-based plastics are produced in a manner that genuinely reduces environmental impacts. Mandatory greenhouse gas reductions, exclusion of biomass from high-carbon or biodiversity-value areas, and a focus on durable products are designed to guide producers toward responsible practices.

However, the effectiveness of these criteria depends on a coherent policy environment for biopolymers, which currently does not exist. Without supportive frameworks, developing these criteria risks becoming a theoretical exercise that adds complexity and uncertainty. Furthermore, restricting support to durable products overlooks highly resource-efficient packaging solutions, which are often lightweight, flexible, and more challenging to recycle mechanically, yet provide significant benefits when replacing fossil-based feedstocks early in the supply chain.

Comments for improvement include aligning sustainability criteria with cascading principles, capping energy use rather than material use unless there is evidence of exceeding planetary boundaries. This approach would better balance environmental outcomes while retaining flexibility for different material applications.

Policy instruments: Additional cap for share or total quantity of biomass used in the sector and Carbon tax on emissions from low-value biomass uses, e.g., from bioenergy and single-use/ non-durable bioplastic products

Setting a cap on the share or total quantity of biomass used in the sector, alongside a carbon tax on emissions from low-value biomass uses such as bioenergy or single-use non-durable bioplastics, is designed to encourage more efficient and responsible use of bio-resources. These mechanisms aim to prioritise high-value applications, limit environmental impacts, and recognise the benefits of biogenic carbon relative to fossil carbon.

The main strength of these instruments lies in their potential to support sustainable practices and guide the sector toward higher-value uses of biomass. Nonetheless, a challenge is that upstream supply chain issues may not be fully addressed, such as shortages of essential bio-based raw materials. For maximum effectiveness, these measures must be integrated with broader strategies that consider the availability and sustainable sourcing of biomass, ensuring that the incentives drive meaningful improvements without unintended constraints on innovation or material access.

Additional policy instruments

Further policy approaches and opportunities were also discussed during the workshop and integrated into the analysis.

Policy instrument: Microplastic restriction - ban on intentionally added microplastics in products (e.g., cosmetics, toothpaste, etc.)

The microplastic restriction seeks to prevent the deliberate introduction of microplastics into consumer products, thereby reducing environmental pollution and mitigating risks associated with microplastics in ecosystems. This policy targets a clear source of microplastic contamination and aligns with broader objectives to limit persistent plastic pollution.

A key limitation is that the policy does not currently distinguish between biodegradable and non-biodegradable microplastics. Treating all microplastics equally could overlook materials that degrade safely and sustainably, potentially constraining innovation in biodegradable alternatives. Additionally, there are questions about whether current regulations sufficiently address additives in plastics that may impact end-of-life outcomes, especially in relation to chemical properties. Integrating considerations of biodegradability and chemical characteristics into the regulation could make it more effective while encouraging development of environmentally safer materials.

Policy instrument: Tax on packaging producers for each ton of non-recycled plastic packaging sold

A tax on non-recycled plastic packaging aims to incentivise producers to reduce waste and increase recycling rates. By assigning a financial cost to non-recycled packaging, the policy encourages more sustainable material use and can help shift the market toward circular solutions.

However, a key challenge discussed during the workshop is the availability of alternatives. If viable substitutes are limited, the cost is likely to be passed on to consumers, potentially driving inflation rather than meaningful environmental change. Clear planning is also needed regarding the allocation of tax revenue. Defining how the funds will be used—for instance, supporting market-based instruments or investment in recycling infrastructure—could strengthen the policy’s impact, ensure transparency, and create a feedback loop that directly supports the transition to a more circular plastics economy.

The following two instruments were also presented during the workshop, but not commented on by attending stakeholders:

- Stop advertising fossil-based plastic products, as it is for cigarettes
- Promote the development of recycling infrastructure for bio-based materials and provide the necessary funding

7.2.4. Construction sector

This section provides a summary of the key strengths, weaknesses, and additional recommendations identified for the proposed policy instruments targeting the construction sector, as discussed during the co-creation workshop. The findings are organised into two groups: first, the circularity policy set, followed by the biomass policy set, which includes both direct regulatory measures and market-based instruments.

Policy set: Circularity

Policy instrument: Ecodesign criteria for building companies on design, construction and use of materials. Aim should be to design for reuse, disassembly, physical durability, adaptability, repair and minimising material intensity.

An Ecodesign Criteria helps underscoring the importance of adopting holistic approaches that extend beyond basic assessments of material circularity. It promotes the integration of full lifecycle thinking into product development, encouraging the construction and manufacturing industries to consider sustainability impacts at every stage from raw material extraction to end-of-life. By supporting comprehensive circularity concepts that include materials, logistics, and collection infrastructure, the policy aims to create more robust and sustainable systems.

However, one of the key weaknesses lies in the limited availability of digital and green skills across the workforce. This skills gap poses a significant challenge to the effective implementation of ecodesign principles, particularly in sectors like construction where small businesses may lack the resources to adopt innovative practices. The disconnect between technological innovation and day-to-day operations further complicates the transition, slowing progress toward more sustainable industry standards.

To strengthen the policy, greater attention must be given to recyclability and the conversion of waste into final products. Emphasising the end-of-life phase of building materials is essential to closing the loop and achieving true circularity. This may require additional product requirements that address aspects such as reusability, disassembly, and material recovery. Addressing these issues holistically will be vital to bridging the gap between sustainability goals and real-world application.

Policy instrument: Innovation subsidy for innovation circular technologies or practices (e.g., use of recycled materials)

An innovation subsidy could play a crucial role in accelerating sustainable practices in the construction sector by promoting real-world demonstrations, particularly in renovation projects.

Subsidised demo-sites can also serve as educational platforms for both professionals and the general public, helping to build awareness and acceptance of innovative building practices. A key strength of this instrument lies in its targeted support for smaller construction companies, which make up 94% of the industry. By offering subsidies, the policy helps equip these micro-enterprises with the tools and resources needed to improve their digital and green skills, which are critical components for the transition to more sustainable construction methods.

Despite its strengths, potential shortcomings in effectively reaching smaller construction companies could remain. Many SMEs may be unaware of available subsidies or lack the administrative capacity to apply for them. Ensuring that these funds are accessible and inclusive is essential, as SMEs play a vital role in renovation and the broader shift toward sustainability in the built environment. Tailored outreach and simplified application processes may be necessary to ensure equitable participation and maximise the impact of the innovation subsidy.

Additional measures could enhance the impact of this policy. For instance, aligning future revisions of standards such as ISO 59040 with circularity goals would strengthen the regulatory framework. Investments should also support the development of infrastructure and innovations that address the end-of-life phase of bio-based materials, ensuring they can be efficiently reused, recycled, or biodegraded. Finally, promoting reparability and design for disassembly to both consumers and businesses would reinforce circular design principles and encourage long-term thinking in construction practices.

Policy instrument: **Material Tax** on the use of virgin raw materials for construction (e.g., gravel, stone, sand) including imports.

A material tax aimed at reducing the use of virgin raw materials could have unintended consequences if not carefully designed. One major concern is that such a tax might raise the cost of wood-based products, even though wood is a fully recyclable and renewable resource. If the tax does not distinguish between sustainably and unsustainably sourced materials, it could penalise industries that rely on responsibly harvested biomass, such as the wood-based panel sector. Without clear differentiation in the policy framework, wood products could be placed at a disadvantage compared to more carbon-intensive materials like steel or concrete. To prevent this, the material tax should be designed to reflect the environmental impact of materials across their entire lifecycle. Incorporating sustainability criteria such as origin, renewability, and recyclability into the tax structure would help promote genuinely low-impact materials and support a more sustainable and circular construction sector.

Policy set: Biomass

Policy instrument: Quota/target for use of biobased materials in new buildings including higher targets for public procurement.

A quota or target-based policy can be a powerful tool to promote the use of local and bio-based materials, helping to strengthen the regional bio-economy while advancing sustainability goals. By prioritising bio-based solutions, particularly in public and social housing projects, governments can lead by example and set new industry standards. This approach not only stimulates local supply chains but also accelerates the adoption of environmentally friendly building practices across the sector.

However, certain regulatory and technical barriers may limit the effective implementation of such quotas. Fire safety regulations, for instance, are often grounded in traditional construction methods and do not reflect the distinct fire behaviour of bio-based materials. As a result, bio-based materials are frequently restricted in application, even when advancements in engineered wood and fire treatments could ensure safety compliance. Similarly, acoustic norms are primarily tailored to conventional materials, failing to account for the unique properties of bio-based solutions and thus constraining their broader use. The way biogenic carbon is handled in LCAs presents another challenge. Often, the carbon sequestration benefits of bio-based materials are cancelled out or overlooked, which misrepresents their full environmental value. Accurately accounting for biogenic carbon would improve the credibility of LCAs and better reflect the long-term climate benefits of using bio-based construction materials.

To support this policy direction, complementary measures should be considered. Making fossil-based materials less economically viable through targeted taxation or regulation would help level the playing field. Establishing specific standards for bio-based materials would increase their acceptance and application, while subsidies or economic incentives for green producers could drive innovation, reduce costs, and facilitate the transition toward more sustainable building practices.

Policy instrument: Innovation subsidy for development and uses of innovative bio-based construction materials.

An innovation subsidy policy can serve as a catalyst for the broader adoption of bio-based solutions by supporting both technological development and public awareness. One of its key strengths lies in promoting the health and performance benefits of bio-based materials. These benefits go beyond sustainability alone and include improved indoor air quality, enhanced thermal insulation, and strong material durability. Emphasising these functional advantages can help shift perceptions and increase market demand, particularly among consumers and builders who prioritise comfort and performance as well as environmental responsibility.

Policy instrument: Sustainability criteria for biomass to be eligible to the quota (e.g., EU Renewable Material Directive following the EU Renewable Energy Directive)

There remains a reluctance to use recycled, reused, and bio-based materials in construction due to concerns about quality, safety, and performance. Despite the availability of innovative solutions, demand remains limited and adoption slow, underscoring the need for stronger incentives, increased awareness, and more robust regulatory frameworks to build confidence and encourage uptake across the sector.

Additionally, subsidies for bioenergy should be carefully reduced to avoid distorting the market. Prioritising bio-based materials for short-term energy production undermines their potential for long-lasting, high-value applications in construction. To maximise resource efficiency, bio-based materials should be directed toward durable uses that store carbon over time.

Ensuring proper implementation of the cascading principle across Member States is essential to achieving this goal. This principle prioritises the most valuable and sustainable use of biomass, helping to align material use with environmental and economic objectives. Promoting renewable materials across the entire life cycle of buildings from design to end-of-life can support a more dynamic and sustainable built environment.

Policy instrument: Subsidy for refurbishment of buildings.

One major challenge is the lack of mandatory requirements for incorporating sustainable materials in both new construction and renovation projects. Without such obligations, builders and developers have little incentive to move away from conventional, often less sustainable materials. This gap hinders the broader adoption of environmentally friendly alternatives and slows progress toward climate and circular economy goals. Introducing targeted subsidies can help address this issue by making sustainable materials more financially attractive and competitive. Subsidies could lower upfront costs, support market entry for innovative products, and reduce the risk for early adopters.

Policy instrument: Carbon tax on all lifecycle GHG emissions of building materials that are not part of current carbon pricing (EU-ETS I & II) including the carbon content of short-life biomass materials.

The rising demand for biomass driven by BECCS (Bioenergy with Carbon Capture and Storage) poses a risk of resource overexploitation. It is essential to ensure strict adherence to sustainability criteria and the cascading principle to maximise efficiency and minimise environmental impact.

Policy instrument: Carbon credits/subsidy, bio-based building materials that ensure long-term storage of carbon (e.g., 50+ years) are exempt from the carbon tax and receive a credit/subsidy.

Requiring proof of carbon storage in buildings for over 50 years presents significant challenges in terms of tracking and documentation. Monitoring building lifecycles for such an extended period could lead to complex and burdensome administrative processes. To ensure the effectiveness of carbon credit systems while avoiding excessive bureaucracy, a balanced and practical approach is necessary that supports long-term carbon storage goals while maintaining feasibility for stakeholders across the construction and materials sectors.

Additional policy instruments

Additional instruments recommended during the conference are the following:

- Policy 1: GHG emissions limits per square meter for construction
- Policy 2: Reward building projects with lower environmental impacts (e.g. taxes/VAT, government procurement)
- Policy 3: Requirements for cascading use of raw materials and recyclability

Mandatory green requirements in public procurement and publicly funded construction projects would play a crucial role in accelerating the adoption of sustainable materials and practices. By embedding environmental criteria into procurement processes, governments can set a strong example for the broader construction industry, creating demand for eco-friendly solutions and signalling a clear policy direction. To further support this transition, greater incentives are needed within the building sector to encourage the integration of bio-based solutions. Leveraging public procurement as a market driver can significantly expand the market share of bio-based materials, promote innovation, and deepen industry knowledge. This approach not only helps normalise the use of sustainable materials but also contributes to shifting mindsets toward environmentally responsible construction practices.

7.3. Closing Event

The closing event of the “From Vision to Implementation: Shaping Policies to Boost Circular Bio-Based Transition” series represented a key milestone in translating co-created visions into actionable policy options for the four SUSTRACK case study sectors: textiles, construction, plastics, and chemicals. The event convened a diverse group of stakeholders, including policymakers, industry representatives, researchers, and civil society actors, to validate and refine policy options capable of accelerating the transition toward a circular bio-based economy.

The event built on the outputs of the IMPLEMENT workshops, where participants engaged in detailed discussions on the transition challenge, the evolving policy landscape, and sectoral visions for transformation. Policy options identified by SUSTRACK were critically assessed, with stakeholders collaboratively exploring their strengths, weaknesses, and potential refinements. This interactive format ensured that the evaluation of proposed measures was informed by practical insights from both policy and industry perspectives.

In addition to consolidating workshop results, the closing event provided an overview of the methods and tools developed by SUSTRACK to monitor and support the transition. These included resources designed to help stakeholders track progress, evaluate interventions, and identify further opportunities for policy innovation. Furthermore, the event presented the key findings from eleven in-depth case studies conducted across the four sectors, offering evidence-based insights into sectoral dynamics, challenges, and opportunities.

The objectives of the closing event were threefold: first, to synthesise the main takeaways from the workshop series into a coherent set of findings; second, to present monitoring methodologies and tools that can be directly utilised by stakeholders; and third, to deliver actionable knowledge in the form of policy options capable of advancing the transition at both European and national levels.

7.4. Main Takeaways

The IMPLEMENT Conference followed the successful format introduced during the DESIGN phase, consisting of targeted workshops and a closing event. By building on this approach, the consortium was able to apply the lessons learned and further refine the organisation and facilitation of stakeholder engagement activities. As a result, the IMPLEMENT phase benefitted from a smoother process, more confident moderation, and stronger outputs.

With the entire consortium now experienced in executing such a series of events, the workshops were more efficiently run and the facilitation more consistent across sessions. The closing event successfully synthesised inputs into a coherent overview of actionable policy options, supported by evidence from the SUSTRACK case studies.

The format again proved effective in balancing inclusiveness and technical depth. Broader audiences were engaged through plenary presentations, while expert-driven sessions ensured targeted input on specific challenges and opportunities. The interactive tools were used with greater confidence and clarity than in previous phases, enabling more meaningful participation and feedback.

8. SURVEY

As described in step 6 of the methodology (Chapter 2), the survey aimed to rank identified policy instruments for the transition towards a CBBE in the four analysed sectors. Since creating a CBBE is a complex policy challenge, the survey was narrowed down to two policy approaches (i) Approach A: Boosting Circularity and (ii) Approach B: Ensuring Sustainability of Biomass Use. Each policy approach included several policy instruments and represented a different type of policy intervention: direct regulation versus market-based policies. Respondents first rated each instrument individually on a scale from “fully recommend” to “not recommend at all,” and then selected the overall approach they would recommend to support and accelerate the transition in the four targeted sectors.

8.1. Survey Results

This section summarises the results of the survey. The first part investigates the generalities of the respondents. To follow, the prioritisations of the policy approaches for each sector are presented.

8.1.1. Generalities of the survey participants

The survey gathered insights from a diverse group of 31 stakeholders representing various sectors and organisational backgrounds. The majority of respondents (61%) came from the business and industry sector, indicating strong engagement from business entities. This was followed by participants from research and academia (26%), with smaller representation from NGOs and other categories.

Geographically, the participants were spread across 13 European countries, with the highest representation from Belgium (6 respondents), followed by Greece (4), and Germany, France, and the Netherlands (three each). This broad geographic distribution ensured that the survey captured a wide range of regional perspectives and practices within the EU.

Regarding sectoral interest, the textiles sector attracted the most attention, with over half of the respondents (16) expressing a desire to participate in this area. The construction sector followed with six participants, while plastics and chemicals had five and four participants, respectively.

8.1.2. Textile sector

Sustainability challenges in the textile sector

The textile industry accounts for a significant share of consumption in the EU, projected to reach 102 million tonnes by 2030. However, it faces major sustainability challenges, including declining product quality and lifespan due to fast fashion, increased reliance on fossil-based fibres, high environmental impacts, and low rates of reuse, repair, and fibre-to-fibre recycling.

Current policy frameworks do not sufficiently support the uptake of bio-based and recycled textiles, particularly for man-made cellulosic fibres (MMCFs) and wool-based materials. While existing policies emphasise synthetic fibre recycling, a large portion of the market remains dependent on fossil-based textiles and low-cost imports, which limits incentives for sustainable alternatives. Research indicates that increasing textile recycling alone may not reduce environmental impacts, as energy-intensive and chemically intensive processes can offset potential benefits. Similarly, substituting fossil-based textiles with bio-based alternatives like MMCFs, without proper safeguards, risks contributing to deforestation and biodiversity loss.

To address these issues, both regulatory frameworks and market-based incentives are needed through a combination of measures that: (i) promote sustainable textile innovations such as MMCFs and recycled fibres, and (ii) simultaneously regulate and reduce overall textile consumption in the EU to limit resource exploitation.

List of policy instruments for the textile sector

Figure 8 below presents the distribution of stakeholder preferences regarding the ten proposed policy instruments aimed at supporting the transition to a circular, bio-based economy in the textile sector. Each instrument was evaluated on a five-point scale ranging from “fully recommend” to “would not recommend at all”.

Figure 8: Stakeholder Recommendations on Policy Instruments for the Textile Sector

The figure presents the distribution of 16 stakeholders’ preferences regarding ten proposed policy instruments aimed at supporting the transition to a CBBE in the textile sector.

The results show strong support for instruments that promote innovation and sustainability. Notably, the innovation subsidy for innovative textile reuse or recycling practices and technologies, and the ban on the destruction of unsold goods, received a high proportion of “fully recommend” responses, indicating broad consensus on their potential impact. Similarly, ecodesign criteria and green VAT were positively received, reflecting stakeholder interest in incentivising durability and reuse.

In contrast, instruments such as the carbon tax on fossil feedstocks and environmental tax on fast fashion received a more mixed response, suggesting concerns about feasibility or economic impact. The quota for recycled and bio-based materials and public procurement without fossil-based content also received varied feedback, highlighting the need for further dialogue on implementation mechanisms.

Overall, the figure illustrates a clear preference for policy instruments that combine environmental ambition with practical incentives, while more restrictive or cost-intensive measures appear to require additional justification or refinement.

Policy approaches

Subsequently, stakeholders were asked to choose between the two overarching policy approaches to support the transition toward a CBBE in the textile sector:

- Approach A: Boosting Circularity
- Approach B: Ensuring Sustainability of Biomass Use (illustrated in Figure 9)

Which of these approaches would you prefer to boost the transition toward a circular and bio-based economy in the textiles sector?

Approach A: Boosting circularity			Approach B: Biomass use		
	Direct regulation	Market-based instruments		Direct regulation	Market-based instruments
Promote transition	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Quota for use of recycled (and bio-based) material in textiles production and imports > Ecodesign criteria for mandatory durability, reparability and recyclability standards (incl. for imports) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Innovation subsidy for innovative textile reuse or recycling practices and technologies, including support for market penetration of innovative products > “Green VAT” Reduced Value-Added Tax on re-used or recycled textiles 	Promote transition	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Quota for use of bio-based (and recycled) feedstock in textile production and imports > Public procurement of textiles without fossil-based content 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Innovation subsidy for developing new technologies and practices for bio-based textiles including support for market penetration of innovative products
Limit resource use	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Ban on Destruction of Unsold Goods (Existing EU instrument) as part of polluter pays principle to discourage overproduction 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Carbon tax on the use of fossil feedstocks in textiles production 	Limit resource use	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Sustainability criteria for textiles to be eligible to the quota, public procurement (e.g., EU Renewable Material Directive following the EU Renewable Energy Directive) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Environmental tax on “fast fashion” textiles, fibers, yarns and fabrics (e.g., including for non-sustainable cotton products) to limit waste and pollution

Figure 9: Overview of Approach A and Approach B for the Textile Sector

Out of 16 respondents, 15 expressed a clear preference for Approach A, indicating strong support for measures that enhance circularity, such as reuse, recycling, and design for durability. Only one respondent selected Approach B, which focuses on ensuring the sustainable use of biomass resources.

This result highlights a broad consensus among stakeholders in the textile sector that circularity-oriented policies are currently seen as more effective and actionable in driving the transition toward a circular and bio-based economy. It also suggests that, while biomass sustainability remains important, stakeholders prioritise interventions that directly reduce resource consumption and waste generation.

8.1.3. Chemical sector

Sustainability challenges in the chemical sector

The chemical industry remains heavily reliant on fossil resources, contributing significantly to global carbon emissions—potentially accounting for 24-38% of the 2020-2050 carbon budget for a 1.5°C pathway. While the EU’s Chemicals Strategy for Sustainability promotes the shift to safe and sustainable-by-design chemicals, several challenges persist.

A key issue is the cost-competitiveness of bio-based chemicals compared to fossil-based alternatives. Existing policies focus on decarbonisation, but for a carbon-dependent sector like chemicals, defossilisation is the more appropriate goal. Moreover, regulatory support for bio-based products lags behind that for bioenergy, skewing incentives toward energy use rather than chemical applications. To enable a sustainable transition, policies should introduce premiums and mandates for bio-based chemicals and penalise virgin fossil inputs, such as through carbon taxes. However, circularity measures must be carefully designed to avoid the accumulation of hazardous substances.

Effective policy approaches should combine transformative measures—such as low-risk chemical development and responsible biomass use—with strategies to limit overall material consumption, ensuring environmental gains are not offset by increased demand.

List of policy instruments for the chemical sector

Figure 10 below presents the distribution of stakeholder preferences regarding the nine proposed policy instruments aimed at supporting the transition to a circular, bio-based economy in the chemical sector. Each instrument was evaluated on a five-point scale ranging from “fully recommend” to “would not recommend at all.” The full list of policy instruments suggested for the chemical sector is included in Annex III.

Figure 10: Stakeholder Recommendations on Policy Instruments for the Chemical Sector

The figure presents stakeholder evaluations of various policy instruments aimed at reducing fossil feedstock use and promoting sustainability in the chemical sector. The results reveal a clear preference for incentive-based and innovation-driven measures. Policies such as innovation subsidies—both general and those specifically targeting circularity—received the highest levels of support, with a majority of responses falling under the “fully recommend” and “partially recommend” categories. This indicates strong stakeholder confidence in the role of technological advancement and circular economy strategies in achieving sustainability goals.

Similarly, extended sustainability criteria and monitoring, as well as sustainability criteria and caps, were positively received. These instruments are likely valued for their ability to ensure transparency, accountability, and alignment with environmental standards such as GHG reductions and sustainable biomass sourcing.

In contrast, more restrictive or prescriptive measures, such as quotas for bio-based feedstock shares and final phase-outs of fossil feedstocks, received more mixed responses. This suggests concerns among others about feasibility, higher/ additional costs for stakeholders, market readiness, or potential unintended consequences.

Carbon taxes and product subsidies also showed a spread of opinions, reflecting ongoing debates about the economic implications and effectiveness of market-based instruments in driving behavioural change.

Overall, the results highlight a stakeholder preference for flexible, supportive policies that enable innovation and gradual transition, while more rigid or cost-intensive measures appear to require further refinement and consensus-building to gain broader acceptance.

Policy Approach Options

Subsequently, stakeholders were asked to choose between the two overarching policy approaches to support the transition toward a circular and bio-based economy in the chemical sector:

- Approach A: Boosting Circularity
- Approach B: Ensuring Sustainability of Biomass Use (illustrated in Figure 11)

Approach A: Circularity in relation to toxicity			Approach B: Sustainability of biomass use			
	Direct regulation	Market-based instruments		Direct regulation	Mixed policy approach	Market-based instruments
Promote transition	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Innovation subsidy For developing low-risk chemicals and toxic-free products according to EU-SSbD*-framework and decontamination technologies <small>(*: Safe and Sustainable by Design)</small>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Innovation subsidy For developing low-risk chemicals and toxic-free products according to EU-SSbD*-framework and decontamination technologies <small>(*: Safe and Sustainable by Design)</small>	Promote transition	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Quota for non-fossil feedstock shares in chemicals production – leading to phase out of fossil feedstocks, e.g. in 2050 ➤ Additional: innovation subsidies for development and market penetration of non-fossil chemicals 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Product subsidy for non-fossil chemicals, for example "green VAT" (reduced Value-Added Tax) ➤ Additional: phase out of fossil feedstocks leading to a final ban, e.g. in 2050 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Innovation subsidy for innovative non-fossil chemicals, including supporting market penetration of novel products
Limit substance use	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Thresholds for key Substances of Concern in products that inhibit reuse, recycling etc. ➤ REACH: extended criteria for chemicals permission that consider recycling, reuse etc. of products ➤ SCIP Extension Extension of EU SCIP database to chemicals inhibiting circularity 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Pollution tax on key Substances of Concern that pose major risks to health or environment and thus inhibit circularity (e.g., lead, PFAS, flame retardants) 	Limit resource use	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Sustainability criteria for biomass to be eligible to the quota (e.g., EU Renewable Materials Directive following the EU Renewable Energy Directive) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Sustainability criteria for biomass to be eligible to the subsidy (e.g., Renewable Materials Directive following the Renewable Energy Directive) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Carbon tax for fossil feedstocks in chemicals production and for low-value biomass uses

Figure 11: Overview of Approach A and Approach B for the Chemical Sector

Out of 4 respondents, 3 expressed a clear preference for Approach A, indicating strong support for measures such as reuse, recycling, and the development of low-toxicity chemicals aligned with the EU’s SSbD framework. These measures are seen as essential for enabling safer material loops and improving the recyclability of chemical products. Only one respondent selected Approach B, which focuses on ensuring the sustainable use of biomass resources through quotas, sustainability criteria, and innovation subsidies for non-fossil feedstocks.

This result suggests a prevailing stakeholder view that circularity-oriented policies are currently more effective and actionable in driving the transition toward a circular and bio-based economy in the chemical sector. While biomass sustainability remains an important consideration, stakeholders appear to prioritise interventions that directly reduce hazardous substances, resource consumption, and waste generation.

8.1.4. Plastics sector

Sustainability Challenges in the Plastic Sector

The EU produces more than 16 million tonnes of plastic waste annually, and this figure continues to rise. Less than half of this waste is currently recycled. Packaging waste dominates both collection and recycling efforts, largely due to existing EU policies, including mandatory recycling targets for packaging and legal obligations for producers to ensure the separate collection and recycling of plastic packaging waste. Since 2019, the EU has also introduced additional measures,

such as bans on certain single-use plastics and requirements for incorporating recycled materials into specific plastic products. These steps mark progress, but significant challenges remain.

In particular, despite these efforts, plastic waste generation in EU countries continues to grow. A major policy gap exists in the treatment of non-packaging plastics, such as those used in construction, electronics, and electrical devices. It is estimated that 60-75% of EU plastics demand relates to such non-packaging applications.

To address this gap, future policy approaches should focus on non-packaging plastics. Research on sustainable transitions indicates that measures such as recycling or substituting with biobased plastics do not automatically reduce overall waste or fossil fuel emissions. In fact, biobased alternatives can, under certain conditions, lead to unsustainable biomass use and increased greenhouse gas emissions. Therefore, direct regulation and market-based approaches should combine policy instruments that:

- i. promote transformative measures such as recycling and sustainable biomass use, and
- ii. contribute to limiting the overall consumption of plastics in the EU.

List of Policy Instruments for the Plastic Sector

Figure 12 below presents the distribution of stakeholder preferences regarding the eleven proposed policy instruments aimed at supporting the transition to a circular, biobased economy in the plastic sector. Each instrument was evaluated on a five-point scale ranging from “fully recommend” to “would not recommend at all”.

Figure 12: Stakeholder Recommendations on Policy Instruments for the Plastic Sector

The results show strong support for innovation subsidies, particularly for bioplastics and circular technologies (reuse, repair, recycling), indicating a clear preference for incentive-based measures that promote technological advancement and sustainable product design.

Ecodesign criteria and recycled content quotas also received favourable ratings, reflecting stakeholder interest in improving product durability and integrating recycled materials into production processes.

More mixed responses were observed for carbon pricing instruments, such as the carbon price for non-durable bioplastics and the fossil carbon tax, suggesting concerns about economic feasibility, implementation complexity or fear of higher costs by the industry. The instrument "removal of bioenergy and fossil subsidies" also received mixed feedback, with responses spread across recommendation levels, indicating differing views on its potential impact.

The ban on non-packaging plastic products and the forest carbon subsidy received varied feedback, with some stakeholders expressing strong support and others remaining neutral or sceptical. This reflects differing views on the effectiveness and potential unintended consequences of these measures.

The sustainability criteria and capped subsidies were generally well received, especially when linked to clear environmental standards such as GHG reduction and biomass sourcing restrictions.

Overall, the figure highlights a stakeholder preference for innovation-driven and design-focused policy instruments, while more restrictive or cost-intensive measures appear to require further discussion and refinement to gain broader acceptance.

Policy approach options

Subsequently, stakeholders were asked to choose between the two overarching policy approaches to support the transition toward a circular and biobased economy in the plastic sector:

- Approach A: Boosting Circularity
- Approach B: Ensuring Sustainability of Biomass Use (illustrated in Figure 13)

Which of these approaches would you prefer to boost the transition toward a circular and bio-based economy in the plastics sector?

Approach A: Boosting circularity			Approach B: Biomass use		
	Direct regulation	Market-based instruments		Direct regulation	Market-based instruments
Promote transition	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Quota for use of recycled content for producers of non-packaging plastics (e.g., major waste sources such as cars, electrical devices etc.) > Ecodesign criteria for non-packaging plastic products to improve ease of repair, recycling etc. > Public procurement 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Innovation subsidy for new technologies, practices and products connected to the re-use, repair or recycling (etc.) of non-packaging plastics 	Promote transition	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Product subsidy paid to producers of durable non-packaging plastic final or intermediate products made from biomass meeting sustainability criteria () 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Innovation subsidy for new bioplastics technologies and for innovative durable bioplastic products to support their market penetration
Limit resource use	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Product bans of additional single-use and short-life plastic products or product parts where sustainable and low-cost alternatives incl. reuse and repair are available 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Carbon price for use of fossil feedstocks as production input, to be paid by producers of non-packaging plastics 	Limit resource use	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Sustainability criteria for receiving the product subsidy. E.g., mandatory greenhouse gas reductions, exclusion of biomass from areas with high carbon or biodiversity value, restriction to durable products etc. > Additional: Cap for share or total quantity of biomass used in the sector 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> > Carbon tax on emissions from low-value biomass uses, e.g. from bioenergy and single-use / non-durable bioplastics products

Figure 13: Overview of Approach A and Approach B for the Plastic Sector

Out of 5 respondents, 4 expressed a clear preference for Approach A: Boosting Circularity, indicating strong support for measures such as reuse, recycling, and design for durability. Similarly to the textile sector, only 1 respondent selected Approach B, which focuses on ensuring the sustainable use of biomass resources.

This result suggests a prevailing stakeholder view that circularity-oriented policies are currently more effective and actionable in driving the transition toward a circular and biobased economy. While biomass sustainability remains relevant, stakeholders appear to prioritise interventions that directly reduce resource consumption and waste generation.

8.1.5. Construction sector

Sustainability Challenges in the Construction Sector

Buildings in the EU account for 40% of annual energy use and 36% of energy-related greenhouse gas emissions. With 75% of the building stock being energy inefficient, renovation is urgently needed. But energy inefficiency is only part of the issue. In 2021, housing made up 52% of the EU’s material footprint and 29% of total consumption expenditure. Of the 3.5 billion tonnes of materials used in construction, nearly three-quarters were non-metallic minerals like sand and gravel. The sector also generates over a third of the EU’s total waste, including hazardous materials such as asbestos.

EU policies focus mainly on improving energy efficiency and increasing the use of renewables, while the Waste Framework Directive promotes recycling and reuse of construction waste. However, avoiding extraction of non-metallic minerals offers limited environmental benefits. The Energy Performance of Buildings Directive introduces lifecycle carbon calculations and minimum energy performance standards, and the revised Construction Products Regulation proposes a Digital Product Passport for materials.

Despite these measures, the renovation rate of the worst-performing buildings remains at just 1%. Research calls for stricter enforcement of energy standards for residential buildings and a clearer strategy for biomass use to support sustainable heating and cooling.

List of Policy Instruments for the Construction Sector

Figure 14 below presents the distribution of stakeholder preferences regarding the ten proposed policy instruments (list available in Annex III) aimed at supporting the transition to a circular, bio-based economy in the construction sector. Each instrument was evaluated on a five-point scale ranging from “fully recommend” to “would not recommend at all.”

Figure 14: Stakeholder Evaluation of Policy Instruments in the Construction Sector

The results show strong support for innovation subsidies targeting circular technologies and ecodesign criteria, with the majority of respondents rating these instruments as “fully recommend.” This indicates a clear preference for measures that promote reuse, design for longevity, and technological innovation.

Subsidies for refurbishment also received positive feedback, reflecting stakeholder interest in extending the life cycle of existing buildings and materials through targeted financial incentives.

The quota or target for the use of bio-based and recycled materials received a more balanced distribution of responses, suggesting that while the concept is supported, stakeholders may have concerns about implementation feasibility or market readiness.

The carbon tax on lifecycle GHG emissions showed the most mixed response, with recommendations spread across all categories. This indicates divergent views on the effectiveness and potential economic impact of such a measure in the construction sector.

Overall, the figure suggests a stakeholder preference for supportive, innovation-oriented policy instruments. However, all proposed policy options warrant further deliberation and refinement. It should also be acknowledged that the apparent preference for subsidies over taxes and quotas is likely attributable to the predominance of industry representatives among respondents, and thus may reflect the composition of the sample rather than the intrinsic qualities of the instruments themselves.

Policy Approaches Options

Subsequently, stakeholders were asked to choose between the two overarching policy approaches to support the transition toward a circular and bio-based economy in the construction sector:

- Approach A: Boosting Circularity
- Approach B: Sustainability of Biomass Use (illustrated in Figure 15)

Approach A: Boosting circularity			Approach B: Biomass use		
	Direct regulation	Market-based instruments		Direct regulation	Market-based instruments
Promote transition	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ► Ecodesign criteria For building companies on design, construction and use of materials. Aim should be to design for reuse, disassembly, physical durability, adaptability and repair and minimising material intensity. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ► Innovation subsidy for innovative circular technologies or practices (e.g., use of recycled materials) 	Promote transition	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ► Quota/target for use of biobased and recycled material in new buildings including higher targets for public procurement 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ► Innovation subsidy for development and uses of innovative bio-based construction materials
Limit resource use	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ► Demolition Standards Requirements for the demolition of buildings, that increase chances for re-use, upcycling and recycling of materials, and thus encourage waste reduction and possibly refurbishment 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ► Material tax on the use of virgin raw materials for construction (e.g., gravel, stone, sand) including imports 	Limit resource use	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ► Sustainability criteria for biobased construction material to be eligible to the quota (e.g., EU Renewable Material Directive following the EU Renewable Energy Directive) ► Subsidy for refurbishment of buildings 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ► Carbon tax on all lifecycle GHG emissions of building materials that are NOT part of current carbon pricing (EU-ETS I+II) including the carbon content of short-life biomass materials. ► Carbon credit / subsidy Bio-based building materials that ensure long-term storage of carbon (e.g., 50+ years) are exempt from the tax and receive a credit / subsidy.

Figure 15: Overview of Approach A and Approach B for the Construction Sector

Out of six respondents from the construction sector, preferences were evenly split between the two proposed policy approaches for supporting the transition toward a circular and bio-based economy. Three respondents selected Approach A: Boosting Circularity, which focuses on strategies such as material reuse, recycling of construction waste, and design for longevity. The other three respondents chose Approach B: Sustainability of Biomass Use, emphasising responsible sourcing and efficient use of renewable materials, such as bio-based construction inputs.

This balanced outcome suggests that stakeholders in the construction sector recognise the importance of both circularity and biomass sustainability. It highlights the need for integrated policy frameworks that combine material efficiency with safeguards for renewable resource use, ensuring that environmental goals are achieved without compromising long-term resource availability.

9. CONCLUSIONS

This report provides a comprehensive overview of the activities undertaken within the SUSTRACK project and the corresponding results achieved in identifying, selecting, and prioritising policy actions to support the transition towards a circular bio-based economy (CBBE). Building on the SUSTRACK’s working definition of CBBE, which served as a conceptual foundation for identifying policy leverage points, the project proposed a set of tangible “policy means” - such as recycling and reuse - to support policymakers in creating effective and consistent policies. Policy actions were identified through a multi-step approach combining extensive literature reviews, different stakeholder engagement activities, and survey-based prioritisation. The analysis focused on four key sectors addressed in the SUSTRACK project: Construction, Textiles, Plastics and Chemicals, applying a case-study approach to ensure sector-specific relevance and applicability.

The first literature review focused on circular economy and bioeconomy policy instruments, while the other drew from resource and environmental economics to identify additional policy options. Together, these reviews provided support for the identification of over 90 policy instruments, which informed the selection of policy options for stakeholder discussion and validation.

Building on this foundation, stakeholder engagement played a central role in the co-creation and refinement of policy actions. SUSTRACK organised three major high-level conferences—INSPIRE, DESIGN, and IMPLEMENT—each building on the outcomes of the previous phase. These events brought together over 500 participants from academia, industry, civil society, and public

authorities. The conferences featured a combination of plenary presentations, expert inputs, and participatory workshops, ensuring that diverse stakeholder perspectives were systematically captured and effectively integrated into the policy co-creation process. Sector-specific workshops facilitated the identification of challenges, good practices, and recommendations, while the closing events of each conference-series synthesised these insights into actionable policy options tailored to the four case study sectors.

In particular, the IINSPIRE conference laid the analytical foundation for stakeholder engagement by presenting SUSTRACK's literature review, case studies, and initial policy scenarios. The DESIGN Conference facilitated the co-creation of transition pathways through sectoral workshops, generating preliminary policy recommendations across key dimensions. The IMPLEMENT conference translated visions into actionable policy options through collaborative assessment, supported by monitoring tools and case study insights.

Drawing on insights from the INSPIRE, the DESIGN and the IMPLEMENT conferences, a structured survey was implemented to rank identified policy instruments for the transition towards a CBBE in the four analysed sectors. Stakeholders were asked to evaluate individual instruments and choose between two overarching policy approaches: Approach A (Boosting Circularity) and Approach B (Ensuring Sustainability of Biomass Use). Across most sectors, stakeholders showed a clear preference for circularity-oriented policies, highlighting the importance of reuse, recycling, and design for durability. However, in the construction sector, preferences were evenly split, indicating the need for integrated approaches that balance circularity with responsible biomass use.

Stakeholders acknowledged that quota-based and ecodesign policies offer strong incentives for circularity and bio-based transitions, especially by stimulating innovation and market demand. However, they also highlighted implementation challenges, including technological limitations, administrative burdens, and risks of market fragmentation. Market-based instruments like subsidies and green taxes were praised for promoting behavioural change and competitiveness, yet concerns were raised about long-term sustainability, equity impacts, and the need for complementary measures. Overall, participants emphasised the importance of clear definitions, harmonised standards, and inclusive design to ensure effectiveness across sectors.

Several cross-cutting conclusions emerge from this analysis:

- **Circularity is a priority:** Stakeholders consistently favoured policy instruments that promote circular practices, such as ecodesign criteria, quotas for recycled content, and bans on the destruction of unsold goods. These measures are seen as effective in reducing resource consumption and waste generation.
- **Innovation must be supported:** Innovation subsidies were among the most recommended instruments across all sectors. Supporting the development and market penetration of new technologies is essential for enabling the transition and maintaining EU competitiveness.
- **Market-based instruments offer flexibility:** While direct regulation remains important, market-based instruments—such as carbon pricing, environmental taxes, and green VAT—can help manage complexity and incentivise sustainable behaviour without imposing rigid constraints.
- **Sustainability criteria or carbon pricing can help to minimise risks associated with biomass uses:** To avoid unintended consequences, especially in biomass use, sustainability criteria must be clearly defined and enforced. These criteria should be harmonised across sectors and aligned with EU climate and biodiversity goals. Alternatively, including low-value biomass uses into carbon pricing can provide another pathway to ensure sustainable biomass use.

- Sector-specific challenges require tailored solutions: Each sector presents unique barriers and opportunities. For example, the chemical sector faces toxicity risks that complicate recycling, while the construction sector must overcome regulatory misalignment and promote long-term carbon storage.
- Stakeholder engagement improves policy relevance: The participatory approach adopted in SUSTRACK ensured that policy recommendations are grounded in real-world needs and perspectives. This enhances their legitimacy and potential for successful implementation.

The final phase of the SUSTRACK stakeholder engagement process was marked by the DEPLOY Conferences, which shifted the focus from European-level visioning to national and local-level implementation. Results of these conferences are included in D5.4. Deployment workshops were held in six countries—Italy, Spain, Germany, Slovakia, the Netherlands, and Belgium—bringing SUSTRACK’s tools, resources, and policy instruments directly to local stakeholders. These workshops facilitated the translation of European strategies into national contexts, bridging the gap between policy design and practical implementation across governance levels. Stakeholders were supported in applying systems thinking, tailoring policy instruments to sector-specific needs, and deepening their understanding of SUSTRACK’s methodologies. As the concluding step in the engagement process, the DEPLOY Conferences ensured continuity between co-created policy frameworks and their real-world application, reinforcing the project’s contribution to a sustainable and inclusive CBBE transition.

In conclusion, this report provides a robust foundation for developing coherent and effective policy frameworks to advance the CBBE in Europe. By combining theoretical insights, empirical evidence, and stakeholder input, SUSTRACK contributes to shaping transformative policies that reconcile environmental sustainability with economic resilience.

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ANNEX I: OVERVIEW OF GOOD EXAMPLE POLICIES

No.	Policy instrument	Short description	CBBE - strategy & means	CBBE - strategy & means	Region	Time-frame	Type of instrument	Barrier addressed	Sector
1	Emission Trading Scheme (ETS)	A cap is set on the total amount of greenhouse gases that can be emitted by the installations and aircraft operators covered by the ETS system. The cap is reduced annually in line with the EU's climate target, ensuring that emissions decrease overtime. Companies can buy allowances for CO2 emissions. If an installation or operator reduce their emissions, they can either keep the spare allowances to use in the future or sell them. The declining cap offers companies certainty about the scarcity of allowances long term and ensures that allowances have market value. covers emissions from around 10,000 installations in the energy sector and manufacturing industry, as well as aircraft operators flying within the EU and departing to Switzerland and the United Kingdom - or around 40% of the EU's emissions.	•Reduce GHG emissions	•Reduce GHG emissions	EU	Current	Economic instrument	1.Lack of incentives	2.Chemical
2	DEI+ vergassing van reststromen (in English: subsidy gasification of residual streams)	This subsidy can be requested for the execution of a demonstration project, aimed at the gasification of waste streams (i.e., biogenic, or mixed). The installation converts these residues to renewable energy carriers, such as green gas, biofuel, or to a chemical. The entire gasification chain, including pre-treatment, torrefaction, gasification, and purification is eligible. This subsidy offers financial support to gasification initiatives, with a total budget of €98 million and a maximally granted amount of €30 million per request.	•Rs (repair, recycle, refuse, reuse, reduce, ...)	•Support material and/or energy (resource) use efficiency	NL	planned/ proposed	Economic instrument	1.Lack of incentives	2.Chemical
3	EU landfill Directive 1999/31/EC	Sets out strict operational requirements for landfill sites that EU countries must implement in national strategies to progressively reduce the amount of biodegradable waste sent to landfills to 10% in 2035. Landfill facilities may not accept used tyres or waste which is liquid, flammable, explosive or corrosive, or from hospitals and medical and veterinary practices only waste that has been treated may be landfilled. National authorities must ensure that the price operators charge for disposing of waste covers all the costs involved from opening to final closure of the site. Allows EU countries to use economic instruments and other measures to encourage applying the waste hierarchy	•Rs (repair, recycle, refuse, reuse, reduce, ...)	•Stimulate cascading use	EU	current	Direct regulation	1.Lack of incentives	5.All
4	Italian bioeconomy Strategy (BIT)	The Italian bioeconomy strategy (BIT) aims to boost sustainable production and quality across agriculture, forestry, and related industries, fostering innovation, investment, and regional coordination. It seeks to enhance environmental sustainability, economic growth, and social cohesion while promoting Italy's participation in Mediterranean initiatives for a greener, more productive region.	•Stimulate the use of alternative/renewable sources e.g. biomass, by-	•Phase out fossil	Italy	planned/ proposed	Other strategies	3.Lack of collaboration	5.All

No.	Policy instrument	Short description	CBBE - strategy & means	CBBE - strategy & means	Region	Time-frame	Type of instrument	Barrier addressed	Sector
			products, wastes						
5	Action Plan for the Implementation of the National Strategy for Bioeconomy (IAP) - Executive Action Plan (2020-2025) on the Italian Bioeconomy Strategy	The Action Plan for implementing the National Bioeconomy Strategy (BITII) outlines a detailed roadmap for fostering sustainable and circular bioeconomic practices in Italy. It aims to leverage bioeconomy to support socio-economic recovery post-Covid19, emphasizing legislative needs, economic opportunities, and concrete projects across sectors like agriculture, forestry, and marine industries. The plan focuses on promoting partnerships, regulatory development, local investment, ecosystem restoration, and public engagement to advance sustainable bioeconomic principles and address legislative barriers.	•Stimulate the use of alternative/renewable sources e.g. biomass, by-products, wastes	•Reduce GHG emissions	Italy	planned/proposed	Other strategies	1.Lack of incentives	5.All
6	National Smart Specialisation Strategy	The National Strategy of Smart Specialization (NSSS) aims to renew Italy's economy by promoting research, innovation, and competitiveness. It focuses on targeted interventions such as enhancing research networks, human capital, and public policies for businesses. Implemented through Action Plans, it fosters collaboration across government levels and stakeholders, guided by a Steering Committee and thematic working groups, facilitating the translation of research outcomes into competitive advantages for national productivity and citizen well-being.	•Stimulate the use of alternative/renewable sources e.g. biomass, by-products, wastes	•Reduce GHG emissions	Italy	planned/proposed	Other strategies	4.Lack of technology readiness	5.All
7	National Strategy for Sustainable Development	The National Strategy for Sustainable Development (SNSvS) serves as a comprehensive framework for coordinating and implementing sustainable development goals in Italy. Its main purpose is to integrate environmental, social, and economic dimensions of sustainability, aligning national policies and actions with the objectives of the United Nations' Agenda 2030. Through strategic planning, policy formulation, and the establishment of indicators for monitoring progress, the SNSvS aims to guide the country towards a more sustainable and inclusive future, ensuring the well-being of both people and the planet.	•Stimulate the use of alternative/renewable sources e.g. biomass, by-products, wastes	•Support material and/or energy (resource) use efficiency	Italy	planned/proposed	Other strategies	3.Lack of collaboration	5.All
8	National Strategy for the Circular Economy	The National Strategy for the Circular Economy aims to promote a transition towards a circular economy in Italy. It focuses on optimizing resource use, reducing waste, and increasing reuse and recycling. It introduces administrative and fiscal tools to strengthen the market for secondary raw materials and achieve climate neutrality objectives, defining a roadmap with actions and measurable targets until 2035.	•Support material and/or energy (resource) use efficiency	•Reduce GHG emissions	Italy	planned/proposed	Other strategies	4.Lack of technology readiness	5.All
9	Plan for Ecological Transition	The Plan for Ecological Transition aims to facilitate the ecological transition by implementing a comprehensive set of measures across various sectors, including decarbonization, sustainable mobility, air	•Reduce GHG emissions	•Support material and/or energy (resource)	Italy	planned/proposed	Other strategies	4.Lack of technology readiness	5.All

No.	Policy instrument	Short description	CBBE - strategy & means	CBBE - strategy & means	Region	Time-frame	Type of instrument	Barrier addressed	Sector
		quality improvement, land use management, water resource enhancement, biodiversity restoration, and circular economy promotion. It utilizes legislative frameworks, economic incentives, technological advancements, and social measures to achieve net-zero greenhouse gas emissions, sustainable mobility, improved air and water quality, reduced land use and hydrogeological risks, enhanced water resource management, biodiversity conservation, and promotion of circular economy practices.		use efficiency					
10	National Recovery and Resilience Plan	The National Recovery and Resilience Plan (PNRR) is a public investment plan aimed at addressing the economic crisis caused by the COVID-19 pandemic. Its main purpose is to stimulate economic growth, improve competitiveness, and enhance sustainability through targeted interventions in the digitalization, innovation, ecological transition, and social inclusion sectors. The PNRR also includes reforms to improve the efficiency of public administration and the judicial system.	•Stimulate the use of alternative/renewable sources e.g. biomass, by-products, wastes	•Reduce GHG emissions	Italy	planned/proposed	Other strategies	3.Lack of collaboration	5.All
11	National Waste Management Programme	The National Waste Management Program (PNGR) serves as a strategic tool guiding regions and autonomous provinces in waste management planning. It sets objectives, criteria, and strategic lines for regional waste management plans over a six-year period (2022-2028). The PNGR aligns with European goals to promote a sustainable and circular economy, thereby contributing to the National Circular Economy Strategy.	•Stimulate the use of alternative/renewable sources e.g. biomass, by-products, wastes	•Reduce GHG emissions	Italy	planned/proposed	Other strategies	4.Lack of technology readiness	5.All
12	Erp Italia Tessile - D.Lgs 116/2020	The Erp Italia Tessile aims to address textile waste management in Italy. It operates as a consortium within the European Recycling Platform, facilitating collection and recycling of textiles. The main purpose is to implement extended producer responsibility (EPR) for textiles, ensuring compliance with waste management regulations and promoting circular economy principles in the textile industry.	•Stimulate cascading use	•Reduce GHG emissions	Italy	current	Information and advice sharing system	3.Lack of collaboration	4.Textiles
13	Memorandum of understanding SPRING (IT) and Bioeconomy 4 Change (FR)	The memorandum of understanding between SPRING and the Bioeconomy 4 Change Cluster aims to strengthen cooperation between Italy and France in the circular bioeconomy. Through collaborations and knowledge exchanges, the main objective is to promote the transition to a more sustainable economy, with a specific focus on researching and developing innovative solutions in the bioplastic sector.			Italy				1.Plastics
14	Action plan for environmental sustainability of	The Action Plan for Environmental Sustainability of Consumption in the Public Administration aims to strengthen procurement practices in line with Green Public Procurement (GPP) guidelines. It seeks to enhance expertise, facilitate	•Support material and/or energy (resource)	•Reduce GHG emissions	Italy	planned/proposed	Other strategies	3.Lack of collaboration	5.All

No.	Policy instrument	Short description	CBBE - strategy & means	CBBE - strategy & means	Region	Time-frame	Type of instrument	Barrier addressed	Sector
	consumption in the public administration sector	information exchange, and promote sustainable and circular economy models in public procurement, fostering green job creation and social cohesion while ensuring efficient monitoring and adaptation to evolving technological and regulatory landscapes.	use efficiency						
15	Report on European Bioeconomy	The Report on European Bioeconomy aims to promote the bioeconomy and sustainability in the textile and clothing sector. It focuses on the use of renewable biological resources and transforming waste into value-added products. The main goal is to reduce the use of non-renewable resources, improve efficiency, and promote circular practices to address environmental and climate challenges.	•Stimulate the use of alternative/renewable sources e.g. biomass, by-products, wastes	•Reduce GHG emissions	Italy	current	Information and advice sharing system	1.Lack of incentives	4.Textiles
16	National Forestry Strategy	The National Forest Strategy (SFN) aims to promote sustainable management of Italy's national forest heritage in alignment with international commitments. It focuses on balancing societal interests with ecosystem protection, fostering sustainable wood economies, and implementing actions to address climate, biodiversity, and socio-economic development challenges. The SFN operates through strategic objectives, actions, financial instruments, and monitoring mechanisms, engaging stakeholders across sectors to ensure effective implementation and long-term sustainability.	•Stimulate the use of alternative/renewable sources e.g. biomass, by-products, wastes	•Reduce GHG emissions	Italy	planned/proposed	Other strategies	4.Lack of technology readiness	5.All
17	Regional strategies for sustainable development - Regional strategies for sustainable development (investigation on the development process)	The Regional strategies for sustainable development aims to reconstruct, up to March 2020, the status of the processes for defining regional and provincial strategies for sustainable development. These strategies constitute one of the main areas of implementation and territorialization at the national level.			Italy				5.All
18	The Made in Italy Law	The "Law December 27, 2023, No. 206" contains organic provisions aimed at enhancing and promoting, in Italy and abroad, excellent productions, cultural heritage, and national cultural roots as factors to be preserved and transmitted not only for identity purposes but also for the growth of the national economy within the framework and in accordance with the rules of the European Union's internal market.	•Stimulate the use of alternative/renewable sources e.g. biomass, by-products, wastes	•Support material and/or energy (resource) use efficiency	Italy	current	Direct regulation	4.Lack of technology readiness	4.Textiles
19	Italian bioeconomy Strategy (BIT) - (Focus on Plastics)	The Italian Bioeconomy Strategy aims to boost Italy's bioeconomy sector by fostering research, innovation, and market growth in bio-based industries such as agriculture, forestry, and bio-based chemicals. It seeks to increase turnover and job opportunities by implementing measures such as waste-	•Stimulate the use of alternative/renewable sources e.g.	•Support material and/or energy (resource) use efficiency	Italy	planned/proposed	Other strategies	1.Lack of incentives	1.Plastics

No.	Policy instrument	Short description	CBBE - strategy & means	CBBE - strategy & means	Region	Time-frame	Type of instrument	Barrier addressed	Sector
		related regulations, public procurement support, and the establishment of local biorefineries. The strategy emphasizes collaboration between government bodies, the private sector, and civil society to achieve sustainable economic development through the bioeconomy.	biomass, by-products, wastes						
20	PLASTEKO Project	Improving regional policies for a more circular management of plastic and its waste, in all its phases: from promoting alternative disposable materials, to initiatives for management and separate collection, up to combating dispersion in water and the environment of plastics and monitoring microplastics. This is the goal of Plasteco, the Interreg project in which the Lombardy Region actively participates, involving universities, research institutions, and private companies as stakeholders, members of the regional observatory for the circular economy and energy transition	•Rs (repair, recycle, refuse, reuse, reduce, ...)	•Support material and/or energy (resource) use efficiency	Lombardy (IT)	current	Information and advice sharing system	2.Lack of information	1.Plastics
21	Textile Pact Memorandum of Understanding	Promote policies and actions aimed at fostering the development of the circular economy of the Prato textile district in Tuscany region, Italy.	•Stimulate the use of alternative/renewable sources e.g. biomass, by-products, wastes	•Support material and/or energy (resource) use efficiency	Italy	current	Other strategies	2.Lack of information	4.Textiles
22	Next Generation Prato	It is the strategic and operative document with which the Municipality of Prato and the main actors of the productive economic fabric share the strategy and related projects to take advantage of the opportunities arisen thanks to the National Recovery and Resilience Plan, and take a significant step towards the ecological, digital and circular transition of the city.	•Stimulate the use of alternative/renewable sources e.g. biomass, by-products, wastes	•Support material and/or energy (resource) use efficiency	Tuscany (IT)	current	Other strategies	3.Lack of collaboration	5.All
23	Toscana Carbon Neutral 2050 Strategy (TCN2050)	The Strategy is committed to making emission reduction actions current, precise and measurable. The goal is to implement immediate actions and achieve, even before 2050 set as the European Union's deadline, a zero emission balance. It is proposed to do this in two ways: on the one hand by reducing emissions, overcoming the model of the traditional economy for sustainable ways of producing and consuming, and on the other hand by proposing a real regional green plan, so that trees and plants enter the spaces of our cities and can, as real filters, make the air we breathe better and absorb the climate-altering gases in the atmosphere. This document has, as mentioned, the goal of carbon neutrality to 2050 and is implemented through the adoption of Action Plans with a validity of	•Reduce GHG emissions	•Stimulate the use of alternative/renewable sources e.g. biomass, by-products, wastes	Tuscany (IT)	current	Other strategies	2.Lack of information	

No.	Policy instrument	Short description	CBBE - strategy & means	CBBE - strategy & means	Region	Time-frame	Type of instrument	Barrier addressed	Sector
		10-year period. The first of these is valid for the period 2020-2030.							
24	Funding Guideline Repair Premium Saxony (Förderrichtlinie Reparaturbonus Sachsen)	Private actors or companies in Saxony (Germany) can apply for subsidy for repairing electronic and electrical devices. The subsidy covers up to 50 % of repair costs, minimum 75 € in total and maximum 200 € per repaired item. Maximum number of eligible repairs per year is 2.	•Rs (repair, recycle, refuse, reuse, reduce, ...)		Saxony (GER)	current	Economic instrument	1.Lack of incentives	
25	Packaging Law (Verpackungsgesetz)	Germany's packaging law sets requirements for the design and collection of packaging (waste): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Packagings have to be reduced to the minimum amount necessary to ensure safety, hygiene and acceptance by consumers - packaging has to be designed so that it can be recycled, including avoidance of harmful substance to minimize environmental damages in case of recycling (includes limits for certain metals) - reusability and use of secondary resources shall be increased (no quantitative target) under consideration of security, hygiene, acceptance, economic viability and technical feasibility - producers of packaging have to participate in waste collection schemes - packaging waste has to be collected separately - producers and retailers have to take back empty packaging - waste collection schemes have to ensure that 55-90 % of collected waste has to be recycled (quota depends on type of waste) - waste collection schemes have to design collection fees in a way that incentivizes the use of materials that can be recycled to a high percentage 	•Rs (repair, recycle, refuse, reuse, reduce, ...)	•Support material and/or energy (resource) use efficiency	Germany	current	Direct regulation	1.Lack of incentives	1.Plastics
26	Funding programmes for wood construction	Some German states (Bavaria, Baden-Württemberg, Hamburg) provide subsidies for the use of wood in construction (buildings)	•Stimulate the use of alternative/renewable sources e.g. biomass, by-products, wastes		Germany	current	Economic instrument	1.Lack of incentives	3.Construction
27	Sewage sludge ordinance	recycling quota for phosphorus from 2029 (50-80 % depending on circumstances)	•Stimulate the use of alternative/renewable sources		Germany	current	Direct regulation	1.Lack of incentives	

No.	Policy instrument	Short description	CBBE - strategy & means	CBBE - strategy & means	Region	Time-frame	Type of instrument	Barrier addressed	Sector
			e.g. biomass, by-products, wastes						
28	SEC - Strategy for Circular Economy	The SEC project ""Strategy for Circular Economy in the Autonomous Province of Bolzano"" was developed by the Institute for Renewable Energy and the Institute for Regional Development of Eurac Research, and funded by the Italian Ministry for the Ecological Transition. The project analyzed, in the period between September 2020 and June 2022, the state of the art on circular economy penetration in the Autonomous Province of Bolzano. The results, collected in 9 public reports, aim to support public policies and private enterprises towards circular economy by focusing on potential synergies between the bioeconomy and construction sectors. In particular, the project addressed the potential recovery and re-use of by-products and waste from agricultural and forestry activities, in building materials or components.	•Stimulate the use of alternative/renewable sources e.g. biomass, by-products, wastes	•Rs (repair, recycle, refuse, reuse, reduce, ...)	Autonomous Province of Bolzano (Italy)	old	Other strategies		3.Construction
29	EU Strategy for Sustainable and Circular Textiles	This document outlines a strategic approach by the European Commission to address sustainability and circularity in the textile industry. The document proposes various measures, regulations, and initiatives to guide and regulate the actions of stakeholders in the textile sector towards more sustainable practices. By setting out goals, strategies, and proposed actions, the document serves as a governance tool to influence behavior, promote compliance with sustainability objectives, and drive systemic change in the textile industry.	•Support material and/or energy (resource) use efficiency	•Stimulate the use of alternative/renewable sources e.g. biomass, by-products, wastes	EU	current	Information and advice sharing system	2.Lack of information	4.Textiles
30	Cardato Recycled - Made in Prato trademark	The "Cardato Recycled" and "Cardato" brands are promoted by the Pistoia-Prato Chamber of Commerce, in collaboration with the Consortium for the Valorization of Carded Textile Products, Unione Industriale Pratese, Cna and Confartigianato. SGS, the international certification body, ensures the certification and also provides a connection with fashion brands. In order to bear the "Cardato Recycled" label, fabrics and yarns must be: produced within the Prato district; made with at least 65% recycled material (clothing or textile processing waste); and have measured the environmental impact of the entire production cycle taking into account three aspects: impact of water consumption, energy consumption and CO2.	•Rs (repair, recycle, refuse, reuse, reduce, ...)	•Reduce GHG emissions	Tuscany (IT)	current	Market based signalling approach	2.Lack of information	4.Textiles
31	Refund system for PET bottles	2007 extended to other plastics, finally replaced by packaging tax on virgin packaging material	•Reduce GHG emissions	•Rs (repair, recycle, refuse, reuse, reduce, ...)	Denmark	old	Economic instrument	1.Lack of incentives	1.Plastics

No.	Policy instrument	Short description	CBBE - strategy & means	CBBE - strategy & means	Region	Time-frame	Type of instrument	Barrier addressed	Sector
32	EU Waste Framework Directive WFD	stipulates waste hierarchy and recycling targets incl. 60 % for plastic packaging until 2025			EU				
33	removal of environmentally harmful subsidies [general]	refers to harmful subsidies in general	•Reduce GHG emissions	•Stimulate the use of alternative/renewable sources e.g. biomass, by-products, wastes		proposed	Other strategies	1.Lack of incentives	5.All
34	Cost-refund system for biomass industry	refund based on achieved CO2-savings [no further explanations provided]	•Stimulate the use of alternative/renewable sources e.g. biomass, by-products, wastes	•Stimulate cascading use		proposed	Economic instrument	1.Lack of incentives	5.All
35	quotas for biomaterial use	no details provided	•Stimulate the use of alternative/renewable sources e.g. biomass, by-products, wastes	•Support material and/or energy (resource) use efficiency		proposed	Direct regulation	1.Lack of incentives	5.All
36	public procurement for biomaterials	no details provided	•Stimulate the use of alternative/renewable sources e.g. biomass, by-products, wastes	•Support material and/or energy (resource) use efficiency		proposed	Direct regulation	1.Lack of incentives	5.All
37	R&D support for bio-based materials	no details provided	•Stimulate the use of alternative/renewable sources e.g. biomass, by-products, wastes	•Support material and/or energy (resource) use efficiency		proposed	Economic instrument	4.Lack of technology readiness	5.All
38	R&D support for enhanced ecodesign	no details provided	•Stimulate	•Rs (repair, recycle,		proposed	Economic instrument	4.Lack of technology readiness	5.All

No.	Policy instrument	Short description	CBBE - strategy & means	CBBE - strategy & means	Region	Time-frame	Type of instrument	Barrier addressed	Sector
	(better design for reuse/recycling)		cascading use	refuse, reuse, reduce, ...)					
39	R&D for improved logistics between sectors to better use byproducts	no details provided	•Stimulate cascading use	•Stimulate the use of alternative/renewable sources e.g. biomass, by-products, wastes		proposed	Economic instrument	4.Lack of technology readiness	5.All
40	virgin raw material taxes	no details provided	•Stimulate cascading use	•Support material and/or energy (resource) use efficiency		proposed	Economic instrument	1.Lack of incentives	5.All
41	VAT reduction on secondary materials	no details provided	•Stimulate cascading use	•Stimulate the use of alternative/renewable sources e.g. biomass, by-products, wastes		proposed	Economic instrument	1.Lack of incentives	5.All
42	loan guarantees	<u>A loan guarantee is a public commitment to repay the lender in the event of a borrower default. Loan guarantees are used, e.g., in US for supporting high-risk large-scale energy infrastructure projects -> https://www.energy.gov/lpo/articles/lpos-loans-and-loan-guarantees-overview-and-characteristics-its-financing-options</u>	•Stimulate the use of alternative/renewable sources e.g. biomass, by-products, wastes			proposed	Other strategies	6. Other	2.Chemical
43	Wood-fibre-act	prioritization of wood uses for traditional forest industry - additional allocation to energy sector only in times of “excess supply”	•Stimulate cascading use	•Support material and/or energy (resource) use efficiency	Sweden	old	Direct regulation	1.Lack of incentives	5.All
44	EU WEEE Directive	Collection and recovery rates for electric and electronic waste (often with plastic components - higher recycling decreases emissions from low-quality recycling in foreign countries that often includes burning plastic components = GHG emissions)	•Rs (repair, recycle, refuse, reuse, reduce, ...)	•Reduce GHG emissions	EU	current	Direct regulation	1.Lack of incentives	1.Plastics
45	EU RoHS Directive	restricts use of hazardous substances in WEEE -> limits in EEs for lead, mercury, cadmium, hexavalent chromium, polybrominated biphenyls (PBBs) and PBDEs			EU	current	Direct regulation	1.Lack of incentives	2.Chemical

No.	Policy instrument	Short description	CBBE - strategy & means	CBBE - strategy & means	Region	Time-frame	Type of instrument	Barrier addressed	Sector
46	carbon pricing	required price level for full defossilization of chemical/plastic industry strongly depends on price development for fossil resources, biomass and electricity - ranges from 190-375 USD/t CO ₂ eq in cost-optimal scenarios - otherwise even higher prices up to more than 900 USD required	•Phase out fossil	•Reduce GHG emissions	global	proposed	Economic instrument	1.Lack of incentives	1.Plastics
47	Packaging and Waste Packaging directive (94/62/EC)	Promote reuse, recycling and other forms of recovery of packaging waste to facilitate the transition to a circular economy	•Rs (repair, recycle, refuse, reuse, reduce, ...)	•Support material and/or energy (resource) use efficiency	EU	old	Direct regulation	1.Lack of incentives	1.Plastics
48	REACH EU Regulation 1907/2006/EC	Regulate the registration, evaluation and authorisation of chemicals to ensure safety for human health and the environment	•Phase out fossil	•Support material and/or energy (resource) use efficiency	EU	current	Direct regulation	2. Lack of information	1.Plastics
49	Waste Framework Directive (2008/98/EC)	Establish measures to protect the environment and human health by preventing waste and increasing recycling	•Rs (repair, recycle, refuse, reuse, reduce, ...)	•Stimulate cascading use	EU	current	Direct regulation	1.Lack of incentives	5.All
50	Ecodesign Directive (2009/125/EC)	Set minimum environmental requirements for energy-using and energy-related products throughout their lifecycle	•Support material and/or energy (resource) use efficiency	•Reduce GHG emissions	EU	current	Direct regulation	4.Lack of technology readiness	5.All
51	Single Use Plastics Directive (2019/904)	Restrict certain single-use plastics and mandates member states to reduce their consumption	•Rs (repair, recycle, refuse, reuse, reduce, ...)	•Support material and/or energy (resource) use efficiency	EU	current	Direct regulation	5. lack of acceptance	1.Plastics
52	EU Plastics Strategy	Aim to transform the way plastics are produced, used, and recycled in the EU	•Rs (repair, recycle, refuse, reuse, reduce, ...)	•Support material and/or energy (resource) use efficiency	EU	current	Information and advice sharing system	3.Lack of collaboration	1.Plastics
53	EU Policy Framework on Biobased, Biodegradable and Compostable Plastics	Encourage the use of biobased, biodegradable, and compostable plastics	•Stimulate the use of alternative/renewable sources e.g. biomass, by-products, wastes	•Support material and/or energy (resource) use efficiency	EU	current	Voluntary approach	4.Lack of technology readiness	1.Plastics
54	EU Directive (2015/720) on Lightweight Plastics Carrier Bags	Measures to reduce the consumption of lightweight plastic carrier bags	•Rs (repair, recycle, refuse, reuse, reduce, ...)	•Support material and/or energy (resource) use efficiency	EU	current	Direct regulation	1.Lack of incentives	1.Plastics

No.	Policy instrument	Short description	CBBE - strategy & means	CBBE - strategy & means	Region	Time-frame	Type of instrument	Barrier addressed	Sector
			reduce, ...)	use efficiency					
55	EU Ecolabel Regulation/2010	Provide a voluntary label for products and services that have a reduced environmental impact	•Support material and/or energy (resource) use efficiency	•Rs (repair, recycle, refuse, reuse, reduce, ...)	EU	current	Voluntary approach	2.Lack of information	5.All
56	Energy Labelling Regulation/2017	Mandatory energy labels for appliances to inform consumers about energy efficiency	•Support material and/or energy (resource) use efficiency	•Rs (repair, recycle, refuse, reuse, reduce, ...)	EU	current	Direct regulation	2.Lack of information	5.All
57	Green Public Procurement /2008	Encourage public authorities to purchase environmentally friendly products and services	•Stimulate the use of alternative/renewable sources e.g. biomass, by-products, wastes	•Support material and/or energy (resource) use efficiency	EU	current	Information and advice sharing system	3.Lack of collaboration	5.All
58	Circular Economy Action Plan/2015	Provide a comprehensive plan for transitioning the EU to a circular economy	•Rs (repair, recycle, refuse, reuse, reduce, ...)	•Support material and/or energy (resource) use efficiency	EU	current	Information and advice sharing system	1.Lack of incentives	5.All
59	Sustainable Products Initiative/2020c	Aim to make products more sustainable through design requirements, with a focus on reducing their environmental footprint	•Rs (repair, recycle, refuse, reuse, reduce, ...)	•Support material and/or energy (resource) use efficiency	EU	planned/proposed	Direct regulation	4.Lack of technology readiness	5.All
60	EU Commission Regulation 10/2011 on plastic food contact materials	Authorise the composition of food contact materials containing plastics	•Support material and/or energy (resource) use efficiency	•Stimulate the use of alternative/renewable sources e.g. biomass, by-products, wastes	EU	current	Direct regulation	4.Lack of technology readiness	1.Plastics
61	Microplastics restrictions	Limit the use of intentionally added microplastics in products	•Rs (repair, recycle, refuse, reuse, reduce, ...)	•Support material and/or energy (resource) use efficiency	EU	planned/proposed	Direct regulation	4.Lack of technology readiness	1.Plastics
62	Levy on certain plastic bags	Impose a tax on certain plastic bags to reduce consumption	•Rs (repair, recycle, refuse, reuse, ...)	•Support material and/or energy (resource)	Denmark	current	Economic instrument	1.Lack of incentives	1.Plastics

No.	Policy instrument	Short description	CBBE - strategy & means	CBBE - strategy & means	Region	Time-frame	Type of instrument	Barrier addressed	Sector
			reduce, ...)	use efficiency					
63	Levy on plastic bags	Impose a tax on plastic bags to reduce consumption	•Rs (repair, recycle, refuse, reuse, reduce, ...)	•Support material and/or energy (resource) use efficiency	Ireland	current	Economic instrument	1.Lack of incentives	1.Plastics
64	Plastic Bags Directive	Limit the use of plastic bags across the EU	•Rs (repair, recycle, refuse, reuse, reduce, ...)	•Support material and/or energy (resource) use efficiency	EU	current	Direct regulation	1.Lack of incentives	1.Plastics
65	EU Classification, Labelling and Packaging of Chemicals	Implementation of GHS	•Support material and/or energy (resource) use efficiency	•Stimulate the use of alternative/renewable sources e.g. biomass, by-products, wastes	EU	current	Direct regulation	2.Lack of information	2.Chemical
66	HELCOM Marine Litter Action Plan	Prevent plastic waste and its discharges into the Baltic Sea	•Rs (repair, recycle, refuse, reuse, reduce, ...)	•Stimulate the use of alternative/renewable sources e.g. biomass, by-products, wastes	Baltic Sea	current	Direct regulation	1.Lack of incentives	5.All
67	Single-use plastic legislations in 14 states	Banning or restriction of plastic items (straws, bags, cups, or single-use plastics in general and micro plastics)	•Support material and/or energy (resource) use efficiency		Brazil (in 14 States)	current	Direct regulation	2.Lack of information	1.Plastics
68	Ban on ultra-thin plastic bags	Prohibit the production of ultra-thin plastic bags and prohibit the retail stores handing out free ultra-thin plastic bags	•Support material and/or energy (resource) use efficiency		China				
69	Ban on six single-use plastics	Ban on six single-use plastic items that are commonly found in the environment that are not practically recyclable and have a potential alternative on the market	•Support material and/or energy (resource) use efficiency		Canada				

No.	Policy instrument	Short description	CBBE - strategy & means	CBBE - strategy & means	Region	Time-frame	Type of instrument	Barrier addressed	Sector
70	OSPAR Commission Action Plan for Marine Litter	Prevent inputs of and significantly reduce marine litter, including microplastics, in the marine environment to reach levels that do not cause adverse impacts to the marine and coastal environment with the ultimate aim of eliminating inputs of litter	•Support material and/or energy (resource) use efficiency		North-East Atlantic				
71	G7 Action Plan to Combat Marine Litter	Address research, land- and sea-based sources of marine litter, removing litter from the sea and public relations	•Support material and/or energy (resource) use efficiency		World wide				
72	Japanese Feed-In Tariff (FIT)	Induce energy cost burdens since program inception cognizant of the energy mix of CO2 intensity reductions in the electricity generation sector	•Support material and/or energy (resource) use efficiency		Japan				
73	Japanese Emissions Trading Systems (ETS)	Tokyo Cap-and-Trade and Saitama ETS pricing	•Support material and/or energy (resource) use efficiency		Japan				
74	Proposed Japanese Hydrogen Economy	Consider the impacts of introducing a hydrogen economy to aid in the achievement of 2050 carbon neutrality goals-modeled and estimated	•Support material and/or energy (resource) use efficiency		Japan				
75	Reinvigoration of Nuclear Power	Restart nuclear power plants and extension of operating lifetimes; no new builds, cognizant of the energy mix CO2 reductions in the electricity-generation sector	•Support material and/or energy (resource) use efficiency		Japan				
76	Transition away from ICE	Implications of a shift to EV and FCV passenger vehicle options post-2035	•Support material and/or energy (resource) use efficiency		Japan				
77	Regulations for Reskilling and Training	This policy proposes that companies spend a percentage of their profit on reskilling and training programs for the circular transition. In the textile sector, this could mean upskilling workers to adapt to new sustainable and circular production methods, promoting innovation, and reducing waste. By investing in their workforce, companies can stay competitive while contributing to a more circular and environmentally friendly industry.	support material and/or energy (resource) use efficiency	Rs (repair, recycle, refuse, reduce...)	The Netherlands, Spain, India	proposed	2. economic instrument 3. Voluntary approach	1. Lack of incentive	4. Textile

No.	Policy instrument	Short description	CBBE - strategy & means	CBBE - strategy & means	Region	Time-frame	Type of instrument	Barrier addressed	Sector
78	Tax Credits for Businesses with Circular Jobs	Tax credits to businesses that dedicate staff to circular jobs, encouraging companies to invest in sustainable practices and create jobs that support the circular economy. In the textile sector, this could incentivize companies to adopt circular business models, reduce waste, and promote sustainable production methods, ultimately contributing to a more circular and environmentally friendly industry.	support material and/or energy (resource) use efficiency	Rs (repair, recycle, refuse, redce...)	The Netherlands, Spain, India	proposed	2. economic instrument	1. Lack of incentives	4. Textile
79	Extended Producer Responsibility (EPR) with Global Accountability Fees	This policy holds producers accountable for the environmental impact of their products throughout their entire lifecycle. In the textile sector, EPR could incentivize companies to design more sustainable products, reduce waste, and promote recycling, ultimately contributing to a more circular and environmentally friendly industry.	Rs (repair, recycle, refuse, reuse, reduce...)	support material and/or energy (resource) use efficiency	The Netherlands, Spain, India	proposed	1. Direct regulation 3. Vountary approach	3. Lack of collaboration	4. Textile
80	Environmental Tax on Products and Services	Tax on products and services that have a negative environmental impact. In the textile sector, this could encourage companies to adopt sustainable production methods, reduce waste, and promote recycling. The revenue generated from this tax could be used to fund initiatives that support the circular economy.	support material and/or energy (resource) use efficiency	Stimulate the use of alternative/renewable sources e.g. biomass, by-products, wastes	Finland	proposed	2. economic instrument	1. Lack of incentives	4. Textile
81	Value Added Tax (VAT) Reform	Aims to reduce VAT on sustainable products and services, making them more competitive in the market. In the textile sector, this could incentivize companies to develop and market sustainable products, promoting a shift towards a circular economy. The VAT reform could also encourage consumers to choose sustainable products over traditional ones.	Stimulate the use of alternative/renewable sources e.g. biomass, by-products, wastes	Rs (repair, recycle, refuse, redce...)	Finland	proposed	2. economic instrument	1. Lack of incentives	4. Textile
82	Eco-Labels and Standards	Establishes a labeling system that certifies products meeting certain environmental and social standards. In the textile sector, eco-labels could help consumers make informed choices about sustainable products, promoting demand for circular and biobased textiles. Eco-labels could also encourage companies to improve their sustainability performance to gain a competitive advantage.	Rs (repair, recycle, refuse, reuse, reduce...)	Stimulate the use of alternative/renewable sources e.g. biomass, by-products, wastes	Finland	proposed	3. Voluntary approach 5. Market based signalling	2. Lack of information	4. Textile
83	Corporate Subsidies Based on Environmental Impact	Provides subsidies to companies that demonstrate a strong environmental performance. In the textile sector, this could incentivize companies to invest in sustainable production methods, reduce waste, and promote recycling. The subsidies could be used to offset the costs of transitioning to a circular economy.	Rs (repair, recycle, refuse, reuse, reduce...)	support material and/or energy (resource) use efficiency	Finland	proposed	2. economic instrument	1. Lack of incentives	4. Textile

No.	Policy instrument	Short description	CBBE - strategy & means	CBBE - strategy & means	Region	Time-frame	Type of instrument	Barrier addressed	Sector
84	legislative intervention mandating the separation of textile waste	Aims to improve the quality of textile waste, which can then be utilized in a circular biobased textile sector. By making separation mandatory, the policy encourages the development of infrastructure and practices that support the recycling and reuse of textile waste.	Rs (repair, recycle, refuse, reuse, reduce...)	support material and/or energy (resource) use efficiency	Czech Republic	future	1. Direct regulation	1. Lack of incentives	4. Textile
85	EU's green public procurement (GPP) criteria for textiles	EU green public procurement (GPP) criteria are designed to make it easier for public authorities to purchase goods, services and works with reduced environmental impacts. The use of the criteria is voluntary. The criteria are formulated in such a way that they can be, if deemed appropriate by the individual authority, integrated into its tender documents with minimal editing	support material and/or energy (resource) use efficiency	Rs (repair, recycle, refuse, redce...)	EU	current	1. Direct regulation 3. Voluntary approach	1. Lack of incentives	4. Textile
86	EU Ecolabel for clothing and textiles	Certification program that establishes ecological criteria, limiting the use of substances harmful to health and the environment, reducing water and air pollution, and criteria for extending the lifetime of clothes. The Ecolabel promotes the use of environmentally friendly textiles and encourages producers to design more sustainable products.	support material and/or energy (resource) use efficiency	Stimulate the use of alternative/renewable sources e.g. biomass, by-products, wastes	EU	current	3. Voluntary approach	1. Lack of incentives 2. Lack of information	4. Textile
87	New Ecodesign Regulation	Define minimum requirements for all products on the internal market regarding circularity, including durability, reliability, reusability, reparability, upgradeability, recyclability, and possibility to remanufacture, recycle and recover materials. The regulation also introduces a mandatory digital passport, providing businesses and consumers with information on harmful chemicals, repair, and fibre composition. It would introduce an obligation for companies to make public information on the destruction of unsold products	support material and/or energy (resource) use efficiency	Stimulate the use of alternative/renewable sources e.g. biomass, by-products, wastes	EU	current	1. Direct regulation	1. Lack of incentives	4. Textile
88	EU Strategy for Sustainable and Circular Textiles	Aims to make the production and consumption of textiles more sustainable by 2030. It sets out to make textiles durable and recyclable, made up largely of recycled fibres free of hazardous substances, and produced in an environmentally friendly way while respecting social rights. The strategy promotes a circular business model for textiles, encouraging companies to design out waste and pollution.	support material and/or energy (resource) use efficiency	Stimulate the use of alternative/renewable sources e.g. biomass, by-products, wastes	EU	current	6. Other (strategy)	6. Other	4. Textile
89	Harmonised product environmental footprint (PEF) methodology	Provides a standardized way to assess the environmental impact of textile products. It enables consumers and companies to make informed decisions about the sustainability of textile products. The PEF methodology substantiates green claims, preventing companies from making misleading environmental claims.	support material and/or energy (resource) use efficiency	Rs (repair, recycle, refuse, reuse, reduce...)	EU	future	1. Direct regulation 5. Market based signalling	2. Lack of information	4. Textile

No.	Policy instrument	Short description	CBBE - strategy & means	CBBE - strategy & means	Region	Time-frame	Type of instrument	Barrier addressed	Sector
90	Durability and longevity standards and labels	These standards and labels aim to promote sustainable design and production modes by setting requirements for the durability and longevity of textile products. By meeting these standards, companies can demonstrate their commitment to sustainability and differentiate themselves in the market. This instrument encourages companies to design and produce more sustainable products	Stimulate the use of alternative/renewable sources e.g. biomass, by-products, wastes	Rs (repair, recycle, refuse, redce...)	EU	planned/proposed	3. Voluntary approach 5. Market based signalling	2. Lack of information	4. Textile
91	Taxes on fast-fashion products with short lifetimes	Discourages the production and consumption of fast-fashion products by imposing taxes on them. The tax revenue can be used to support more sustainable fashion initiatives. By increasing the cost of fast-fashion products, this tax can incentivize consumers to opt for more sustainable alternatives.	support material and/or energy (resource) use efficiency	Stimulate the use of alternative/renewable sources e.g. biomass, by-products, wastes	EU	planned/proposed	2. Economic instrument	1. Lack of incentive	4. Textile
92	Reduced taxes on repair	Encourages the repair of textiles by reducing taxes on repair services. By making repair services more affordable, this policy can incentivize consumers to repair their textiles instead of discarding them. This can help reduce waste and promote a more circular textile sector.	Rs (repair, recycle, refuse, redce...)		EU	planned/proposed	2. Economic instrument	1. Lack of incentive	4. Textile
93	Extended Producer Responsibility (EPR) schemes	EPR schemes aim to hold manufacturers responsible for the waste generated by their products. By requiring manufacturers to take back and recycle their products, EPR schemes can incentivize them to design more sustainable products and reduce waste.	Rs (repair, recycle, refuse, reuse, reduce...)	support material and/or energy (resource) use efficiency	EU	planned/proposed	1. Direct regulation 3. Vountary approach	3. Lack of collaboration	4. Textile
94	Financial incentives to "slow-fashion" companies	Supports companies that adopt slow-fashion business models by providing them with financial incentives. Slow-fashion companies prioritize sustainability and durability over fast production and low costs.	Rs (repair, recycle, refuse, reuse, reduce...)	support material and/or energy (resource) use efficiency	EU	planned/proposed	2. Economic instrument	1. Lack of incentive	4. Textile
95	Emission Trading Scheme (ETS)	A cap is set on the total amount of greenhouse gases that can be emitted by the installations and aircraft operators covered by the ETS system. The cap is reduced annually in line with the EU's climate target, ensuring that emissions decrease overtime. Companies can buy allowances for CO2 emissions. f an installation or operator reduce their emissions, they can either keep the spare allowances to use in the future or sell them. The declining cap offers companies certainty about the scarcity of allowances long term and ensures that allowances have market value. covers emissions from around 10,000 installations in the energy sector and manufacturing industry, as well as aircraft operators flying within the EU and departing to Switzerland and the United Kingdom - or around 40% of the EU's emissions.	•Reduce GHG emissions	•Reduce GHG emissions	EU	Current	Economic instrument	1.Lack of incentives	2.Chemical

No.	Policy instrument	Short description	CBBE - strategy & means	CBBE - strategy & means	Region	Time-frame	Type of instrument	Barrier addressed	Sector
96	DEI+ vergassing van reststromen (in English: subsidy gasification of residual streams)	This subsidy can be requested for the execution of a demonstration project, aimed at the gasification of waste streams (i.e., biogenic, or mixed). The installation converts these residues to renewable energy carriers, such as green gas, biofuel, or to a chemical. The entire gasification chain, including pre-treatment, torrefaction, gasification, and purification is eligible.	•Rs (repair, recycle, refuse, reuse, reduce, ...)	•Support material and/or energy (resource) use efficiency	NL	planned/proposed	Economic instrument	1.Lack of incentives	2.Chemical
97	EU landfill Directive 1999/31/EC	Sets out strict operational requirements for landfill sites that EU countries must implement in national strategies to progressively reduce the amount of biodegradable waste sent to landfills to 10% in 2035. Landfill facilities may not accept used tyres or waste which is liquid, flammable, explosive or corrosive, or from hospitals and medical and veterinary practices only waste that has been treated may be landfilled. National authorities must ensure that the price operators charge for disposing of waste covers all the costs involved from opening to final closure of the site. Allows EU countries to use economic instruments and other measures to encourage applying the waste hierarchy	•Rs (repair, recycle, refuse, reuse, reduce, ...)	•Stimulate cascading use	EU	current	Direct regulation	1.Lack of incentives	5.All
98	PLASTEKO Project	Improving regional policies for a more circular management of plastic and its waste, in all its phases: from promoting alternative disposable materials, to initiatives for management and separate collection, up to combating dispersion in water and the environment of plastics and monitoring microplastics. This is the goal of Plasteco, the Interreg project in which the Lombardy Region actively participates, involving universities, research institutions, and private companies as stakeholders, members of the regional observatory for the circular economy and energy transition	•Rs (repair, recycle, refuse, reuse, reduce, ...)	•Support material and/or energy (resource) use efficiency	Regional - Lombardy (IT)	current	Information and advice sharing system	2.Lack of information	1.Plastics
99	Textile Pact Memorandum of Understanding	Promote policies and actions aimed at fostering the development of the circular economy of the Prato textile district in Tuscany region, Italy.	•Stimulate the use of alternative/renewable sources e.g. biomass, by-products, wastes	•Support material and/or energy (resource) use efficiency	Regional - Tuscany (IT)	current	Other strategies	2.Lack of information	4.Textiles
100	Next Generation Prato	It is the strategic and operative document with which the Municipality of Prato and the main actors of the productive economic fabric share the strategy and related projects to take advantage of the opportunities arisen thanks to the National Recovery and Resilience Plan, and take a significant step towards the ecological, digital and circular transition of the city.	•Stimulate the use of alternative/renewable sources e.g. biomass, by-	•Support material and/or energy (resource) use efficiency	Regional - Tuscany (IT)	current	Other strategies	3.Lack of collaboration	5.All

No.	Policy instrument	Short description	CBBE - strategy & means	CBBE - strategy & means	Region	Time-frame	Type of instrument	Barrier addressed	Sector
			products, wastes						
101	Toscana Carbon Neutral 2050 Strategy (TCN2050)	The Strategy is committed to making emission reduction actions current, precise and measurable. The goal is to implement immediate actions and achieve, even before 2050 set as the European Union's deadline, a zero emission balance. It is proposed to do this in two ways: on the one hand by reducing emissions, overcoming the model of the traditional economy for sustainable ways of producing and consuming, and on the other hand by proposing a real regional green plan, so that trees and plants enter the spaces of our cities and can, as real filters, make the air we breathe better and absorb the climate-altering gases in the atmosphere. This document has, as mentioned, the goal of carbon neutrality to 2050 and is implemented through the adoption of Action Plans with a validity of 10-year period. The first of these is valid for the period 2020-2030.	•Reduce GHG emissions	•Stimulate the use of alternative/renewable sources e.g. biomass, by-products, wastes	Regional - Tuscany (IT)	current	Other strategies	2.Lack of information	
102	Funding Guideline Repair Premium Saxony (Förderrichtlinie Reparaturbonus Sachsen)	Private actors or companies in Saxony (Germany) can apply for subsidy for repairing electronic and electrical devices. The subsidy covers up to 50 % of repair costs, minimum 75 € in total and maximum 200 € per repaired	•Rs (repair, recycle, refuse, reuse, reduce, ...)		Regional - Saxony (GER)	current	Economic instrument	1.Lack of incentives	
103	Packaging Law (Verpackungsgesetz)	Germany's packaging law sets requirements for the design and collection of packaging (waste): e.g. Packagings have to be reduced to the minimum amount necessary to ensure safety, hygiene and acceptance by consumer, to be designed so that it can be recycled, reusability and use of secondary resources shall be increased (no quantitative target), producers of packaging have to participate in waste collection schemes, packaging waste has to be collected separately, producers and retailers have to take back empty packaging, 55-90 % of collected waste has to be recycled (quota depends on type of waste), waste collection schemes have to design collection fees in a way that incentivizes the use of materials that can be recycled	•Rs (repair, recycle, refuse, reuse, reduce, ...)	•Support material and/or energy (resource) use efficiency	Germany	current	Direct regulation	1.Lack of incentives	1.Plastics
104	Circular Economy Law (KrWG, Kreislaufwirtschaftsgesetz)	Recycling quota for municipal waste (50 % in 2020, rising to 65 % in 2035), waste hierarchy, defines waste vs. byproducts and end of waste status, requires separate collection of waste for recycling, ban on mixing of dangerous wastes, "product liability", states (Länder) have to create waste management plans and create waste prevention programmes	•Stimulate the use of alternative/renewable sources e.g. biomass, by-products, wastes	•Rs (repair, recycle, refuse, reuse, reduce, ...)	Germany	current	Direct regulation	1.Lack of incentives	5.All

No.	Policy instrument	Short description	CBBE - strategy & means	CBBE - strategy & means	Region	Time-frame	Type of instrument	Barrier addressed	Sector
105	Funding programmes for wood construction	Some German states (Bavaria, Baden-Württemberg, Hamburg) provide subsidies for the use of wood in construction (buildings)	•Stimulate the use of alternative/renewable sources e.g. biomass, by-products, wastes		Germany	current	Economic instrument	1.Lack of incentives	3.Construction
106	Sewage sludge ordinance	recycling quota for phosphorus from 2029 (50-80 % depending on circumstances)	•Stimulate the use of alternative/renewable sources e.g. biomass, by-products, wastes		Germany	current	Direct regulation	1.Lack of incentives	
107	EU Strategy for Sustainable and Circular Textiles	This document outlines a strategic approach by the European Commission to address sustainability and circularity in the textile industry. The document proposes various measures, regulations, and initiatives to guide and regulate the actions of stakeholders in the textile sector towards more sustainable practices. By setting out goals, strategies, and proposed actions, the document serves as a governance tool to influence behavior, promote compliance with sustainability objectives, and drive systemic change in the textile industry.	•Support material and/or energy (resource) use efficiency	•Stimulate the use of alternative/renewable sources e.g. biomass, by-products, wastes	EU	current	Information and advice sharing system	2.Lack of information	4.Textiles

ANNEX II: LITERATURE REVIEWED FROM RESOURCE AND ENVIRONMENTAL ECONOMICS

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ANNEX III: LIST OF POLICY INSTRUMENTS PER SECTOR USED IN SURVEY

Textile Sector: list of policy instruments

- Quota for use of recycled (and bio-based) materials: Quota for recycled and bio-based materials in textiles production and imports.
- Ecodesign criteria: Mandatory standards for durability, repairability, and recyclability, including imports.
- Ban on Destruction of Unsold Goods: Ban on destroying unsold goods to discourage overproduction.
- Public procurement of textiles without fossil-based content: Procurement of textiles without fossil-based content.
- Sustainability criteria: Criteria for textiles to be eligible for quotas and public procurement, e.g., EU Renewable Material Directive.
- Innovation subsidy for textile reuse or recycling: Subsidy for innovative textile reuse or recycling practices and technologies.
- “Green VAT”: Reduced VAT on reused or recycled textiles.
- Carbon tax: Tax on fossil feedstocks in textiles production.
- Innovation subsidy for bio-based textiles: Subsidy for developing new technologies and practices for bio-based textiles.
- Environmental tax on “fast fashion”: Tax on fast fashion textiles, fibers, yarns, and fabrics to limit waste and pollution.

Chemical Sector: list of policy instruments

- Quota for biobased feedstock shares in chemicals production: Quota for using biological resources in chemicals production, phasing out fossil feedstock by 2050.
- Product subsidy: Subsidy for non-fossil chemicals, e.g., reduced VAT.
- Sustainability criteria and cap: Quota fulfillment subject to sustainability criteria, including mandatory GHG reductions and biomass bans from high-value areas.
- Phase out: Final ban on fossil feedstocks by 2050.
- Innovation subsidy for low toxicity novel products: Subsidy for developing low-risk, toxic-free chemicals and decontamination technologies.
- Thresholds: Limits for substances of concern that inhibit reuse and recycling.
- Extended criteria and monitoring data: Extended criteria for chemical permissions considering recycling and reuse.
- Innovation subsidies: Subsidy for developing and marketing novel biobased chemicals.
- Carbon tax: Tax on fossil feedstocks in chemicals production and low-value biomass uses.

Plastic Sector: list of policy instruments

- Quota for use of recycled material: Producers must use a certain percentage of recycled plastics in products, e.g., 30% in automotive by 2035.
- Ecodesign criteria: Ambitious product criteria for non-packaging plastics to improve repair and recycling, e.g., restriction on colored PET.
- Subsidy for bio-based carbon: Subsidy for producers of durable non-packaging plastics made from sustainable biomass, e.g., bio-based plastics in window frames.

- Sustainability criteria and cap: Subsidy payments subject to sustainability criteria, including GHG reductions and biomass bans from high-value areas, e.g., 70% lower life cycle carbon emissions.
- Innovation subsidy: circularity: Subsidies for innovative technologies and products related to reuse, repair, or recycling of non-packaging plastics.
- Fossil carbon tax: Tax on fossil resources used by producers of non-packaging plastics, potentially very high to be effective.
- Ban of non-packaging plastic products or components: Ban on certain plastic products or parts with sustainable alternatives, expanding until waste and emissions targets are met.
- Innovation subsidy: bioplastics: Subsidies for innovative bioplastics technologies and durable bioplastic products, e.g., bioplastics from biomass waste.
- Carbon price for non-durable bioplastics: Carbon price on single-use and short-life bio-based plastics to prevent overuse of forest biomass and limit GHG emissions.
- Forest carbon subsidy: Subsidy for forest owners to increase carbon storage, ensuring biomass is harvested only when it's a more efficient climate mitigation option.
- Removal of bioenergy and fossil subsidies: Removal of bioenergy subsidies (except for innovative bioenergy) and fossil subsidies to shift biomass resources to the material sector.

Construction Sector: list of policy instruments

- Ecodesign criteria: Design for reuse, disassembly, durability, adaptability, repair, and minimizing material intensity.
- Sustainability criteria: Criteria for biobased construction materials to be eligible for the quota, e.g., EU Renewable Material Directive.
- Quota/target for use of biobased and recycled material: Targets for biobased and recycled materials in new buildings, with higher targets for public procurement.
- Innovation subsidies: Subsidies for developing and using innovative bio-based construction materials.
- Innovation subsidy for circular technologies or practices: Subsidies for innovative circular technologies or practices, e.g., use of recycled materials.
- Material tax: Tax on virgin raw materials for construction, including imports.
- Subsidy for refurbishment: Subsidy for building refurbishment.
- Demolition standards: Requirements for demolition to increase reuse, upcycling, and recycling of materials, encouraging waste reduction and refurbishment.
- Carbon credit/subsidy: Bio-based building materials ensuring long-term carbon storage (e.g., 50+ years) are exempt from the tax and receive a credit/subsidy.
- Carbon tax: Tax on lifecycle GHG emissions of building materials not covered by current carbon pricing, including short-life biomass materials.

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